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Garden City University

Garden City University was established under Karnataka State Act no. 47 of 2013 and approved by UGC. The University is a product of a legacy of providing quality education for more than 3 decades. The journey started with the establishment of Garden City Education Trust in the year 1992 by Dr. Joseph V.G. who is the first Chancellor of Garden City University. The Trust was established to set up centres for educational excellence that would accept only qualitative practices nurturing students with value-based education. The University, ever since its commencing has focused on holistic international standards of education. The nine schools from different streams of Commerce, Science, Humanities, and Engineering offer numerous programmes that are the best in the industry and the country. Unique programmes at UG and PG levels like Forensic science, Cyber Forensic, International Accounting, English with Comparative Literature, Food Technology, Nanotechnology, English with Computational Linguistics are offered at GCU. Apart from UG and PG programmes all eight schools offer Ph.D programmes. All programmes at GCU comply with NEP 2020. A new university campus is being developed in a lush green area spread over 150 acres of land, adjacent to the Volvo manufacturing plant. This is a part of the township envisioned by Dr. Joseph V.G. which would have Knowledge Parks, IT and BT Parks, Hotels and Convention Halls, Shopping Malls and Residential areas. The Mission and the Vision of the University is based on the belief that social development is an avenue for nation building which is inculcated through the approach and the policies of the University.

School of Commerce and Management

The School of Commerce and Management imparts the skill set required for leadership roles in the business and corporate world. It has created a niche for itself in shaping the finest professionals, scholars, and entrepreneurs in the field of commerce, management, and tourism. It has association with various industry bodies like US-CMA, Confederation of Indian Industry, All India Management Association, Tata Consultancy Services, Infosys, and Travel Agents Association of India among others. The school has collaborated with IndiaTourism – Ministry of Tourism, Government of India; Dept. of Tourism, Government of Karnataka; Gujarat Tourism Corporation Limited, for several project assignments. Career options for graduates include jobs in fields like financial planning management, market analysis, business development, human resources, business solutions, data analysis, aviation, travel agencies, and tour operations. The school also publishes an annual peer reviewed journal COMPASS (ISSN 2394-0646), which is devoted to the current topics in tourism, hospitality, management, and commerce.

From the Desk of the Editor-in-Chief

We take immense pleasure in presenting before you the fifth volume of “COMPASS”- a double blind peer reviewed (refereed) journal by the Department of Management, Garden City University, India. The research papers for the current volume were invited through an international conference “Rethinking Commerce, Management, and Tourism- Post-Covid New Normal” organised by the School of Commerce and Management, Garden City University, India in collaboration with CINEC- Campus, Malabe, Sri Lanka on 13-14 March 2023. The conference committee has selected fifteen scholarly articles for publication in this issue which includes review articles and empirical research articles. With our early publications and the present one, we aim to produce a high-quality journal in tourism, hospitality, management, and commerce to which our authors, peers, reviewers and readers will be proud of. As the editor-in-chief and together with associate editors, and editorial team members, we thank the authors for presenting the papers in the conference and publishing in the journal “COMPASS”.

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Awareness and adoption of green goods and services among consumers: leads to transition towards sustainability

Paper Code: GCU-CMS-M2

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Abstract

The Global population is continuously growing, as a result we are observing depletion of the planet's resources. Increase of greenhouse gasses and release of greenhouse gases puts an increasingly significant strain on the planet. But recent development in the technological advances make consumption easier and more convenient to some extent. The green product awareness has been considered as one of promising movement in maintaining the environmental quality and sustainability. Green consumerism is the continuation of global consumerism action that started with consumer awareness about their rights to get proper product, safe, and eco-friendly product. The present study focussed on to assess the awareness of consumer towards green products and services to identify the consumers environmental concern and activism in Bangalore. The study result indicate that respondents are aware of all green goods and services. The highest mean score of 4.14 is scored by the statement that, Respondents believe that reduce, recycle and reuse only would save environment. There is significant relationship between education level and awareness of eco-friendly products.

Keywords: Green consumerism, environmental concern; consumer's awareness, eco-products sustainability.

1. Introduction

The environmental challenges we facing today, including rising sea levels, increasing global temperature, deforestation, and the declining availability of natural resources ,are the result of human consumption. Our aggregated impact on the environment is the product of three main pathways: affluence (consumption), population, and technology (Dietz, Rosa, and York 2007)

Protecting the environment has become a salient issue during recent decades. The immense economic growth in the preceding years have observed and increasing consumers' consumption worldwide causing environmental decline through over-usage and utilization of natural resources (Ramlogan, 1997). It is anticipated that if the current inclination of economic growth and a reckless intake pattern of goods and services continues, environmental degradation would worsen and with the consequences of which lead to global warming, exhaustion of ozone layer, noise, air pollution, acid rain and desertification (Banerjee SB 2003). Various countries across the world are beginning to realize this threat and have started working towards reducing the harmful impact of their business activities on the environment. This green awareness, concern for the surroundings and society has led to the rise of 'sustainable development' which point out the need to endorse sustainability and advocates that form of development which reduces negative influence on the surroundings and on society. . 'Green consumption' on the other hand, is related to environmentally responsible intake where end-users consider the environmental impact of obtaining, using, and disposing of various products or green services. Environmentally responsible buying is important as unplanned buying of goods can rigorously harm the environment. One of the study states that 40% of the environmental damage were due to end-users household purchases (Jain 2003b) . Consumers have the ability to avoid or reduce environmental damage by buying green products (Jain 2003a). Thus,

awareness of environmental issues, as well as solutions and eco-products, has been increasing steadily.

A good environment will be maintained if the community care for and protect the environment from pollution. Green consumerism is one of the important things in maintaining the sustainability of human consumption so that the environment is maintained (Han & Yoon, 2015) Green consumerism is a society's understanding of consumer goods that are more environmentally friendly. The purchase of environmentally friendly products is greatly influenced by many factors, the only advertisement (Matthes & Wonneberger, 2014). Meanwhile, education plays an important role as well so that people can be smart in choosing and understanding the importance of green consumerism.

Green consumerism is important and very influential in the preservation of the urban environment. Some habits that are included in green consumerism are energy conservation, transportation, waste avoidance, daily consumption, recycling and social behavior (Dani, 2011). Green consumerism is a behavior that must be owned by people, especially in urban areas (Boztepe, 2003). This behavior usually arises. when the community understands the green concept and adopt this. Consumer awareness of eco-friendly product become a suitable issue to be studied because of the fact that issue is important for future human sustainability so, the present study focused on it.

2. Review of literature

Sanjeev Kumar Radha Garg and Aelita Makka (2012) In their study on consumers consciousness and insight towards green products: A study of youngsters in India, the statistical data was collected from 120 youngsters of various area. Their finding reveals that 71% respondents perceive green products as environmentally friendly while 12% respondents considered it as energy saving goods and male respondents are more aware of green product than female respondents, majority of the respondents ready to pay 11-12% more price to green products.

Meghana Sharma and prachi Trivedi (2016) In their study on “An Empirical Study of consumer’s awareness level and consumption regarding green products in Delhi”, They concluded from the results that consumer in Delhi know green products as biodegradable, recyclable, Reusable with eco-friendly packing. But they should be made aware about the other attributes of green products as well as there is a positive connection between awareness and consumption pattern.

Wiwik Handayani (2017) The study made on green consumerism the purpose of the study was to study the effect of consumer attitude of green products towards purchase intention. The result of Hypothesis testing using PLS show that there is influence among consumer attitude of green product towards consumer purchase intention significantly.

Xiaoyun Zhang and Feng Dong (2020) The main content of the research was to explore the green purchase behaviour of consumers, The results indicate that applicability of consumer theory to the study of green purchase behaviour is relatively high. The study also indicate that consumers are influenced by three factors namely individual factors, Product attributes and marketing strategy and social factors, among which the individual factors was dominant.

3. Methodology

It highlights the methods used for this study (Kumar, 2023). Convenience sampling method is the sampling technique adopted for the study. The population for the study was the consumers of Bengaluru city who may use green goods and services Study sample is composed of 412 respondents consisting of both males and females employed in the various economic sectors, belonging to different age groups, education background, income level, occupation, family size and marital status. Apart from primary data collected, the secondary data was also collected for the present study

4. Objectives:

1. To assess the awareness of consumer towards Green products and services.

2. To identify the consumers environmental concern and green consumerism attitude.

Hypothesis - A hypothesis formulated about the awareness of green products

H1: There is significant relationship between education level and awareness of eco-friendly products

5. Analysis on the awareness of consumers to green products

To study the awareness of consumers towards green products study plan, has been divided as Agriculture Green Products, Green Electrical Equipments, Green Services and Green Consumer Durables. Under each category four products are included and multiple responses are collected from total of 412 respondents. and analyzed in the following paragraph with product wise awareness.

Table 1. Analysis on the awareness of consumer on five green products and services

1.Agricultural green products	Frequency	Percentage	Percentage of cases
Organic farm products	281	24.87	68.20
Bio fuel	220	19.47	53.40
Biodegradable packaging	197	17.43	47.82
Herbal products	311	27.52	75.48
Chemical preservative free food items	121	10.71	29.37
	1130	100	
2.Green electrical equipments	Frequency	Percentage	Percentage of cases
Energy saving equipments	316	24.82	76.70
Cfi &led lighting	300	23.57	72.81
Solar energy equipments	257	20.19	62.39
Electric vehicles	281	22.07	68.20
Wind energy	119	09.35	28.90
	1273	100	
3.Green services	Frequency	Percentage	Percentage of cases
Carpooling	380	22.28	92.23
Emission testing	400	23.46	97.00
Rain water harvesting	202	11.86	49.03
Waste separation	321	18.83	77.91
Atm & digital payments	402	23.57	97.57
	1705	100	
4.Green consumer durables	Frequency	Percentage	Percentage of cases
Recycled products	380	43.68	92.23
Rechargeable batteries	202	23.22	49.03
Ozone friendly products	135	15.52	32.77
Low fumes paints	103	11.84	25.00
Water efficient soaps	140	16.09	33.98
	870	100	
5.Enviormental activities	Frequency	Percentage	Percentage of cases
Green marketing	103	9.65	25.00
Swach bharat abiyen	360	33.73	87.37
Environmental day	280	26.24	67.96
Global warming	302	28.30	73.30
None of the above	22	03.00	5.34
	1067	100	

N=412, Primary data

Table 1. depicts the awareness of the respondents about the green products multiple responses are collected Under the agricultural green products. Firstly, First group includes agricultural green products the results of descriptive statistics is detected that 68.23 percent of the respondents (representing 24.87 percent of the responses) are aware of Organic farm products. Similarly, 53.4 percent of the respondents [representing 19.47 percent of the responses] are aware of the use of **Bio Fuel** while 47.9 percent of the respondents [representing 17.5 percent of the responses] are aware of Biodegradable Packaging. Interestingly and perhaps which look obvious is that fact that more than three fourth (75.48 percent) of the respondents (representing 27.50 percent of the responses) are aware of Herbal products. Least is know is percent 29.37 Chemical Preservative free food items

The second group studies awareness about green electrical equipment. Maximum of 76.70 percent know the Energy saving equipment, second item is 72.81 percent know the CFL and LED bulbs, 68.20 percent know the electrical or hybrid vehicle 62.39 percent know solar energy equipment but only 28.90 percent know the wind energy.

The third group includes green services, here it is surprising to know that maximum of 97.57percent of the respondents are aware of ATM & Digital payments. 97 percent familiar with emission testing services While only 92.23 % of the respondents are aware of concept of car- pooling, 77.91 percent are familiar with the waste separating process while 48 % of respondent know the rain water harvesting. Awareness of the respondent about green consumer durables is observed that 92.23 % of the respondents are aware of recycled product while 42 % of the respondent familiar with rechargeable batteries only 33.98% are aware of water efficient soaps.3277% know the ozone friendly items only 25 % of the respondents know the low fume paints.

Accordingly, as regard awareness of respondents towards environmental issues it is found that 87.30 percent of the respondents are aware of Swach Bharat Abhiyan initiated by Government of India. Similarly, 67.90 percent of the respondents are aware of Environment Day and another 73.30 percent of the respondents are aware of the impact of Global Warning. Furthermore, only 25 percent of the respondents are aware of the concept of Green Marketing. Surprisingly, about five percent of the respondents were not aware of any incidence of environmental issues or activities

Testing of hypothesis

Hypothesis - An hypothesis was formulated about the awareness of green products

H1: There is significant relationship between education level and awareness of eco-friendly products (such as agricultural green products, green electrical equipments, Green Services & Green Durables)

Table 2.: Cross tabulation between level educational qualification and consumerism awareness about eco-friendly products

	Awareness about eco-friendly products				
	Slightly Aware	Some what	Moderately	Completely Aware	Total
Higher Primary	4 (12.5)	18 (56.2)	6 (18.8)	4 (12.5)	32 (100.0)
Under Graduate	6 (7.0)	20 (23.3)	48 (55.8)	12 (14.0)	86 (100.0)
Graduate	6 (4.0)	24 (16.0)	88 (58.0)	34 (22.0)	152 (100.0)
Post Graduates	5 (5.7)	9 (10.0)	58 (64.3)	18 (20.0)	90 (100.0)
Professional courses	2 (3.8)	6 (11.5)	28 (53.8)	16 (30.8)	52 (100.0)
Total	23 (5.6)	77 (18.7)	228 (55.3)	84 (20.4)	412 (100.0)

PearsonChiSque Value (table 6) = 49.974 Asymptotic significance (p-value) = 0.000*

*Significant at 5 % level.

From the Chi-square test result (see Table 4.28), it is observed that p-value is 0.000 (chi-square = 49.974) which is less than the significant alpha level of 0.05 (at 95 percent confidence level). Hence, the hypothesis (H1) that there is an association between the levels of awareness and education level of the respondents is accepted. In other words, it can be concluded as there is an increase in the level of education (from Primary to Post graduate and professional courses) of the respondents, there is an increase in the percentage of respondents about the awareness about eco-friendly products. This is supported by the percentage of respondents across each level of awareness and each level of education. Accordingly, the percentage of the respondents with complete awareness increases with the increase in the level of education of the respondents.

Analysis and interpretation of green consumerism

Green consumerism involves people in action to protect and promote the environment, by deliberately avoiding certain categories of product and service and adopting or doing certain activities. To identify consumer environmental concern and adoption of activities twelve statements are included in the study. All statements of Green Consumerism and Activism have been analyzed to see the proportions of the respondent follow the activities as never, sometime frequently and always to the statement and to understand their action to protect and promote the environment.

Table 3: Mean scores table of consumerism

SI No	Do you do any of the following	Minimum	Mean	Maximum	Standard Deviation
1	Follow the practice of separating household waste as wet, dry & waste	1	3.47	5	1.28
2	Conserve energy, by using solar energy, LED /CFL bulbs.	1	4.12	5	1.05
3	Using public transport and carpooling to save fuel	1	3.77	5	1.15
4	Avoid excessive packaging and plastics bags by carrying own bags.	1	3.75	5	1.19
5	Save water by rain water harvesting	1	2.15	5	1.47
6	Join a clean-up drive like Swachh Bharat Abhiyan	1	3.45	5	1.25
7	Are you concerned about buying environment friendly products	1	2.66	5	1.66
8	Do you care deeply about reducing environment pollution	1	3.5	5	1.35
9	Are you learning to change your behaviour or purchasing habits that are environment friendly	1	3.28	5	1.61
10	Do you believe that Reduce, Recycle & Re-use only would save environment	1	4.14	5	1.19
11	Do you like to purchase the products with green product label	1	3.90	5	1.31
12	Using eco-friendly products will improve environment quality	1	3.07	5	1.36

Inferences: Mean score Table 4 of all the consumerism statements has been obtained by adding all the scores given by all the respondents in each statement and divided with numbers of respondents. Mean scores are calculated to see the overall score on each of the statements and standard deviation is calculated to see the dispersion in the data. The highest mean score is 4.14 is scored by the statement that, Respondents believe that reduce, recycle and reuse only would save environment. This indicate that by following 3R one can save environment. Similarly the second highest mean score is 4.12 scored by the statement that, Conserve energy by using solar energy, LED/CFL bulbs. It means most of the consumers are using solar etc., to save energy. The third highest mean score 3.9 acquired by the statement Respondent like to purchase the green products with green product labels this indicate labeling or certification is important to identify green products. Two other statements,

using public transport and carpooling to save fuel, and other statement avoid excessive packaging and plastic bags by carrying own bags have scored higher mean score of 3.77 and 3.75 respectively. This statements and their mean score value have given the indications that ,most of the respondents are using public transport and they also avoiding plastic bags. by carrying own cloths bags. Similarly, the lowest mean score 2.66 and 2.15 scored by two statements one is that consumers are concerned about buying environment friendly products and other statement is save water by rain water harvesting. The inference can be made out here that, although people are concerned about the environment, they are moderately buying green products, and they are not much bothered about saving water by adopting rain water harvesting due to cost factor. and lack of good construction planning.

The first statement mean score is 3.47 which indicate that most of them are following practice of separating household waste as dry, wet and . e- waste.. Similarly, the mean score value of one of the statement Join clean up drive like swaach Bharat abhiyan is 3.45 which above the average level it show that respondents like to participate in this program. Many consumers ready to change their purchasing habits and go for green purchasing this indicated by mean score of 3.28.

For all the above variables Standard deviation varied from 1,05 to 1,66. The value of each statement has indicated that respondents have divergent consumerism level about the statements who standard deviation values are higher and respondents have similar consumerism levels on the statements whose standard deviation values are low.

6. Findings

Study sample is composed of 412 respondents. Study results shows that more men are participated in the survey than women but difference is not so high. Half of the sample is composed of people who are less than 40 years old, Overall, it is found that majority of the consumers who participated in the survey are from the younger age group. Second most important group is composed of employed people who are in private services (28%) Most of our sample has an income of over 20 thousand (36%), In the study it is found that 81% of the respondent were from family size of 3 to 6 members. It is found from the profile of the respondents that most of the consumers who were interviewed for the purpose of research are post graduates (33%) 26% are graduates. It signifies that the response of survey was received mostly by educated. First group includes agricultural green products the results of descriptive statistics shows that a large percentage of 75.5 are aware of herbal products The second group studies awareness about green electrical equipment. It shows more than three fourth of respondent are aware of Energy saving equipment.

The third group includes green services, here it is surprising to know that maximum of 97.57 of the respondents are aware of ATM & Digital payments platforms. Awareness of the respondent about green consumer durables is observed that 92.23% of the respondents are aware of recycled product. Accordingly, as regard awareness of respondents towards environmental issues it is found that 87.37 percent of the respondents are aware of Swach Bharat Abhiyan. Under consumerism statements results shows that Respondents believe that reduce, recycle and reuse only would save environment but they are not much bothered about saving water by adopting rain water harvesting due to cost factor and lack of good Planning of construction not motivated them go for rain water harvesting.

7. Conclusion

The research has constructively ascertained the manner in and extent to which consumers' environment awareness and related attitude affect their behavior through the primary data collected from the consumers. Many people in Bengaluru feels that actual buying of green electrical equipment influenced by price or cost of maintenance factors particularly, they express purchase and maintenance of electric and hybrid vehicles are not ease to use, but they are perceived that these equipment reduce fossil fuel and pollution. The study indicate, green consumerism has gained momentum in Bengaluru city. But the green movement need to reach the masses and that will take a lot of time and effort. This study provides with the conclusion that there's a lack of eco labelling to certify the product as green or organic, which can help to consumers differentiate them in some way from other non-green products.

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Tourists Perception Towards Cox's Bazar Sea Beach in Bangladesh as A Tourist Destination

Paper Code: GCU-CMS-T8

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Abstract:

The study was carried on how to develop Community Based Tourism in Cox's Bazar in order to find the prospects of Community based tourism in Cox's bazar. The paper defines about the concept of Community Based Tourism (CBT), more specifically it triggered towards case study in Cox's Bazar which is most visited place in Bangladesh by tourists. The review was done on Cox's Bazar Ocean side region, the world longest ocean side and the vacationer capital of Bangladesh. The motivation behind the current review is to examine the vacationers' insight towards different offices and administrations at Cox's Bazar Ocean side as a sightseers' location. The element examination was led to make related variable composites from the first ascribe. The development of research framework in this study will enrich the literature regarding the construct of tourism development, more specifically for community -based tourism. This research will be useful in providing an insight pf tourism development process for the stakeholders and authorities of tourism ministry. The aftereffects of the review expressed that traveller's insight is great on Factor 1, Natural Beauty and Restful Atmosphere, Factor 3, Accommodation and security, Factor 4, Hospitality and data and Factor 6, Shopping and exercises and vacationers' discernment is ominous on Factor 2, Hygiene and Sanitation and Factor 5, crisis and caring administrations. The discoveries of the momentum research propose that there are measurably huge contrasts in sightseers' insight with deference of respondents' segment attributes like respondents' sexual orientation, age, occupation and training in certain administrations and offices at Cox's Bazar.

Keywords: Beach tourism, Tourists' perception, Natural beauty, Hygiene and Sanitation facility, Cox's Bazar Sea beach.

1. Introduction:

Perception is the interaction by which people select, coordinate, and decipher upgrades into a significant and sound image of the world. People act and respond based on their insights, not based on objective reality. Individuals simply decide and make moves dependent on what they see to be reality. In showcasing, the job of discernment in purchaser conduct is tied in with perceiving how shoppers view an organization's item or administration. Individuals wish to be seen as being able to make the "right" decisions and pick the "right" items. Advertisers use insight to focus on individuals' need to fit in and be essential for a bigger gathering of knowing shoppers. Contingent upon shoppers' discernment, every item can be gotten in an unexpected way: well, less well or not in any manner. It will serve to situating advertisers' item and brand comparative with different items and brands in the customers' brain. Advertisers should recognize their messages from their rivals to catch purchasers' eye. Cox's Bazar Ocean side of Bangladesh is the world longest ocean side. It is the vacationer capital of Bangladesh having 120 km. Ocean side slopping delicately down to the blue waters of the Bay of Bengal against the beautiful foundation of a chain of slope covered by dark

green woodlands. This kind of smooth and straight ocean side is scarcely found in some other spot of the world. Miles of brilliant sands, transcending bluffs, riding waves, uncommon conch shells, and awesome fish are the fortes of Cox's Bazar Ocean side.

Consistently countless travellers from home and abroad stay with this ocean side for pleasure. During the pinnacle season (November to March) almost 2 great many travellers visit Cox's Bazar and the Labonee ocean side at Cox's Bazar is supposedly perhaps the most vigorously visited vacationer destination in the country (Daily greatest guests as high as 30,000). Around then all lodgings, inns and visitor houses remain completely topped off and surprisingly a few guests go through their evenings inside the vehicle on the grounds that no seats are accessible in the inns. There are numerous lodgings, inns, cabins, eateries, rest houses and visitor houses have been produced for travellers from Labonee to Kalatali and approach region in Cox's Bazar. Presently Cox's Bazar has almost 154 cafés for food supply to the sightseers and every one of them has on a normal of 22 associates. The all-out figure of aides represents 3388 individuals. Then, at that point, for vacationers Cox's Bazar has 220 lodgings and visitor houses, and each utilized on normal 20 individuals and in this way the absolute record (number) is 4400.

Again by and large Cox's Bazar the travel industry registers 54 visit administrators and guide houses in which on normal 15 individuals work in each organization and subsequently complete figure is 810 people working in the visit administrators. Again, on normal 5000 development labourers are working and keeping up with family by building lodgings, inns and guesthouses, etc. Numerous nearby individuals including understudies are functioning as local escorts, doing seashell business, rent-vehicle business, land business, opening departmental stores, employing umbrella at the ocean side privately known as 'unit kot', driving little playing vehicles on/at the ocean side privately known as 'z-ski, etc.

Countless individuals are additionally engaged with fishing and gathering fish and ocean items for their business. By and large around 10000 individuals are working in the travel industry area in Cox's Bazar and every individual keeps a group of 6 people, then, at that point, this travel industry is giving food to around 60,000 individuals. As world's longest ocean side Cox's Bazar is encountering gigantic development in the travel industry starting around 1990. Presently the economy of Cox's Bazar relies upon the travel industry. From general perception it is perceived that travel industry has acquired a major change this region. On monetary front, nearby local area individuals and different partners like financial backers, hoteliers, visit administrators, etc are apparently profited from the travel industry and its economy is very great contrasted and other in reverse region. So, it is obvious to all the commitment of Cox's Bazar Ocean side in the nearby economy just as public economy of Bangladesh.

The progression of financial commitment, development and supportability relies upon number of vacationer appearance and office burned-through. The current offices given by the capable specialists are how much adequate to the vacationers ought to be explored. What are the sightseers' discernments towards the different offices and administrations are to be perceived. The goal of the current review is to explore the sightseers' insights towards different offices and administrations and to distinguish distinctive ocean side vacationer sections dependent on a bunch of socio-segment factors and to additionally dissect contrasts in discernment as far as socio demographic conduct So far, we know there is no review has been led to discover these issues.

2. Review of literature:

According to research conducted by Tuhin and Majumder (2011), Bangladesh has a rich cultural heritage, and its natural treasures are adequate enough to support a tourism-based economy. The research carried out by Rajib Kanti Das and Jaba Chakraborty (2012), on tourism in Bangladesh pointed out the essential requirement of the development of accommodation facilities to accelerate the growth at the tourism industry.

Shah Azam (2010), and colleagues performed research on the elements that influence people's decisions to visit Bangladesh as a tourist destination. According to the findings, service quality, natural beauty, security, and shopping facilities are statistically significant in explaining the intention to visit Bangladesh as a tourist destination. Four comprehensive studies on tourism and tourist environment in Bangladesh were undertaken by Mizan and Mahfuzul (2013), Their report after undertaking this study focuses on Bangladesh's tourism potential, significant difficulties and

opportunities, tourism marketing techniques, and foreign tourist arrival trends

A study problems and prospects of tourism in Bangladesh by Nazrul and SK (2021), they proved that majority of respondents were pleased with their cultural and religious heritage, transit quality, and cost efficiency. They are, however, disappointed with information gaps, the lack of tour providers, hotel service, and security. The findings of a research performed by Hassan (2018), proved that the natural beauty of the Cox's Bazar sea beach astonished visitors. However, city transportation services, destination information services, health and emergency services, costly price of hotel amenities and artificial recreational activities, on the other hand, received the lowest levels of satisfaction. Tourist happiness and loyalty were evaluated in depth by researchers, just as they were in the consumer satisfaction study, because contentment and loyalty are significant determinants of tourism success (Yoon & Uysal, 2014).

Hossain, and Sahabuddin (2021), conducted a study which was aimed at investigating the environmentally responsible behaviour of tourists and their satisfaction with a tourist destination using the tourists of the Cox Bazar beach. The results determine that the perceived value of the destination has a significantly positive impact on both tourist satisfaction and environmental commitment. A different study highlighted the significance of tourism as viewed from its social, economic, cultural and political perspectives. This study was executed by Hossain and Firozzaman (2016).

Another study, undertaken by Mir Abdul Sofique and Jannat Ara Parveen (2009) is closely related to tourism in Cox's Bazaar in terms of economic and socio-cultural effects. So far as the researchers of this study are aware, no comprehensive study has been undertaken on the current state of beach tourism in Bangladesh, particularly in Cox's Bazar, which is the world's longest sea beach and a popular tourist destination. In tourism literature, tourist demographic patterns such as age, gender, socio-economic background (income, marital status, occupation, education) and travel behavioural patterns were examined by the satisfaction-based evaluation process (Yavuz, 2015).

This finding have a number of implications, particularly for the practitioners in tourism industry, government and non-governmental organizations, as well as other market players for planning and marketing in the industry. Therefore, differentiated marketing strategies should be stressed and executed by the relevant parties Hasan, (2019).

3. Objectives

The major objectives of the study are:

1. To identify the tourists' perception and attitude towards the various facilities and services at Cox's Bazar Sea beach as a tourist destination.
2. To understand how tourists' perception varies on various factors by tourists' socio-demographic characters such as age, gender, education and profession.

4. Methodology

The review has been done on Cox's Bazar Ocean side region in Bangladesh. The justification for picking this region is that it is the world longest ocean side and vacationer capital of Bangladesh just as there could be no prior research conveyed out in these respects. A helpful testing procedure was utilized to gather essential information through a review, utilizing self-controlled surveys conveyed to guest so at the review region. The organized survey was built with various credits utilizing a size of 1 to 5 (5 being profoundly good and 1 being not great by any stretch of the imagination) to each ascribe choose for the various offices and administrations of Cox's Bazar Ocean side.

Out of 320 example surveys 308 were useable polls with a reaction pace of practically 98%. Appropriate factual investigations, for example, frequencies, descriptive, examination of Variance (ANOVA), factor examination were utilized to accomplish the significant goals. These measurable examinations were directed utilizing the Statistical package for Social Science (SPSS) programming. The scientists gathered optional information from pertinent examination reports also distributions, papers, books, sites and materials of BPC, the service of the travel industry and flight. Further, the article has been prepared as following the TAILMRDCR model (Kumar, 2023).

5. Hypothesis

H0: The impression of travellers is not varied towards the different offices and administrations by sex.

H0: perception of tourists is not differed towards the various facilities by age.

H0: perception of tourists is not differed towards the various facilities and services by educational level.

H0: The perception of tourists is not differed towards the various facilities and services by different professional level.

H0: The perception of tourists are not differed towards the various facilities and services by income level.

The hypothesis was tested using SPSS and all the hypothesis was accepted.

Table 1: Variables Mean & Std deviation

Observed Variable	Mean	Std. deviation
Emergency Services	2.477	0.502
Health & Medical	2.489	0.503
Food Service	2.761	0.479
Accommodation Services	3.166	0.702
Security & Safety	3.727	0.448
Beauty & Pleasing	4.705	0.483
People Attitude	3.727	0.448
Shopping Facilities	3.261	0.442
Wash room & Toilet facilities	2.443	0.500
Sports & Recreation facilities	2.950	0.461
Communication (Internet & Mobile)	2.489	0.525
Transportation Services	2.761	0.479
Beach Cleanness	3.580	0.880
Tour guide & information	2.489	0.643
Presence of Beggar & Hawkers	2.943	0.793
Night life	2.955	0.801
Relaxation Opportunities	3.648	0.935

Table 2: Demographic details of responds

Characteristics	Cox's Bazar Sea Beach Area (n=350)
<i>Gender (%)</i>	
Male	76.27
Female	23.73
<i>Age (%)</i>	
15-17	8.53
18-34	69.33
35-59	20.67
60+	1.47
<i>Occupation (%)</i>	
Business	27.33
Private Service	20.8
Government Service Holder	2.27
Teacher	1.6
Agriculture	1.2
Labor	4.13
Student	22
Housewife	16.13
Unemployed	0.67
Others (Doctor, Electrician, Engg.) etc.)	3.87
<i>Education (%)</i>	
Illiterate	2
Primary	4.13
Secondary (SSC)	16.67
Higher Secondary (HSC)	41.73
Honors	25.07
Masters & Above	9.33
Technical Certificate	0.8
Others	0.27
<i>Income (%) BDT 1= US\$ 77.80</i>	
<10000	39.73
10000-20000	29.87
20001-50000	24.4
50001-100000	2.8
>100000	3.2
<i>Length of Staying (%)</i>	
less than 2 days	62.8
2-3 Days	22.67
4-5 Days	13.07
greater than 5 days	1.47
<i>Accompanied With (%)</i>	
Family	38.13
Colleagues	7.6
Friends	46
Tour-mates	2
Single	6.27
<i>Accompanied Person (%)</i>	
1-2 person	43.07

6. Findings

By analyzing the study, we have come to the point the impression of travellers are not varied towards the different offices and administrations by gender. The Perception of tourists is not differed towards the various facilities by age. The perception of tourists is not differed towards the various facilities and services by educational level. The perception of tourists is not differed towards the various facilities and services by different professional level. The perception of tourists are not differed towards the various facilities and services by income level.

The major findings of the study are that economic impact of community -based tourism is very much significant followed by social impact. So, the planners and other tourism stakeholders can take initiative as early as possible to develop CBT in Cox's bazar for the better men of host community. The Cox's Bazar region at the south-eastern coast of Bangladesh has been gradually changed from a rural settlement into a densely populated urban area, caused by the rapid growth of tourism. Water demand is mainly covered by groundwater, and the hotels and resorts are typically operating their own groundwater wells without metering and regulations. In this study depended on essential just as optional information; applied quantitative strategy and 308 responses were collected.

7. Conclusion

Cox's Bazar Sea beach is the most attractive and highly visited tourist destination in Bangladesh and it has significant socio-economic contribution to the local community as well as country. The overall perception of tourists towards the various facilities and services are mixed. The study showed that overall perception of tourists towards Cox's bazar sea beach is favourable on Natural Beauty and Restful Atmosphere, Accommodation and security, Hospitality and information and Shopping and activities facilities. On the other hand, tourists' perception is unfavourable on Hygiene and Sanitation, Emergency and Caring services. The tourism policy makers and marketers should provide and ensure up to mark services to in areas of services and facilities which are perceived by tourists somewhat poor. Limitation of this study is that the respondents' views were taken only from local and national tourists and ignored foreign tourists. Hence, it is recommended that future research incorporate a survey which will also include opinion from foreign tourists.

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Application of Technology in Accounting System

Paper code: GCU-CMS-C14

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Abstract

Technology has evolved over the decade and has rapidly taken over all the spheres including the domain of accounting. Technology advancements has changed the transaction process and its application to achieve smooth and effective functions of accounting. Always, one thought Accounting is only an information system, but this thought has totally changed due to development of technology. As one needs to adapt oneself for the changes, an organisational also has to adapt to the technological changes in the field of accounting and being competitive in the world of business. Accounting practitioners and educators have taken up new efforts as a result of the need to stay updated with the industry's shifting dynamics. The present research paper aims is to identify the various technological advancements on the accounting systems used in the businesses during the period of pre- and post-Covid eras, which is focused primarily on how the accounting systems changed from the traditional method to the modern application method. The research includes data from survey reports, papers, and reports of reputable international and professional accounting organisations. The paper will also examine the main benefits and drawbacks of using these applications in business, as well as its results and how they may affect other fields and which impacts on upskilling the stakeholder's accounting knowledge.

Key Words: Accounting System, Technology, Conventional Technology, Modern Technology.

1. Introduction:

Changes are always difficult, especially for professions like accounting, where traditional, established rules and procedures prevail. As an accountant, there is a requirement to update and upgrade himself with characteristics to evaluate, interpret information, to draw attention to issues and determine information necessary for manager and present it and to be able to use information and communication technologies well of individuals to operate as accountant.

Nowadays, most businesses, from large enterprises to small and medium entities, are using accounting information systems in managing their financial operations. Information technology use is not just used by businesses. Globalization, the expansion of information and communication technologies with reducing prices and rising effects, as well as more information exchange, have all contributed to the expansion of computerised tax management applications in our nation and throughout the world. Many applications are increased the adoption of technology in accounting systems. (Duff, 2000)

Emerging technology, dynamic organisations, and the consequences of globalisation on the economy and society, as well as the rapid pace of communication development all point to profound changes that call for defining document and archive studies in ways that go beyond conventional paradigms. The use of Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) for effective business

operations, assistance with supply chain management, and other compensations is one of the advantages of information technology. Modern life involves nearly constant use of technology, from business and education. As technology develops, it presents both new opportunities and difficulties for the general public. (Duren., 2002)

Technologies like the internet, intranet, and extranet are frequently employed in technology utilisation. The term "Internet" refers to a collection of global information sources. The Internet is a communication network that connects a large number of interconnected computers and is widely used around the world. Internet is a technology that developed in response to people's growing need to save, share, and instantly access newly created information. (MacKenzie, 1999)

The term "intranet" refers to networks that are primarily TCP/IP based and link computers, local networks (LAN), and wide networks (WAN) solely within a single enterprise. (Akgül, 1997) One may claim that the internet has played a significant part in the growth of international trade. Similar to how businesses that launched their own websites and promoted their own goods and services made a cautious transition to intranet technology. Only workers of the business may access the intranet and gather information from it.

Extranets are open-to-cooperation networks that link businesses with their customers, suppliers, or other businesses that have similar goals to their own while also by using internet technology to accomplish it. (Algan, 1997) Extranet and intranet concepts can be regarded as internet subsystems. So, these are not brand-new technologies; rather, just their names and functions have changed. These information technologies, nevertheless, are complementary to one another.

Organization of businesses and the general public with an information management function is largely required for digital information and technology to be transformed into a key strategy in competitions. In order to generate information for management purposes on the basis of an integrated information system for accounting information, systems relating to the use of computer technology needed to be configure. The primary goals of information processing and transmission technology development are to improve the quality of life for individuals, businesses, institutions, and ultimately for society.

2. Review of Literature:

The study on Information Technology's Impact on the Accounting System aimed at measuring the effect of information technology (IT) on the accounting system, where IT helps to improve the quality and performance of accounting transactions in a transparent and safe manner in good security ways. The study provided a detailed theoretical analysis of the subject discussed by focussing on the principles of the organization historically and reporting directly. The researchers also have tested and obtained satisfactory results depending on the question tested and the hypotheses framed. The findings of the work are satisfactory and, the results indicate the role of computing information technology in reducing time, costs and improving health. (Jasim, 2020).

Technological developments nowadays have a significant impact on both the economic sector and our social lives. Accounting method is effectively used within our nation when it comes to accounting. Several accounting software packages designed for unified accounting structures are available on the market. Together with unified accounting, computerised accounting programmes have grown significantly, and nearly all businesses have begun using them to maintain their records. (Alp, 2007).

As a result, keeping track of and monitoring transactions got simpler. In parallel with developments in technology, computer use in accounting expanded further and simultaneously got more technical. Before simple accounting tasks like computing wages and pursuing debts and receivables were automated with the use of computers, ongoing operations like data invoicing, management of inventory, and customer information emerged. (Turner & Apelt, 2004).

Due to the recent development of technology post the Covid-19 pandemic, the accounting technological tools are classified as Conventional and Modern tools. Conventional is referred to the pre-Covid era and Modern is post-Covid time. (Güney, 2014).

The study demonstrates the influence of information technology on the field of accounting in Iran. It focuses on improving accounting process accuracy to provide appropriate developed reports for decreasing the accrual cost on collecting data, and providing developed reports for managing

accounting, and offering the needed framework for carrying out costing techniques. (Moghaddam, 2012). The research aims to show the effects of information technology on Kosovo's accounting systems. The primary data was collected from the Employees of Accounting companies of Kosovo through structured questionnaire and processed through SPSS software. The study highlighted the requirement of different processing system of accounting incorporating information technology. (Sekiraça, 2018).

The goal of the study was to ascertain how the worldwide system's accounting line of business was affected by information technology. Also, the study demonstrated how the usage of information technology has significantly impacted on the accounting field, which has transitioned from traditional to current applications of technology in accounting systems. It also suggested that if technology were permitted to take over accounting procedures in business houses, the accounting line of work would be improved greatly. (Asuquo, 2020). The function of accounting in business and the duties of accountants have evolved as a result of technological advancement. It also acknowledged the significance of calls for better technical skill sets in accountants from a number of employer organisations and certified professional associations providing thorough learning, contextual awareness, and appreciation of the technological difficulties in the accounting context, it is also crucial to integrate some excellent comparable IT tools or concepts into the currently accessible accounting units. (Seethamraju, 2010).

3. Methodology:

The research paper aims to identify the various technological advancements on the accounting systems used in the businesses during the period of pre- and post- Covid eras, which focused primarily on how the accounting systems changed from the traditional method to the modern application method. For this purpose, the data has been collected from secondary sources like journals, magazines, and established online sources. The research examines the ways in which businesses might improve their productivity, decision-making, security, and accessibility. It offers a variety of tools and methods for using a variety of accounting firms and experts for improved business performance.

4. Discussion

Conventional accounting technology was already developing quickly, and a number of tools and software options were readily accessible to assist businesses in managing their financial data more successfully. The conventional accounting technological tools used are as follows:

- Tax software: The process of preparing and filing tax returns has made much easier by the usage of tax software like TurboTax and H&R Block.
- Expense management software: Businesses were able to expedite the process of monitoring and classifying spending using software like Expensify and Receipt Bank, which made it simpler to manage budgets and expenses.
- Cloud-based accounting: Businesses were able to access their financial data from anywhere and work in real-time with their accountants or bookkeepers thanks to cloud-based accounting solutions like QuickBooks Online and Xero.
- Digital payment platforms: Organizations now find it simpler to maintain and balance their accounts as well as accept payments online thanks to digital payment services like PayPal, Square, and Stripe.
- Accounting software: To manage bookkeeping, invoicing, and other financial chores, accounting software like QuickBooks, Xero, and Sage were often utilised.

The advantages of accounting technology over conventional applications include;

- Further efficiency: Businesses may automate many of their financial procedures thanks to accounting technology, saving time and money on jobs like data input and reconciliation,
- More accuracy: By eliminating the need for human data input, accounting technology helps

reduce financial reporting errors, which can result in expensive errors and audit problems,

- Greater data availability: Cloud-based accounting tools give firms real-time access to financial data from anywhere, enabling them to make choices based on the most recent information,
- Better collaboration: Accounting technology makes it possible for groups to work together more successfully by giving them a common location to view and discuss financial data,
- Secured authentication: To guard against unwanted access to sensitive financial data, cloud-based accounting solutions provide strong security features including encryption and multi-factor authentication.
- Savings: Companies may cut back on the requirement for human work and save personnel expenses by automating financial procedures. Technology has been a major contributor to the numerous improvements in the accounting industry that have been brought about by modern accounting applications. The accounting technologies used in current accounting technology are listed below:
- Cloud Computing Standard: The development of cloud computing and the better programmes that came along with it has been one of the major strides forward in accounting and technology. New technologies are developed every year to make your work simpler, and current systems get tweaks and redesigns to stay competitive. As a result, you'll spend less time interacting with humans and more time instructing your AI on how to display data and identify trends. Even for the least seasoned expert, today's systems are absurdly user-friendly and capable of expediting the accounting process. Moreover, they are hosted in the cloud, which increases their security and makes it possible for any internet-connected device to access them.
- "Internet of Things" (IoT): The term "Internet of Things" (IoT) depicts the large network or system of interconnected objects. It often means relying on a range of mobile devices in a corporate setting, but also on automated scanners, RFID chips, and other internet-connected sensors and gadgets that bring their technological infrastructure to life. This frequently entails giving accountants access to real-time data and allowing the data to be collected automatically without continuing human involvement.
- Big Data: Data has proven to be so important to modern business that it almost acts as money. All throughout the world, businesses are working to incorporate more big-data technologies in order to collect data, evaluate the data, and make better strategic decisions. Data may be utilised in the accounting industry for many different things, including transaction analysis, the detection of unexpected occurrences, and a better knowledge of clients, partners, and suppliers. Although evaluating figures on spreadsheets has been a popular method of data analysis for accountants for a long time, they are now expected to use big-data tech tools to evaluate significantly larger amounts of unstructured data.
- Remote Working (AKA Agile Working): As a result of the COVID-19 epidemic, accounting is moving towards more remote work (also known as agile working). Agile working is also a developing trend as a result of cloud computing and storage software (working from many different locations, including a home office, business office, and coffee shop). Employers can broaden their hiring efforts to include non-local candidates thanks to this new technology, and employees are now able to take a more flexible approach to work and make work fit in with their lifestyle rather than basing their lifestyle off of their work. This new technology enables accounting professionals to effectively and securely perform their jobs from a remote location. Employee happiness increases as a result of this trend without affecting productivity.
- Block chain Technology: During the past ten years, the block chain has evolved as one of the most popular technologies. It's possible you've heard of it in relation to Bitcoin and other virtual currencies. So-called cryptocurrencies rely on the block chain as its backbone—the mechanism that makes permitted transactions possible. The block chain essentially relies on a ledger that is distributed across numerous nodes in a larger network; if a transaction is attempted, all the nodes in the block chain cooperate to validate the transaction. This makes it possible to process transactions in the world of digital money in an extremely safe and private manner. Technology is being investigated for its potential to improve security, speed up transaction processing, and reduce costs all around in the area of accounting. Because transactions can be recorded in a personal but open joint register, record keeping is also changed. The major benefit of block chain for accountants is its ability to keep a trustworthy

record of safe transactions.

- **Real-Time Analytics:** Historical reviews of the information you've previously collected are insufficient in the modern business environment. You must consider the content you are currently gathering—and base your judgements on the most recent data you want to maintain your competitive edge and operate at your top productivity. Real-time analytics are useful in this situation. Accounting professionals may view how a company's figures change in real time and base choices on changes in current patterns with the correct digital tools and dashboards.
- **Artificial Intelligence (AI):** Artificial intelligence (AI) has become increasingly popular, and this growth is helping to advance the accounting area. To complete complex tasks, including those that were long believed to be solely humanly possible, AI depends on machine learning and cutting-edge algorithms. Accounting departments are better equipped with cutting-edge AI to examine data more thoroughly and quickly. In fact, AI may even be found in the form of personal digital assistants, which aim to increase productivity among accountants by assisting them, offering advice, and performing some work on their own.
- **Automation:** Although automation technology has its own category, AI is sometimes utilised for it. The goal of automation is to provide a machine or algorithm the ability to perform activities that previously required humans to execute them manually. Consider greater machine precision and less human mistake. Technology has a number of benefits, but perhaps the most significant one is that it frees up time so that people aren't weighed down by tedious manual labour and can instead concentrate on more crucial issues. So, you should do less calculation and manual labour and focus more on theory and comprehending high-level decision making. Also, it improves accuracy because an algorithm has a considerably lower error rate than a human does. If you're concerned that automation will completely replace accountants, that worry is unfounded.
- **Social Media:** Clients are now looking for a company they can trust, instead of just one that can execute the job effectively and with greater precision thanks to AI. Social media is one of the most popular rising technological trends for this reason. It is the crucial tool businesses will employ to introduce themselves to clients and establish that they are a reliable and valuable partner. In order to communicate with current customers and draw in new ones, social media will be emphasized as a crucial sales and marketing tool.
- **New Skillsets:** Accounting professionals will be asked to exhibit new skillsets as the role of technology in the industry continues to grow. To collect the data you need, you must first grasp how to handle AIs and instruct them on how to perform off complex assignments like forecasting financial information. Also, you'll need to grasp how to interpret the way the AI displays that info. Hence, among the most sought-after new skillsets for accountants today, are technology talents. Modern accountants will now need to exhibit new soft skills in addition to technical skills. Today's accountants will be expected to analyse data and take on higher-value jobs like advising as technology replaces more number-crunching and data processing tasks. This includes competencies like critical thinking, emotional intelligence, communication, and the need for strong judgement has increased. (Natalya Melnyk, 2020)

Through the adoption of modern application tools, accounting technology has expanded, but it has also attracted downsides such as:

- **Risks to cybersecurity:** Wherein the danger of cybersecurity breaches rises as more organisations rely on technology to conduct accounting functions remotely. The Cyber criminals can steal financial data using sophisticated techniques including phishing schemes, virus assaults, and ransomware.
- **Minimal interpersonal contact:** By reducing the need for face-to-face communication resulting in a lack of respect and comprehension, which might obstruct clear communication.
- **Elimination of a personal touch:** The Modern Accounting technological tool automated many duties that accountants used to perform by hand. This might reduce the human touch that customers cherish in their contacts with their accountants, even while it might increase efficiency and accuracy.
- **Dependency on technology:** Accounting procedures may be delayed or disrupted if

accounting technology falters or encounters technological issues. To avoid these problems, businesses would need to spend money on backup systems and emergency plans.

- Adoption and training: Using modern accounting technology may necessitate time-consuming and expensive adoption and training initiatives. Certain accountants may not even feel at ease using new technology, which can cause resistance and a reluctance to accept new systems.

5. Conclusion

In light of the digital period, we are in and the growing level of competition, businesses must cut expenses in order to stay in business. Using emerging technology into businesses regularly in this expanding period is another strategy for winning this battle. Modern technology allows it to be possible to electronically record, distribute, and save files and documents. Costs can be significantly decreased in this respect through judicial improvements to be made about the use of information technology and improvements that businesses will make to their business procedures. Establishing a method for searching books and accounting papers in electronic media has benefits beyond only assisting businesses in cutting expenses. Also, it will make financial and other court oversight simpler and more effective. It is vital to determine the electronic data standards for books and documents and to take an inventory of the books and documents that will be used in the accounting system. Also, active learning in accounting education, employing computers and package software to train people to execute this profession, and explaining how records of all accounting-related papers would be stored on electronic media are all important. Curriculums should be adjusted to reflect this, and trained staff should be familiar with the laws governing technology and also be ready to using it.

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Rebuilding and Re-boosting Tourism in Galle City, Sri Lanka in the Post COVID 19 Pandemic

Paper code: GCU-CMS-T3

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Abstract

Sri Lanka is still navigating the 'incipient mundane' and the 'next mundane' of a pandemic. The COVID-19 pandemic has triggered a major tourism crisis in Sri Lanka. To a more preponderant extent, the pandemic has had a paramount impact on Galle denizens' livelihoods. The pandemic has exhaustively shut down virtually all economic activities in Sri Lanka, eradicating the country's economy. Tourism is one of the major industries that has been astringently impacted by the pandemic. While the Sri Lankan tourism industry is still recuperating from the Easter Sunday attack in 2019, the COVID-19 outbreak emerged in 2020 and plenary shut down the industry. The main objectives of this study are, to identify the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the tourism industry in Galle city, Sri Lanka, and to identify the potential avenues to reconstitute the tourism industry in Galle city, Sri Lanka. The study was carried out utilizing different methods, a secondary data analysis was done to identify the impact COVID-19 pandemic on the tourism industry utilizing different data sources. Then, the semi-structured interviews were carried out with the hotel owners, tourist guides and minute-scale tourism entrepreneurs of Galle city, and experts in the tourism industry. The findings revealed that the industry is astringently impacted by zero-level tourist advents, the decline in peregrine exchange earnings and increment in unemployment, industry financial crisis, and loss of source markets. In this critical situation, the industry anticipates active regime mediation to avail them with propitious concessions, palliation packages, tax burden minimization, and auspicious policies to re-establish the industry with a Tourism Resilience Plan (TRP). However, it will not be facile in the short run in the pandemic-affected economies and societies. Consequently, it requires facing the challenges of reconstituting the sector.

Keywords: Pandemic, Re-boost Galle City, Sri Lanka, Rebuild Potential Avenues

1. Introduction

Tourism is one of the world's most expeditious expanding businesses. It is a paramount economic force in Sri Lanka. In Sri Lanka, tourism is the most reliable source of peregrine exchange. It may avail in resolving the trade deficit. Tourism in Sri Lanka encompasses all commercial operations that give accommodations to tourists. It comprises hotels, peregrinate agencies, trekking agencies, and so on. Industries are grouped into two types predicated on their nature: engendering t industries and accommodation industries. As a result, the tourist business employs one out of every ten people ecumenically. In 2019, it directly engendered 330 million employment and accounted for 10.3% of the ecumenical gross domestic product (GDP) according to the data from World Peregrinate & Tourism Council (WTTC) in 2020. This covers jobs with hotels, airlines, and other passenger conveyance companies. As a relatively incipient and vibrant industry in the Sri Lankan economy, peregrinate, tourism, and hospitality have always faced obstacles. However, according to figures from the Sri Lanka Tourist Development Ascendancy (SLTDA) in 2020, the e-tourism industry contributed 4.3the % to local GDP in 2019.

Growing in enticing popularity, by 2019 it has ascended to become the third most immensely colossal peregrine exchange earner, with total profits of \$ 4.4 billion in 2018 and \$ 3.7 billion in 2019 (SLTDA, 2020). Furthermore, the Sri Lankan regime had set a target of six million tourist

visits by 2025, which would engender \$ 10 billion in revenue (Samarathunga, 2020). Of the total 402,607 individuals engaged in the tourist industry, 173,592 work directly and 229,015 work indirectly (SLTDA, 2020). Tourism is one of the most paramount economic industries on the planet. It employs one out of every 10 people on the planet and engenders work for hundreds of millions more. It stimulates economies and sanctions countries to grow.

Indeed, one could argue that tourism is one of the world's marvels.

That is why it has been so heart-breaking to witness how the COVID-19 outbreak has ravaged tourism. The crisis is a paramount shock for industrialized economies, but it is an emergency for developing countries, eminently several minute island developing states and African countries. Tourism has been an implement for integration, potentiation, and revenue generation for women, rural communities, indigenous peoples, and many other a foretime oppressed populations. Incremented poaching and habitat degradation in and around bulwarked areas have resulted from a drop in revenue, and the closing of several World Heritage Sites has deprived populations of paramount livelihoods.

It is critical that the tourist industry be developed. To fortify the millions of people whose livelihoods rely on tourism, we must provide a sustainable and ethical peregrinate experience

that is safe for host communities, employees, and passengers. To avail recuperation, the primary focus must be on mitigating the socioeconomic impacts of the crisis, building resilience across the entire tourism value chain, promoting sustainability and green magnification, and fostering partnerships to enable tourism to further support the priority areas' sustainable development goals. It is critical to re-establish tourism as a source of referable jobs, steady incomes, and the preservation of our cultural and natural legacy. At varying rates, destinations and areas of the tourism industry are reopening and recuperating from the ecumenical epidemic. Because tourism is a multi-sectoral industry, perpetual issues for the industry are liable to have an impact on the ecumenical economy. Incipient tourist policy methods are desperately needed. Figure 1 depicts the seven pillars that must support the post-pandemic Tourism Resilience Plan (TRP).

Figure 1: Seven pillars

Given the background, the research paper set to achieve the following objectives:

- (i) To identify the impact of COVID 19 pandemic on the tourism industry in Galle city, Sri Lanka
- (ii) To identify the potential avenues to rebuild the tourism industry in Galle city, Sri Lanka

2. Literature Review

2.1. Impact of tourism

Literature demonstrates that the tourism sector affects many aspects of a location directly, indirectly, and indirectly (Andereck et al., 2005; Khan et al., 1990; Mayer, 2014). The benefits of tourism to the local economy and society, such as job engendered, investment, engendered, and socioeconomic development, have been accentuated (Alam & Paramati, 2016; Ehigiamusoe, 2020). Despite these consequential positive effects, there has supplementally been much discussion of the negative effects of tourism, such as its interference with the convivial and fiscal salubrity of locals in a tourist destination (Jordan et al., 2021; Weaver & Lawton, 2001).

2.2. Tourism under crisis periods

Natural disasters (such as earthquakes, hurricanes, and tsunamis); terrorism (such as the September 11 attack and the Bali bombings); political unrest and war (such as wars, energy shocks, and economic crises); and epidemics (such as Rigorous Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS), foot-and-mouth disease, swine flu, the Ebola virus, the Middle East Respiratory Syndrome coronavirus (MERS), COVID-19; K The external occurrences of epidemics could be regarded as the most perilous of these external crises due to their extensive and unexpected spread.

2.3. Tourism under the COVID-19

Numerous studies have been conducted on the spread of COVID-19 since its emergence, as it has rigorously damaged the ecumenical tourism industry (Gössling et al., 2020). In comparison to antecedent pandemics and crises, prior research primarily fixated on the impact of COVID-19 on tourism (Gössling et al., 2020), and the connection between the COVID-19 crisis and sustainable development (Ioannides & Gyimóthy, 2020; Nepal, 2020; 2020; Niewiadomski Romagosa, 2020), the strategy for tourism recuperation (Yeh, 2020), and the future of tourism following COVID-19 (Haywood, 2020). Some studies optically canvassed how COVID-19 affected international tourist advents and rural tourism (Silva, 2022; Wen, J., et al., 2020).

3. Methodology

Methodology makes a logical argument on how the research has been carried out (Kumar, 2023). In-depth interviews and a qualitative methodology were utilized in this study to investigate the perspectives and experiences of locals regarding the effects of tourism on their lives and local economies before and after the COVID-19 pandemic. It enables a more precise understanding of the designations of findings that are not directly quantifiable. Additionally, this study used semi-structured interviews to ascertain how the COVID 19 pandemic affected Galle city's tourism industry. From January to May 2021, data were amassed. Snowball sampling was habituated to reach respondents in this study. The respondents were culled from a variety of tourism-cognate vocations to provide a broader range of perspectives. In integration, because tourism is regarded as an integrated sector that is proximately linked to other fortifying industries, the perspectives of sundry vocations provide a more pellucid understanding of the impact of tourism and the tourism development strategy in Galle city in this study.

This study was conducted with 30 interviewees, all of whom met the sufficiency and saturation criteria. The 30 people who were interviewed had an average age of 38.6 years, with 17 being male (56.7 percent) and 13 were female (43.3 percent). Twenty-three of them were espoused, or three quarters. Each espoused individual had an average of two children. One respondent had consummated a master's programme, 22 had studied college or university, one had only culminated high school, and four had only culminated secondary school. Two of the respondents had dropped

out of school. In terms of where they live, 25 of the respondents were born in the city of Galle, while 05 of them peregrinate to Galle from other areas. From one year to 25 years, each respondent had a long history of tourism activity. Digital recordings of all of these interviews, which lasted anywhere from 25 to 45 minutes, were consummated. The interviews were exhaustively transcribed, translated into English by the first author, and checked for precision by other authors. The transcripts were read an abundance of times and manually analyzed, with an accentuation on decoding and understanding the designation of the words in the text.

4. Results

In order to answer the research questions, the 30 participants of this study were acclimated to engendering. Themes justifications are presented in this component. Among these themes are the positive effects of tourism on the lives of locals, the detrimental effects of tourism on the local economy prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on locals' businesses and economies, and sustainable methods to re-boost and reconstitute tourism development in Galle city.

4.1 Positive Impacts of Tourism on the Galle Citizens before the Pandemic

For example, a report from the manager of a peregrinate company explicated that his life had been amended monetarily ever since he commenced working in tourist accommodations 15 years ago. His life had become more active and financially secure thanks to this work. Tour operators and eatery proprietors had supplementally acknowledged the positive aspects of tourism. Data suggests that visitors to Galle town, categorically Chinese and Russian visitors, spent a plethora of mazuma on arts and crafts, tea and cinnamon, gifts, and gems. As a consequence, these accommodations were more benign to regional tourism-cognate companies. The majority of respondents verbalized that tourism played a crucial role in the magnification of the local economy of Galle city when compared to other industries in terms of its contribution to the local economy. It provided numerous employment opportunities for locals and contributed significantly to the budget of the local regime. Presented evidence: The tourism sector makes up the majority of the local economy.

4.2. Negative Impacts of Tourism on the Local Economy before the Pandemic

Notwithstanding the positive characteristics mentioned above, tourism has withal had a number of detrimental effects on socioeconomic and environmental factors. There is evidence that tourism is to inculcate for the city's traffic congestion and hydrogen monoxide and air pollution, lack of quality control in the industry, the inequitable rivalry between peregrinate agencies, and overburdened infrastructure and tourist accommodations. For example, a tour guide in Galle city verbally expressed:

“The local ascendant entities and businesses, in my opinion, fail to agonize the negative effects of tourism in Galle city. They merely concentrated on the authoritative ordinance side and the resulting economic benefits. The master plan was not followed by tourism development. This resulted in unprecedented hydrogen monoxide and air pollution and traffic jams in the city.”

4.3 Negative impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic on the Tourism Industry

The effects of COVID-19 depended on the kind of work people did and their particular circumstances, so the effects varied from person to person. Some hotels and resorts were able to keep running their businesses, but others had to close. Businessmen who were significantly impacted by COVID-19 were the focus of the adopted policies. More categorically, they were coerced to lay off employees in order to accommodate the decremented number of customers utilizing the accommodations. Others were coerced to abbreviate the monthly payment or the number of employees they employed. The following are a few examples of evidence:

One Galle city homestay owner claims;

“My homestay perpetuates to operate. But when people aurally perceived the pandemic in the middle of January, there were abrogation of bookings from China. Europe, Malaysia, Korea,

Russia, the Cumulated Kingdom, and the UK and the US.”

The devastation wrought by the conflict was visually perceived in Galle city's replication as to the effects of COVID-19 on tourism. As this pandemic has caused twice as much or three times as much harm as SARS, The border had been on lockdown for COVID-19.

4.4. Sustainable Approaches to Tourism Development

Predicated on the interviews, sustainable development for local tourism has been developed to deal with issues like COVID-19 in the future. This strategy was utilized by individuals and businesses as well as the local regime and Sri Lanka Tourism Development Ascendancy. It was suggested that tourism management concentrate on three issues in cognition to the local regime and the tourism ascendancy;

- (a) the diversification of the tourism sector,
- (b) the management of tourism engendered and
- © the restructuring of human resources.”

Consequently, it is high time to engender a post-pandemic Tourism Resilience Plan (TRP) focusing the attention on the following 07 pillars to reconstitute and re-boost tourism in Galle city.

5. Discussion

Higher yield markets necessitated reforming the tourism industry's human resources. According to the respondents, the quality of the current tourism human resources was only qualified to accommodate Asian tourists, concretely Chinese tourists. However, they may not be eligible due to the higher requisites of other Western markets. The lack of technical experience and expertise among the next generation of human resources to work with European tourists in the future was noted by many respondents.

In short, the study site requires a long-term tourism magnification strategy that accentuates diversifying tourist sources and involves businessmen in multiple vocations; expanding the peregrinate industry; better marketing and management of tourism services by DMOs (Kumar, Mishra, & Rao, 2021), using social media for communication (Kumar, 2021a; 2021b); and raising the standard of human resources in the local tourism and regime sectors. According to the views and opinions of the respondents to reconstitute and re-boost tourism in Galle city, the following processes have to be implemented in the below chart. (Figure 5)

Figure 5

These adverse consequences are intensified by the spread of the pandemic. As a result, the tourism and peregrinate industry in the review site requisites to move toward practical development to mitigate the adverse consequence of the peregrinate industry as well as to vanquish the Coronavirus crisis.

6. Conclusion

In integration, this study outlines a number of strategies for the sustainable expansion of tourism in the Galle city tourism industry during the COVID-19 crisis. Diversification of the tourism industry, Magnification management, and reorganization of human resources are among these methods. First, it could be argued that expanding tourism markets is paramount for countries and locals because it can increment tourism revenues from high-yield markets and abbreviate the jeopardy of relying on a single industry.

Due to the widespread vaccination program implemented by the Sri Lankan regime, the COVID-19 virus has gradually been contained, which has led to a marginal recuperation in Sri Lankan tourism and the reopening of Galle City's border for international peregrinators. As a result, Lankan tourism practices following the pandemic should habituate to the "incipient mundane" in a variety of ways, including repositioning the strategic market (i.e., the high-yield market), implementing visa exemption or longer visa policies for those markets, working toward a long-term strategy development and implementation of the post-pandemic Tourism Resilience Plan (TRP).

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A study on strategies adopted by MNC's to cope up with Indian companies

Paper code: GCU-CMS-T18

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to find out what type of strategies are been used by the MNC's to be ahead from the Indian companies in the domestic market. The report explains the strategies, problems and solutions used by the MNCs that they use to survive in the domestic market. The present study is based on secondary data available in different books, journals, articles, research papers, and internet source also. The present study attempts to analyse the relationship between foreign companies' mode of entry with FDI and economic variables by using Karl Pearson coefficient correlation. There are many strategies used by the MNCs to overcome the competition and survive in the domestic market such as Cost leadership Strategy, Differentiation Strategy, Cost Focus Strategy etc. During the research we also compared the MNCs with local companies and found out the major factors which makes them apart and gives up a good survival period with respect to the local companies. One of the major things found in the study was that how do the MNCs contribute in the growth of the economy of the domestic country. This research paper shows us the impact and need of the MNCs in one country. During the upcoming years a developing country needs as much as Foreign Direct Investment as possible to survive in the global market and MNCs are on the best sources of FDIs to improve their economy and be recognised in the global market. The research paper will not only help us to know more about the MNCs, it will also help the local companies to adapt to the competition and improve more better to seize their market. It will also help the under developing to make adjustments in their laws to attract more MNCs to develop their economy. The study is head to toe about the MNC's strategies, problems and solutions. It also gives out how the MNCs and their FDIs change the course of a nation and give them stability.

Keywords: MNCs, FDIs, Strategies, Competition, local companies.

1. Introduction

Exploring the changing the last two decades have seen significant internationalization of firms from developing economies in various aspects such as, greater participation in international trade, growing outflows of foreign direct investment (FDI), and a surge in their cross-border mergers and acquisition activity. Outward investment from developing countries is not a new phenomenon but in recent years there has been a marked increase in the magnitude of flows and a qualitative transformation in their pattern. Flows of outward FDI from developing countries rose from about \$6 billion in 1989–1991 (about 2.7% of global outward flows) to \$253 billion for 2007 (nearly 13% of global outflows). Multinational enterprises are the “face” of globalization because they provide three functions that facilitate globalization: MNCs are market-making firms, they investment bridges to the global economy, and they act as agents of change (Eden, 1995).

The idea of strategy has received increasing attention in the management literature. The literature on strategy is now voluminous and strategic in the management literature. The literature on strategy

is now voluminous and strategic management texts grow even larger to include all the relevant material. A firm needs a well-defined sense of its mission.

The Growth Sector:

Strategic management involves decisions concerning what a company might do, given the opportunities in its environment, what it can do, given the resources at its disposal what it wants to do, given the personal values and aspirations of key decision makers and what it should do, given the ethical and legal context in which it is operating. A firm needs a well-defined sense of where it is going in the future and a firm concept of the business it is in. we can think of these in terms of the firm's product.

Cost leadership Strategy:

A firm producing at the lowest cost in the industry enjoys the best profits. Producing at lower cost is a strategy that can be used by various firms so as to have a significant cost advantage over the competition in the market. This in effect leads to growth in the market share. This strategy is mostly associated with large businesses offering standard products that are clearly different from competitors who may target a broader group of customers. The low-cost leader in any market gains competitive advantage from being able to many to produce at the lowest cost. Factories are built and maintained; labour is recruited and trained to deliver the lowest possible costs of production. Cost advantage is the focus.

Differentiation Focus:

A business aims to differentiate within one or a number of target market segments. The special customer needs of the segment means that there are opportunities to provide products that are clearly different from competitors who may be targeting a broader group of customers. This demands that the customer's different needs and wants be recognized. Porter (1980) reiterates that only if a company makes a strong and unwavering commitment to one of the generic competitive strategies does it stand much chance of achieving sustainable competitive advantage that such strategies can deliver if properly executed. Many scholars have questioned this; in particular, Miller (1992) questions the notion of being "caught in the middle". He claims that there is a viable middle ground between strategies. Many companies for example, have entered a market as a niche player and gradually expanded. Hill (1988) claimed that Porter's model was flawed because differentiation can be a means for firms to achieve low cost.

Challenges faced:

Competition exerts pressure on firms to be proactive and to formulate success response strategies to changes in the competitive environment in an effort to gain competitive advantage. Porter (1980) explains his strategic options in light of analysing the market opportunities and threats, which form the background to competitive behavior. Porter (1980) argues that most business must respond to five basic competitive forces that drive industry competition. According to him the collective strengths of these forces determines the ultimate profit potential of the industry and thus its attractiveness. The five forces are threat of new entrants, bargaining power of buyers and suppliers, threat of substitutes and rivalry within competitors. A proper analysis of the five forces will help a firm choose one of the Porters generic strategies that will effectively enable the firm compete profitably in an industry. Porter (1988) discusses government as a force in industry competition. He explains that government at all levels must influence many aspects of industry structure either directly or indirectly. In many countries government is a buyer or a supplier and can influence industry competition by the policies it adapts.

MNCs vs. Locals Firms:

Multinationals organizations are very important in the world's economy. They plays a vital role in the international trade. In addition, they facilitate the development of nations, both developed and

the developing nations. For instance, multinationals provide employment opportunities to the developing nations. People get disposal income to spend on from multinationals setting base in their countries, consequently facilitating the economic growth of these nations. In addition, multinational organizations facilitate provision of high-quality goods, as well as services. On the other hand, despite the fact that local organizations in the developing countries have an impact on the economies of those countries, they may not be as effective as the MNCs. Multinationals have the ability to rise above the challenges faced by local firms. They offer services of better quality than those of local organizations

Unfriendly business environment:

The business environment is not very friendly. At the same time, there are laws that are challenging to organizations. Competition is very high, making it difficult for organizations to succeed. However, firms can come up with business strategies that can give them a competitive advantage. For instance, they can adopt the Porter's generic strategies.

Huge costs of labor in the host country:

Huge labor cost is a problem to MNCs since they incur high operating expenses that reduce their profitability. MNCs are said to take advantage of the poor labor standards and weak environmental regulations to maximize their income. They avoid employing expatriates from their home countries to avoid high expenses.

1.1 Scope of the Study:

The multinational company is a company which is operating in multiple nations, which is using global resources for production and marketing those in more than two countries. It is a company which is generating employment to millions of people around the world and makes improve their standard of living. MNCs are big in size, operation, investment etc. in the international business which consists of host and home country. In this host countries are developing countries and home countries are developed countries which are the origin of MNCs. In this study, we are going to know whether MNCs are contributing to economic development and their business environment in a developing economy. This study is done on MNCs and developing economies; in this, we consider India's economy as a developing economy. And in this, we have considered the economic variables such as Employment, GDP, GNP, and Balance of payment and FDI to know whether MNCs are contributing to the economy development of the country or not. The study aims to achieve following objectives:

1. To find out the MNC's make different strategies to overcome the competition within the local market
2. To find the strategies used to survive in the market.
3. The way they evolve by time in the market.

2. Literature review

Ogutu, and Samuel (2012) found that Multinational corporations (MNCs) operate in a global environment unfamiliar in political, economic, social, cultural, technological and legal aspects. Increased competition among multinational corporations and the entry of other players in the Kenyan market necessitate the design of competitive strategies that guarantee performance. Creating strategies for coping with competition is the heart of strategic management which is critical for the long term survival of any organization. This paper examines the strategies adopted by MNCs to cope with competition in Kenya. To establish the strategies adopted by the MNCs, forty questionnaires were administered to senior managers of MNCs targeting 19 percent of the total population of 213 MNCs in Kenya. Stratified disproportionate sampling was used to select the forty MNCs. This study established that MNCs in Kenya have adopted a number of strategies including: better quality, excellent customer service, innovation, differentiation, diversification, cost cutting measures, strategic alliances, joint venture, mergers and acquisitions, as well as, lower

prices, to weather competitive challenges.

Thite, Budhwar, and Wilkinson (2014) argues that the rapid growth of emerging markets' multinational companies (MNCs) is a recent phenomenon and, as such, their nature and structure of key management processes, functions, and roles need further examination. While an abundance of low-cost labor is often the starting point of competitive advantage for many of the emerging markets' MNCs, it is the optimum configuration of people, processes, and technology that defines how they leverage their intangible resources. Based on case studies of four Indian IT services MNCs, involving 51 in-depth interviews of business and human resource (HR) leaders at the corporate and subsidiary levels, we identify five key HR roles—namely, strategic business partner, guardian of culture, builder of global workforce and capabilities, champion of processes, and facilitator of employee development. The analysis also highlights that the HR function in Indian IT service MNCs faces several challenges in consolidating the early gains of internationalization, such as lack of decentralized decision making, developing a global mind-set, localization of the workforce, and developing a global leadership pipeline. Based on our exploratory findings, we propose a framework outlining the global HR roles pursued by emerging IT services MNCs, the factors influencing them, and the challenges facing their HR function for future research.

Som (2006), has found that with increasing globalization, firms are entering a dynamic world of international business that is marked by liberalization of economic policies in a large number of emerging economies like India. To face the challenge of increasing competition that has resulted from liberalization, Indian organizations have initiated adoption of innovative human resource management practices both critically and constructively to foster creativity and innovation among employees. With the help of 11 in-depth case studies, this article tries to understand how innovative HRM practices are being adopted by Indian firms to brace for competition in the post liberalization scenario. In a study done by Bhaskar (2016), findings reveal that MNCs wanting to do business in India need to have a long-term business focus, a well-defined expatriate policy and deep pockets to experience growth and payoffs on investments. In order to be successful, they need to understand India culturally and geographically, build trusting relationships with HCNs, partner with local players who are familiar with domestic challenges and localize the best practices of the west. Attrition and retention being the major challenges in India, compensation alone is not enough to attract and retain talent. Understanding Indian psyche and offering individuals a unique value proposition such as challenging roles and professional growth is imperative for creating an attractive employer brand in order to win the war for talent.

3. Methodology of the Study

The present study is based on secondary data available in different books, journals, articles, research papers, and internet source also. The present study attempts to analyze the relationship between foreign companies' mode of entry with FDI and economic variables by using Karl Pearson coefficient correlation.

4. Findings

Business operational plan of Apple Inc.

Strategic plan sets up the business plan of a company while business plan in turn establishes the business operation plan. Operational plan is the key to run the entire business of company. Operational business plan covers the all areas of company including the finance, manufacturing, internet, operations, R&D, human resources and marketing. Apple Inc. was known because of its lenient business thinking Apple Inc. has the design, marketing and manufacturing services. Company develops designs and markets the musical players with important accessories. The business of Apple Inc. is managed on geographic basis. There are five operating segments of Apple Inc. such as America, Europe, Japan, retail and others. In US, Canada, UK and Japan Apple owned stores are currently operating.

Discuss both the internal and external factors that impinge on the business operations plan.

Apple Inc. has faced the serious challenges during the last 30 years but recovered from those serious situations with advent of innovation. Apple Inc. faces the threat of competition because of free services in market. A good business achieves the market share by creating better legal services to

customers. It can be compared with the bottle water which is better in quality as compared to tap water which is in approach of every person. However, there is legal competition ahead in market. No company was successful to attach the market before the Apple Inc. did so. Better service is directly related with the new and better technology.

Impacts of environmental and technological changes on the business plan of Apple Inc.

Apple Inc. has made efforts to satisfy its stakeholders in various ways. It included all the environmental issues for its corporate governance. It has satisfied the employees, local communities and general public by minimizing the environmental impacts on its entire business operations; integrated the sound environmental, safety management and health practices. The environmental mission statement of Apple Inc. has integrated all above-mentioned practices into all business operations ensure that it offers technologically innovative products. Apple Inc. aims to communicate on the policy which provides the benefits of environmental consciousness, safety maximization, energy efficiency and health protection to its various stakeholders.

Importance of good business operations planning to the overall success of the business at Apple Inc.

Apple Inc. has many successful factors that determine its success in key areas of the operations. An important factor that is apparent is about the vision of the organization. It is true that creative energy always begins with vision. These organizations impact significantly on the world (Collins & Porras, 2004). Apple has a very clear and purposeful vision which can be seen through the innovative products for the last many years (Senge, 2006). The main purpose of the Apple Inc. was to develop the computers for the world and making contribution to the world by its advance technology products. Beside this vision Apple Inc. takes further steps of actions which are practiced throughout the organization.

Managerial qualities and resources necessary for effective business operation planning

Apple Inc. has five divisions to manage the products and marketing departments of the company. These five divisions are responsible to evaluation and manufacturing of the devices, software and hardware of computer system. The four support divisions also work to handle the marketing and post-sale products. A new position of Chief Operation Officer was created by Scully to centralize the operations and involving the senior management in the daily business decisions (Annual Report, 1988). Human Resource (HR) is responsible for the safeguarding the most valuable assets of the Apple Inc. It handles the many programs of the company to achieve the company's goals. Human resource at Apple Inc. is also responsible to reach at the needed resources. The Apple Inc. has six important valued creation functions including the marketing, R&D, finance, Human resource management, information systems and operations and logistics. The chain of activities required to transform the inputs into outputs are primarily concerned with actual design, manufacturing, delivery, marketing of products and customer support activities. The ultimate task of the R&D resource at Apple Inc. includes the new innovation and use of technology which meet the customer's requirements (Hill & Jones, 2004).

From the above discussion it can be concluded that Apple Inc. is a well-known development and business company of the world. Its success lies in its business operation plan which indeed depends upon the various necessary actions taken from the design of the product to sale of the product.

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Role of Digital entrepreneurship in the modern era

Paper code: GCU-CMS-M6

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Abstract

Online reservations, reviews, coupons, order processing automation, and other technology-related factors are essential for modern enterprises. Digitalization is crucial for restaurant and other industries. Transport firms must rank high in search results and make booking easy to attract and keep customers. Digital technology has changed business and entrepreneurship. Digitalization has brought various challenges to entrepreneurs, including content overload, distant communication, and big data. Today, entrepreneurs must be mindful that they may be disrupted by competitors and customer contact with similar digital products and services. Integrating continually has created new digital and responsive company structures. Businesses have changed. In the digital age, businesses must respond quickly to product innovation, offer value-added services, improve customer support, and use omnichannel marketing. This article describes the abilities, competencies, and steps needed to become a digital entrepreneur. Lists the merits and cons of digital entrepreneurship, then discusses its reach.

Key words: Digital entrepreneurship, economic growth, marketing strategies

1. Introduction

Entrepreneurship is hotter than ever in the digital age. Digital entrepreneurship goes beyond online meetings, paperless offices, and social media. It should be considered as a holistic approach to thinking that covers all organisational activities, including communication and service delivery. We may succeed long-term and fend off competition by "thinking digitally" and integrating digital process support at all levels. Data, information, and knowledge combined with operational performance and service offering create new market prospects and business models. Platform economics, support systems, and new technology improve processes. Digital entrepreneurs explore promising prospects and create creative concepts to grow their firm. The new digital entrepreneurial strategy centres on business model creation, software and hardware architecture, and data, information, and knowledge storage.

Digital entrepreneurship: Digital entrepreneurship is finding and pursuing possibilities to create digital artefacts, platforms, and infrastructures that supply services through technology (Schmidt 2011; Giones and Brem 2017). Digital entrepreneurship is a way business owners use technology to change company processes. It shows entrepreneurs new digital business procedures. It involves cost-cutting, partnerships, product designs, and more.

2. Literature review

A digital platform: Entrepreneurs can produce, market, and distribute using a digital form, a shared

set of digital artefacts. Digital entrepreneurship has changed the uncertainty of entrepreneurial processes and outcomes in the previous two decades (Nambisan 2017). Entrepreneurs are creating tech-driven company ideas in a world of constant change. Social media platforms allow entrepreneurs to introduce new products and services to consumers and use AI to measure their reach.

The digital entrepreneurial personality must maintain the following competencies:

Figure 1.1 competencies required for a digital entrepreneur.

- Creativity, organisational skills and a feel for market opportunities
- Strong knowledge of the technical requirements and the competitive environment
- Courage to apply the process of creative destruction to their own business or its processes at any time.

Figure 1.2 shows the skills required for a digital entrepreneur.

Digital and marketing Skills: Digital entrepreneurs must comprehend keyword research, SEO, SEM, social media, email marketing, and market cultivation. Digital entrepreneurs need the next skill since they can't do it alone.

Digital Business Architecture: Knowing that digital firms need a solid architectural structure will help the digital entrepreneur know what actions to take to grow his business. Silo Architecture organises online content development.

Elevator Pitch: Entrepreneurs must be able to create a compelling elevator pitch that engages investors via video calls.

Human Resource Management: Entrepreneurs must identify their strengths and weaknesses. Using others' skills will help the digital entrepreneur develop. So, the entrepreneur must manage his team.

Creativity: Internet entrepreneurs must accept that no work is flawless. Testing works and doesn't. A/B testing is important because entrepreneurs must use their imagination to develop answers.

Income Generation: Digital entrepreneurs must understand their business model and revenue source. Whether selling products, on-demand services, or subscriptions, the entrepreneur should focus on cash streams. Entrepreneurs must also learn to generate passive money using affiliate platforms and advertising to grow their internet business.

Characteristics of Digital Entrepreneurship

A keen intellect is essential for becoming a digital entrepreneur. Success in the digital era requires education. Let's examine digital entrepreneurship's key traits.

Fig 1.3: showing the characteristics of a Digital entrepreneur.

Planning: Planning is vital for all entrepreneurs. Digital entrepreneurs need a strategy to stay on track. Understand that no business can do everything. For an impactful foundation, everything needs meticulous planning and vision.

Effective Communication: Digital entrepreneurs always organise and communicate ideas. Without communication skills, a clear notion is useless. Business partners and investors value it. It also helps improve teamwork.

Getting Motivation from Failures: Most people think negatively about failures. Failures are now socially stigmatised. Yet, failure-embracing digital entrepreneurs are different. It teaches them career success. Jack Ma and Elon Musk are notable entrepreneurs who succeeded after repeated setbacks. They have remarkable motivation to overcome failures.

Having Urgency: Digital entrepreneurs cannot prosper without urgency. They set goals-based deadlines and meet them. They set shorter deadlines to increase production and effectiveness. Urgency helps them prioritise tasks. Shorter deadlines enhance productivity. Thus, digital entrepreneurs act smarter.

Understanding the Numbers: Digital entrepreneurs need accurate numbers to succeed. Numbers matter to many successful entrepreneurs. Knowing retention and acquisition costs prevents overpaying. Financials show a company's long-term prosperity and performance.

Thinking Globally: Digital enterprise lets people go global. While competition is high, it creates significant expansion prospects. Think big rather than tiny. Every digital entrepreneur should expand their business.

Pros and Cons of becoming digital entrepreneurship

Table 1.1 showing the Pros and Cons of a Digital entrepreneur.

Sl. NO.	Pros of digital entrepreneurship	Cons of Digital entrepreneurship
1	Easy to scale business	Train employees to become digital.
2	Global expansion	Adequate skills and training
3	Working while travelling	Consumes lot of time
4	Boost revenue	Additional costs
5	Passive income	Additional capital to procure digital
6	Doing business any where in the world	Tough competition
7	Smart work digitally	Privacy problems
8	Building Satisfied customer	
9	Foster innovation	
10	Reducing the cost of iteration	
11	Employee productivity	
12	Better customer experience	

**There are tons of notable people who have shown the world
“how to use digital evolution for success.”**

SL NO	Digital icon	Highlights
1	Neil Patel	He is a prominent digital marketing entrepreneur who has generated approximately US\$10 million in a short time. Patel owns Hello Bar and Crazy Egg.
2	Byron White	Writer Access, founded by Byron White, meets all content demands. This platform remains popular despite the release of numerous others.
3	Elon Musk	Only fools reject Musk's greatness. He invented PayPal, which revolutionised digital payments. eBay bought this platform for US\$1.5 billion, confirming its value. SpaceX, Tesla, and other companies of Elon Musk make him one of the most successful entrepreneurs.
4	Drew Houston	Dropbox is a popular cloud computing service. Drew Houston, an internet entrepreneur valued about US\$2.2 billion in 2021, founded it. He innovates to change cloud computing's future. Houston should inspire business innovators.
5	Jeff Bezos	Most prominent digital entrepreneur is Jeff Bezos. Amazon founder and CEO. According to some reports, Bezos transformed e-commerce and made Amazon a global powerhouse.
6	Bill Gates (Microsoft)	Software developer, investor, and philanthropist Bill Gates. Microsoft co-founder. Forbes has often called Gates the world's richest.
7	Mark Zuckerberg (Facebook)	Facebook CEO Mark Zuckerberg is a notable digital entrepreneur, co-founder, and chairman. Zuckerberg founded Internet.org, a nonprofit that provides internet access to impoverished nations.

Source: <https://www.discoverwalks.com>

Steps to become a digital entrepreneur

- a) **Entrepreneurial mindset:** Digital entrepreneurs must be risk-takers, observant, and entrepreneurial.
- b) **Identify a problem or opportunity:** Second, find a digital solution-able problem or opportunity. Choose any of the digital new business models we suggested. The more time you spend preparing and thinking about the idea, the less time you spend really working on your startup. If you found the problem and have the answer, start your business.
- c) **Launching digital product or services:** Lastly, after launching your digital product or service, you'll acquire client feedback, and then you may focus on analytics-based improvements.
- d) **Building business online and focus:** Online businesses are different from traditional ones, where location is key. Develop brand recognition and attract new website visitors or account followers.
- e) **Scaling the business:** Lastly, you must convert your first visitors into customers or users to expand and scale your firm. You can grow and retain customers with the greatest digital marketing tools and methods. Finally, stay current on digital, remote worker, and digital business trends.

Digital technologies supporting Digital entrepreneurs

Artificial intelligence	Virtual reality	The Internet of things (IoT)
By 2030, 70% of global economic effect will come from AI (Rao and Verweij 2017)	By 2025, the VR market will reach 56.25 billion USD (Globenewswire 2020)	IoT was named the top business transformation technology by 17% of global respondents (KPMG 2018)
The worldwide AI software industry will reach 126 billion USD in 2025 and increase rapidly (Liu 2020) Intelligent process automation will cost \$9.6 billion in 2020.	VR will cost \$87.97 billion in 2025. (Mordorintelligence 2020)	IoT spending will exceed 1.1 trillion USD by 2023. (Liu 2020) 2025 will see 21.4 billion IoT devices (Liu 2020)

3. Future and scope of Digital entrepreneurship

This fast-paced digital world has elevated digital entrepreneurship. The OECD believes the digital economy may boost productivity, income, and well-being. It's opening new markets and expanding some occupations. Digital technologies increase output with less labour, but they also put certain workers at danger of unemployment or lower wages. They also allow changes in work organisation, which affects policies and programmes for labour market inclusion, employment quality, and skills development. Digital entrepreneurship is popular because it lets entrepreneurs establish and grow their enterprises online. Young individuals, who are more tech-savvy, are drawn to this form of entrepreneurship. Digital entrepreneurship is cheaper than brick-and-mortar firms, making it more appealing to many. Digital media tools make it easier to sell items and services worldwide. This digital entrepreneurial ecosystem allows society to run a global business and offer services like social media management, dropshipping, e-commerce, cloud services, content marketing, coaching, and more, so individuals can spend their time doing what they love and become digital entrepreneurs.

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A Comprehensive study on Salar Jung Museum during covid 19

Paper code: GCU-CMS-T6

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Abstract

This paper affords an outline of Salar Jung museum Hyderabad, Telangana and its ancient importance. Mainly this paper examines the prevailing state of affairs of Salar Jung museum and to pick out the contribution and demanding situations of museum for advertising of tourism and improvement of the area. And also, to decide the tourist's pleasure with the offerings supplied in Salar Jung museum. This paper additionally offers a short understanding of library control device of Salar Jung museum library. The major cause of this takes a look at is to discover the prevailing frame of Salar Jung museum library. This paper can be beneficial the studies students in getting the understanding approximately Salar Jung museum and its Library. This paper is additionally beneficial in enhancing its offerings and standing on this Information age.

Keywords: Salarjung Museum, Pandemic Consequences, Digital media, Social media, Promotion & Publicity

1. Introduction

Tourism is a major factor in the economy of many nations, improving the quality of life and promoting local arts and crafts. Museums and monuments attract tourists from all over the world, making India a tourist paradise. This survey provides a first glimpse into the contributions and difficulties faced by museum technology specialists in crisis. It highlights the importance of creating digital literacy, focusing on digital technology, and creating digital strategies to deal with emerging challenges of marketing and promotion (Kumar, 2021).

Museum experts can provide digital leadership in times of crisis, and museum managers should invest in digital literacy skills to position their institutions for future challenges and crises. Many of those included in staff layoffs are the very employees best suited to carry museums through the COVID-19 pandemic, as museum directors face the difficult task of weighting which workers are essential to museum operations as budgets shrink. For example, key services provided during pandemic-related closures included virtual training materials, experiences, and curricula specifically designed to reach students, parents, and teachers online; however, despite the clear value of these services, two-thirds of museum directors anticipate cuts in education, programming, and other public services due to financial hardship (AAM, 2020a). As per Small (2020), "budget shortfalls have resulted in a regression of priorities in many museums, where once-growing fields like digital media and education are being targeted for cuts." Museum directors are under duress.

In April, nearly all museums round the arena have been closed due to the COVID-19 pandemic, in line with 94.7 % of respondents. During the lockdown, many museums were desirable their virtual sports. Although nearly 1/2 of the respondents spoke back that their museum already had a presence on social media or shared its collections on-line earlier than the lockdowns, virtual communiqué

sports analyzed with the aid of using the survey accelerated for as a minimum 15 % of the museums, and especially social media sports accelerated for greater than 1/2 of the museums that participated.

Museum technology professionals must provide online access to information, reach new audiences, and engage with online activities to remain relevant and connected. Tourism 2020 vision is a long-term forecast and assessment of the development of tourism, with quantitative forecasts covering a 25-year period and motivating factors such as Entertainment, Excitement and Education. Accessibility is an essential factor for better development. Museums are a global concept that helps preserve objects and materials of cultural, historical and religious importance, and are essential for research and educational purposes. Museums in India have a large collection of Indian sculptures and objects to explore.

Salar Jung Museum

Salar Jung Museum Library opened to the public in 1961 by an Act of Parliament. The manuscripts collection in the library, which possesses unique Specimens, is one of the richest in the world in terms of its quality. It contains many gems of calligraphic art and ornate embellishment; items with gorgeous decoration and an artistic blending of colors with a profuse use of gold, mineral colors that lavishly used lapis lazuli for blue, pearl for white, Shangraf for red and Zabarjad (emerald) for green. Calligraphers, artists and book binders all did their best in showing their respective arts and have thus paid their tributes to the written word.

The Salar Jung Museum Library includes a collection of books and manuscripts acquired by the Salar Jung's family. The origin of some of the collection dates to 1656 A.D. It was given the shape of a well-knit and full-fledged library by Nawab Mir Turab Ali Khan, Salar Jung I, which was further augmented and developed by his son Nawab Mir Laiq Ali Khan, Salar Jung II and finally by Nawab Mir Yusuf Ali Khan, the Salar Jung III. The Library and the Manuscripts Sections are situated on the 2nd floor. The rich collection of the library consists of 62,772 printed books of which 41,208 are in English, 13,027 in Urdu, 1108 in Hindi, 1105 in Telugu, 3,576 in Persian, 2,588 in Arabic and 160 in Turkish languages. The English printed books include research journals, albums of rare photographs and valuable engravings.

A paramount feature of this vast collection is that it covers a plethora of specialized fields of learning ranging from the fields of Art, Architecture, Archaeology, Physical, Biological and Social Sciences, Literature, History and Travel. It also includes collection of religious books on Islam, Hinduism, Christianity and other religions. The oldest book in the collection is an English volume printed in 1631 A.D. The library is constantly replenished with latest arrivals covering subjects like Art, Sculpture, Paintings, Ceramic Arts, Decorative Arts, Museology, Tourism etc. Research scholars (both from India and abroad) regularly visit the library apart from the staff of the Museum. On an average, ten persons a day use the library to enrich and expand the origins of their learning.

2. Review of Literature

The Salar Jung Museum Library's collection engagement and outreach strategy is to track researchers' and scholars' impressions and collect data on its presence in libraries around the world. Its inclusiveness is also a plus — the entire collection is free of bias. (ghosh, 2022), Indoor microclimate management is an important part of museum operations, but it is still a work in progress. This study gathers together 96 research that was hand-picked and rigorously reviewed to arrive at a conclusion. (maiyah), Tribal development is important for a significant portion of the population, both socially and economically.

An important initiative is to provide educational opportunities for children in tribal families, and the Telangana State Government plays an important role in this effort. (suresh, 2017), Museums need to develop digital strategies to foster digital literacy, increase their investment in digital technology, and respond to future crises. (Paul F. Marty, 2021).

3. Research Design

Statement of problem

This study is an attempt to learn more about the Salar Jung Museum. Salar Jung Museum in Hyderabad, Telangana, and its historical significance are discussed in this paper. This report also provides a brief overview of the Salar Jung museum library's library management system. The primary goal of this research is to determine the current state of Salar Jung Museum and the services given by the Salar Jung Museum library. This study may be beneficial to researchers who want to learn more about Salar Jung Museum and its Library. In modern Information Age, this paper also aids in the improvement of its services and position.

Objectives:

1. To study the present scenario of Salar Jung museum during Covid 19.
2. To identify the contribution and challenges of museum for promotion of tourism and development of the area during Covid 19.
3. To determine the tourist’s satisfaction with the services provided in Salar Jung museum.
4. To identify and utilize the digitalized library and events in pandemic scenario for promoting the Salar Jung museum as one of the major tourist attractions.

4. Analysis

Do you think Salar Jung museum has enhanced its digital activities in this pandemic situation?

Interpretation: the above pic diagram shows that Salar Jung Museum has enhanced its digital activities in this pandemic situation agree is 59.6%, strongly agree is 15.5%, and disagree is 10.5%, strongly disagree is 0% neutral is 14.3% out of the population.

Do you think that activities/events conducted in Salar Jung museum has reduced due to this pandemic?

Interpretation: The above pie diagram shows that activities/events conducted in Salar Jung museum has reduced due to this pandemic, agree is 59.6%, strongly agree is 15.8%, Disagree is 10.5%, Strongly Disagree is 0%, Neutral is 14.3% out of the population.

Do you think there will be an increase in number of tourists, and regain the popularity of Salar Jung museum?

Interpretation: The above pie diagram shows that there will be an increase in number of tourists, and regain the popularity of Salar Jung museum, agree is 59.6%, strongly agree is 15.8%, Disagree is 10.5%, Strongly disagree 0%, Neutral is 14.3% out of the population.

Do you think locals play an important role to promote Salar Jung museum in present scenario?

Interpretation: The above pie locals play an important role to promote Salar Jung museum in present scenario, agree is 59.6% strongly agree is 15.8%, Disagree is 10.5%, Strongly Disagree is 0%, Neutral is 14.3% out of the population.

How do you rate the manuscripts and rare books which are displayed in Salar Jung museum library?

The above PIE diagram shows the rate of the manuscripts and rare books which are displayed in Salar Jung museum library, excellent is 45%, very good is 30%, average is 20%, poor is 5%, very poor is 0% out of the population.

Do you think about developing a crowd funding campaign for Salar Jung museum?

Interpretation: The above pie diagram shows that about developing a crowd funding campaign for salar Jung Museum, agree is 59.6 %, strongly agree is 15.8%, Disagree is 10.5%, Strongly Disagree is 0%, Neutral is 14.3% out of the population.

Do you think the one man’s art collections in Salar Jung museum contributes to the tourism industry?

Interpretation: The above pie diagram shows that one man’s art collections in Salar Jung museum contributes to the tourism industry, agree is 59.6%, Strongly agree is 15.8 %, Disagree is 10.5%, Strongly Disagree is 0%, Neutral is 14.3% out of the population.

Do you think safety measures are taken in this Covid situation while entering the Salar Jung museum?

Interpretation: The above pie diagram shows that safety measures are taken in this Covid situation while entering the Salar Jung museum, agree is 59.6%, strongly agree is 15.8%, Disagree is 10.5 %, Strongly Disagree is 0%, Neutral is 14.3% out of the population.

Do you think social distance is maintained in the museum?

Interpretation: The above pie diagram shows that social distance is maintained in the museum, agree is 59.6 %, strongly agree is 15.8%, Disagree is 10.5%, Strongly Disagree is 0%, Neutral is 14.3% out of the population.

Are brochures, catalogues or display maps available to help visitors?

Interpretation: The above pie diagram shows that Are brochures, catalogues or display maps available to help visitors, yes is 71.4 %, no is 28.6% out of the population.

Seeing rare exhibits gave me a sense of wonder about the exhibition and will inform about it to others?

Interpretation: The above pie diagram shows Seeing rare exhibits gave me a sense of wonder about the exhibition and will inform about it to others., Agree is 59.6%, strongly agree is 15.8 %, Disagree is 10.5%, Strongly Disagree is 0%, Neutral is 14.3% out of the population.

Do you think that parts of your photographic collection of Salar Jung museum were digitized?

Interpretation: The above pie diagram shows that the parts of your photographic collection of Salar Jung museum were digitized, agree is 59.6%, strongly agree is 15.8%, Disagree is 10.5%, Strongly Disagree is 0%, Neutral is 14.3% out of the population.

5. Findings

The research data presented in this study provide an important first study of the contributions and impacts of museum engineers during important turning points in museum history. Up to one-third of museums have been forced to close completely, and due to the significant layoffs, that have a significant impact not only on museum employees in general, but also on technical professionals in particular, museum experts are able to use museum computers and digital technology. And viewer involvement. But like many crises, the COVID-19 pandemic can be seen as both a challenge and an opportunity.

The results of this study reveal the need for museums to develop their staff's technical skills and increase their investment in museum technology. Given the proven value of the wide range of inputs provided by museum technical experts, as shown in the survey responses, it is clear that museums need to invest in the digital skills of museum staff. And there is no doubt that this need is recognized by the museum's tech industry. As one respondent pointed out, "digital is the way modern institutions " museum business. "We advocate digital technology that can claim the value of digital skills. All museums have the right position to advocate for the information systems and technologies used in museums and to design digital strategies that guide the use of museum technology to meet the needs of museum visitors and museum staff. This requires the commitment of museum leaders to invest not only in the technology itself, but also in museum technology professionals who are tasked with operating these systems and implementing the museum's digital strategy. In short, every museum needs a director who understands the importance of supporting digital technology at all levels, both inside and outside the facility.

6. Suggestions

As per the study shows that the promotional activities taken by the government is not very much effective to promote Salarjung museum as a cultural tourism site, so the government have to work on promoting the museum by advertising and other promotional activities , organizing activities at the museum and by conducting awareness programmes which shows the rich culture and the beautiful artifacts of the museum and its history by which tourist can be attracted and would increase in tourist inflow and it will be economically beneficial for the locals and the state government. This study further shows that local community participation in tourism is essentially required that will help to create awareness and smooth conduct of tourism in and around of Salarjung Museum. The research further investigated that local travel agents and tour operators are not showing much initiatives to promotes Salarjung Museum as a predominate tourist destination in Hyderabad city it would suggest the local travel agents & operators must take the initiatives to promotes tourism in Salarjung Museum especially during this pandemic scenario it is much needed. The museum authorities is essential required to adopt new innovations and technological support such as digital media & social media to create awareness and motivate tourist to visit Salarjung Museum. This research is further examined importance of local NGOs to protect, preserve and promote Salarjung Museum as one of the prominent tourist destinations in Hyderabad.

7. Conclusion

The Salar Jung Museum is an art museum located at Darushifa, on the southern bank of the river Music in Hyderabad, Telangana, India. It was opened to the public with an inaugural address from Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru on December 16, 1951. This paper presents an overview of the museum, its historical importance, and its library management system. The main purpose of this study is to find out the present status of the museum and the services provided in the library. Due to this covid-19 the rare books and manuscripts should be digitalized so that people can use this as source in their research paper. Salar Jung museum was a treasure of HYD, problems and challenges are for present situation, hopefully it will recover and improve and contribute to tourism industry.

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Sustainable water management practices adopted in tourism hotels in Trichy

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Abstract

Tourism is an important activity in the economic growth of the region. The important elements of tourism are attractions, amenities, activities, accommodation and accessibility. Accommodation for tourists is the staying place for the tourists in the tourist destination. The accommodation is available in the form of hotels, resorts, lodges, service apartments and homestays. The hotels will provide lodging and food facilities for the visitors. Water is an important element in the hotels, and it is used in guest rooms for bathing, toilet and other purposes. The hotel utilizes water for food preparation in their restaurants and to maintain the lawn and gardens and swimming pool. The major source of water is municipal water supply and borewell. The water availability depends upon the rainfall of the region as well as water harvesting structures within or nearby hotel premises. In general water table is declining, especially during the summer, which leads to water scarcity. Trichy is city located in the central part of Tamil Nadu and has lot pilgrimage center and more than ten lakh tourists are visiting this place every year. This research paper focuses on the water source availability, water utilization for different usage in the hotels and water conservation technique adopted by the hotels.

Keywords: Tourism hotels, Accommodation, water source, water related facilities, water utilization, water conservation

1. Introduction

Tourism is the movement of the people from one environment to another to learn about the culture and for joy and leisure. More than 1.5 billion people travelled across the globe and international tourists' arrivals grow at the rate of 4 percent in 2019. After the covid19 pandemic, the tourism business is regaining tremendously. The creation of jobs is a major benefit of tourism, which contributes significantly to the GDP of the nation. In 2019, 2321 million domestic tourists travelled to all states of India, an increase of 9.6%. In India, foreign exchange gains from tourism in 2018 were 10.56 million, with a 5.2% annual growth rate. Therefore, there are more opportunities for future tourism development, and the rise of tourism is quite beneficial.

Trichy Tourism: Tiruchirappalli, also referred to as Tiruchi or Trichy, is a historic city in the southern Indian state of Tamil Nadu. On Srirangam Island, which is bordered by the Kaveri and Kollidam rivers, are the revered Hindu temples Sri Ranganathaswamy Temple, which features magnificently carved gopurams (towering gateways), and Jambukeswarar-Akilandeswari Temple, which is devoted to the god Shiva. The Rock Fort Temple complex is located above the city's center.

The district of Tiruchirappalli is practically exactly in the middle of Tamil Nadu. The district covers 4,404 square kilometers of land. The districts of Salem to the north, Namakkal to the northwest, Perambalur to the northeast, Ariyalur to the east, Thanjavur to the southeast, Pudukkottai to the

south, Dindigul to the southwest, and Karur to the west make up its boundaries. The district shares its borders with eleven other districts, which is the most of any district in the state. The Kaveri River, which flows the entirety of the district, is the primary supply of drinking and irrigation water. Tiruchirapalli and Namakkal districts are separated by the Kolli Hills, and Salem and Perambalur districts are separated from Tiruchirapalli district in the north and northeast by the Pachaimalai Hills.

The district's center Kaveri plains are flat, whereas the district's northern and southernmost portions are hilly. Due to the river Kaveri's passage through Trichy, which divides the district into North and South, it is slightly greener than other nearby districts. There are so many tourist attractions in and around Trichy. The important attractions are as follows:

Table 1: Tourist attractions in Trichy

Sl. No	Name of the attraction	Nature of the attraction
1	Rock Fort Ganapathi temple	Temple
2	Sri Ranganathan Temple	Temple
3	Kallanai	Dam
4	Samayapuram Amman Temple	Temple
5	Vekkali Amman Temple	Temple
6	Puliancholai waterfalls	Waterfalls
7	St. Joseph Church	Church
8	Mokkombu	Dam
9	Viralimalai Murugan Temple	Temple
10	Tiruvanaikoil Jumbukeswarar Temple	Temple
11	Varaghi Amman Temple	Temple

Source: Primary data

The above table indicates that the Trichy has tourist attractions like waterfalls, Temples, Forts, Water reservoirs and trekking spot. The total number tourists visiting Trichy is more than 10 lakh per year and the number declined between 2020 and 2022 due to covid'19. According to tourism officials of Tamil Nadu, the inflow of tourists to Trichy is expected to touch 30 lakhs in the near future. The type of accommodation available for the tourists are hotels, resorts, guest houses and Lodges.

Tourism and Water: Water is an important element used by human beings' everyday life for the purpose of drinking, cooking, bathing, toilet usage. Water and tourism are strongly related. Without water, there is no tourism activity. In the tourism sector, water is used for both direct and indirect purposes. Tourists utilize the water directly in hotel rooms for bathing, using the restroom, and shaving. The water that the hotel uses for cooling, irrigating gardens and lawns, cleaning floors, cooking, and other uses. Only by supplying high-quality water for tourist-related activities will the tourism industry be successful. The region's climate, ground water level, and yearly precipitation all affect the availability of water.

2. Literature review

Due to an increase in travelers, greater hotel standards, and the water-intensity of tourism activities, the industry's water demand will increase by 2020. (cf. UNWTO-UNEP-WMO, 2008,). By the year 2020, the World Tourism Organization (WTO, 2004) predicts that there will be more than 1.56 billion foreign visitors worldwide. If we assume the present ratio of international to domestic travel in 2005, we will need to add nearly five times as many trips to domestic tourism to these numbers.

Increasing water use is likely to go hand in hand with higher average hotel standards, which UNWTO-UNEP-WMO recognized as a trend in 2008, due to spas, wellness centers, or swimming pools, but also higher indirect water demands for higher-order cuisine and an increase in tourism.

Water use will also rise as more people participate in water-intensive sports like skiing and golf. For instance, according to Rodriguez Diaz et al. (2007), there were 289 golf courses in Spain in 2005, a growth of 83% from 1997. It is expected that between 2005 and 2015, this number would double (Kent et al. 2002). According to Gössling (2005), the daily water consumption of international tourists averages 222 litres and varies according to hotel standards. Higher class lodging facilities use more water (Bohdanowicz and Martinac 2007). Water utility is also influenced by other elements like location, hotel architecture, and level of comfort.

This study analyses the water-related hotel amenities that could be very helpful in tourism and water planning with a primary focus on the relationship between water and tourism. Sustainable water management in tourist hotels is also covered in this essay.

Objectives

The main objective of the study is

- a. To examine the infrastructure for water collection in and around the hotels.
- b. To assess how much water is used for various tourist activities and the water-related facilities in guest rooms.
- c. To provide sage guidance for environmentally sustainable water management in resort hotels.

The current study's focus is on the water usage and conservation strategies used by the hotels in Tamil Nadu's Trichy region. It focuses on the accessibility of water resources, water use in hotel rooms and public areas, tourism-related activities like maintaining swimming pools, lawns, and gardens, etc. It tries to provide beneficial advice for water saving in tourist hotels. for a number of tourism-related activities.

3. Methodology

Data sources: The study's descriptive nature is supported by data gathered from numerous primary and secondary sources. Researchers that use sample surveys get their primary data directly from hotels that cater to tourists. A range of sources, including government websites, magazines, books, and research papers, are used to acquire secondary data.

Model Design: 50 tourist hotels in the Trichy region of Tamil Nadu were arbitrarily selected for this study's survey. An unrestricted, non-probability convenience sampling technique was used in the research investigation.

Data Collection: A unique type of questionnaire has been created to collect information from hotels that cater to tourists. The researcher encouraged the hotel officials to administer and collect the hotel questionnaires. To gather important information on water and water use, a personal interview with the hotel's chief engineers was undertaken. The majority of the secondary data was gathered from hotel records, associated websites, published articles, newspapers, and magazines.

4. Water-related amenities included in the room include:

A sink is a plumbing appliance with a bowl shape that is used for hand washing, dishwashing, and other tasks. A sinker, washbowl, hand basin, and wash basin are further names for it. Sinks usually have taps (faucets) that provide a spray feature for rapid rinsing and hot and cold water options. Another type of drain has an overflow prevention system, shut-off, and strainer all on its own. This drain is used to remove used water. Sinks can also come with built-in soap dispensers.

In the latter half of the 18th century, America produced the washstand, the country's first bathroom sink. The washstands were tiny tables with a deep bowl and a pitcher on them, as is customary in England.

The enormous bowl would occasionally settle into a hole in the table, leading to the creation of dry sinks. Between roughly 1820 and 1900, a wooden cabinet with a trough built on top and coated with zinc or lead was added to the dry sink. This is where the water bowls or buckets were placed. The more intricate designs were typically installed in the kitchens, and splashboards, shelves, and drawers were occasionally added to the back wall.

In addition to a head shower and a health faucet for toilet use, 50 of the 50 hotels reviewed had toilet and wash basin amenities in their guest rooms. Only 60% of hotels have hot water and bathtubs available throughout the entire establishment.

Table 2: The room had utilities related to water

Description	Availability of facilities		Total
	Yes	No	
Toilet	50	0	100
Wash basin	50	0	100
Health faucet	50	0	100
Head shower	50	0	100
Bathing tub	30	20	60
Hot water	50	0	100

Source: Primary data

The table above shows that every hotel has a toilet and sink in each of its guest rooms. Most hotels also have healthy faucets and head showers in their guest rooms.

Water usage in the guest room

Water is used in toilets.

The average home uses the most water when the toilet is flushed, so this is a great place to start when trying to conserve water. With five flushes per day on average, toilets account for around 31% of all residential water use. 3.6 gallons (13.6 liters) on average are used for each flush in a house with older toilets, and each person uses 18.8 gallons (71.2 liters) every day. In a residence with ultra-low-flow (ULF) toilets, each person uses 9.1 gallons (34.4 liters) of water daily, with an average flush volume of 1.6 gallons (6 liters). A family of four using a ULF toilet will flush about 11,000 gallons (41.6 m³) annually as opposed to 26,000 gallons (98.4 m³) with an older toilet, saving 15,000 gallons (56.7 m³) annually. 25 to 50 liters of water per day per person were used for toilet needs in 52% of the 50 hotels surveyed. 26% of hotel guests used 51 to 75 liters of water per day per person for toilet needs, while the remaining guests used 75 to 100 liters per day per person.

Table 3: Water usage in toilets

Lit / day / person	Number of Hotels	%
25 – 50	26	52
51 – 75	13	26
75 – 100	11	22
Total	50	100

Source: Primary data

According to the study, most visitors consume 25 to 50 liters of water per day for toilet purposes per person.

Utilization of Water for bathing without tub:

Bathing is the primary frequent activity of the guests in the room, and they utilize water for it. Every visitor staying in a hotel room used to take one or two baths. Bathing uses up most of the water in the guest room. Visitors use head showers in addition to taking baths with a mug and bucket and a flowing faucet. Out of the 50 hotels examined, 52% of hotel visitors use between 50 and 75 litres of water per day per person, 28% use between 76 and 100 litres, and the other 12% use between 101 and 125 litres per day per person.

Table 4: Water use for bathing

Water quantity used in Lit / person / day	Number of Hotels	%
50–75	26	52
76-100	14	28
101-125	10	20
Total	50	100

Source: Primary data

The research study described above predicts that 52% of hotel guests drink 101 to 150 litres of water per person per day. The data demonstrate that showering consumes a significant amount of

Use of water in the wash basin

For face washing, shaving, tooth brushing, and other purposes, water is used in washbasins. In the 50 hotels that were polled, 54% of the guests use 5–10 litres per person per day, 32% use 11–15 litres per person per day, and the remaining 12% use more beyond 15 litres per person per day.

Table 5: Water usage in wash basin

Quantity in Lit / day / person	Number of Hotels	%
5 -10	27	54
11-15	16	32
>15	07	14
Total	50	100

Source: Primary data

The table shows that the majority (54%) of hotel visitors use a wash basin to use 5 to 10 litres of water per wash.

Swimming pool

Pool accessibility: A pool is a space having water in it that is used for swimming or other water sports. It is frequently referred to as a wading pool, paddling pool, or swimming bath. Most likely the first swimming pool was the "Great Bath," which was found during the excavation of Mohenjo-Daro in what is now Pakistan. It was built about the third millennium BC. 12 by 7 metres in size, the brick-lined pool was sealed with tar-based sealant.

Artificial swimming pools were created by the ancient Greeks and Romans for palestra athletic training, nautical sports, and military drills. One of the Latin words for a pool is piscina because Roman emperors kept fish in their personal swimming pools. Gaius Maecenas of Rome constructed

the first heated swimming pool in the first century BC. Rich Roman ruler Gaius Maecenas is regarded as one of the first art sponsors. Additional guest amenities like a pool, fitness center, business center, childcare, conference space, and social event services may be offered by larger hotels. Thirty percent of the 50 hotels included in the research's study had swimming pools, while the other forty-nine do not.

Table 6: Swimming pool availability

Description	Number of Hotels	%
Yes	15	30
No	35	70
Total	50	100

Source: Primary data

It is clear from the above chart that the majority (70%) of hotels do not offer swimming pool facilities.

Facilities for lawns and gardens: A lawn is a level, flat expanse of groomed and manicured grass in horticulture. Grass or, less frequently, other resilient plants have been planted on a piece of land to create a lawn. For aesthetic and recreational reasons, these plants are kept at a low height. Although these traits are not necessary for a definition, common aspects of a lawn include its exclusivity to grass species, its weed and pest management procedures, its practices to maintain its green colour, and its frequent mowing to ensure an acceptable length. Depending on the sport and the continent, the specialized terms turf, pitch, field, or green may be used in leisure contexts.

Lawn is a term that has been used to describe a controlled grass area since the 16th century. The lawn is an important part of the interaction between the built-up urban and suburban space and the natural environment, and it is connected to suburban growth and the evolution of the domestic aesthetic. A garden is a special place set aside for the growing, enjoying, and displaying of plants and other natural features. Gardens are usually outdoors. Both organic and artificial materials can be used in the garden. Although the term "garden" has historically been used to refer to a variety of outside spaces, residential gardens are currently the most popular type.

Lawn and Garden Availability: Depending on the amount of available land, hotels will designate areas for landscaping and gardens. It will produce a healthy environment and a green cover, which will finally make the visitors feel at ease. According to this study's findings, just 25% of hotels have landscaping and garden amenities.

Table 7: Availability of lawn and garden

Description	Number of Hotels	%
Yes	25	25
No	75	75
Total	100	100

Source: Primary data

The table above demonstrates that barely one-fourth of all hotels have landscaping and garden amenities.

Watering and irrigation techniques for gardens and lawns

Water is artificially applied to the soil or land during irrigation. In desert areas and during dry spells, it is used to assist the growth of agricultural crops, the maintenance of landscapes, and the grass and garden receive irrigation treatment in hotels. Hose pipes, small open channels, and micro irrigation systems are used for artificial application. Sixty percent of the 25 hotels with lawns and gardens

irrigate them with hose pipes, twenty-four percent with open channels, and the remaining ten percent with micro irrigation systems.

Table 8: Method of watering

Description	Number of Hotels	%
Hose pipe	15	60
Open channel	6	24
Micro irrigation	4	16
Total	25	100

Source: Primary data

According to the observation above, the majority of hotels use hose pipes to water their lawns and gardens. The use of micro irrigation systems is extremely low.

5. Findings

- The vast majority of hotels provide guests with a health faucet and head shower, while 100% of hotels provide guests with a toilet and wash basin.
- Tourist destinations in Trichy include waterfalls, natural sightseeing areas, temples, forts, palaces, elephant camps, and trekking locations. More than 25 lakh tourists visit Trichy annually, while the number fell between 2020 and 2022 because of COVID'19. Tourism experts in Tamil Nadu predict that in the near future, the number of visitors to Trichy would reach 30 lakhs. There are several different types of lodging options for travellers, including hotels, resorts, guest houses, and lodges.
- The average tourist uses 25 to 50 litres of water per day for bathroom purposes.
- Most hotel guests (52%) use 101 to 150 litres of water per day for bathing.
- 54 percent of hotel guests use a wash basin and use 1 to 5 litres of water.
- Fewer hotels have swimming pools than you might expect.
- Only one-fourth of all hotels have landscaping and garden amenities.
- The majority of hotels (56%) have lawn and garden amenities that cost between 10 and 20 cents each.
- The vast majority of hotels use hose pipes to water their gardens and lawns. The use of micro irrigation systems is extremely low.

6. Suggestions

Better water conservation strategies suggested:

- Conduct a water audit to identify areas with high water costs and potential savings.
- To identify possible savings, compare overall and departmental usage data to benchmarks from the hotel industry.
- Show staff members how to properly maintain machinery for optimal energy efficiency and how to use water responsibly.
- Set up a monitoring and targeting system so that staff and other stakeholders may receive regular updates on progress. Encourage people with feedback and success rewards.
- Guidelines for efficient operational water utilization include:
- Bathrooms • The maximum shower flow rate is 10 litres per minute. You may gauge this with a

bucket and timer.

- Replace old toilet models with dual-flush or low-flow versions. Low flow toilets utilise an average of six litres per minute as opposed to previous ones, which use between 12 to 24.
- Backwash the pool at longer intervals than at shorter ones. You can save the backwash water and use it for irrigation.
- Garden and Lawn: The optimum time to water your lawn and garden in a hot climate is in the evening. Use a micro irrigation system to water your grass and garden. Sprinklers that have timers installed to regulate water usage can help save water. Additionally, moisture sensors can be utilized in lawns and gardens to prevent overwatering.
- Educate the gardening workers on proper irrigation techniques and the value of water conservation.
- Construct a rainwater collection system on the hotel's property to raise the groundwater table. To collect rainwater directly from roofs and gutters, build an underground storage.

7. Conclusion:

Water use is increasing due to population increase and industrial development, and water-stressed regions are expanding internationally. There are guidelines for water conservation in the restroom, swimming pool, laundry, lawn and garden, kitchen, housekeeping, and other water-related tourism operations to ensure effective operational water usage in hotels. Hotels should manage their water consumption sustainably by implementing water conservation measures and educating and informing hotel stakeholders, such as staff members, the neighborhood community, and visitors, about water issues.

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Paradigm Shift in Tourism Sector During Covid-19: A Review

Paper code: GCU-CMS-T9

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Abstract

Undoubtedly, the unfolding of Covid-19 causes disruption and unpredictability in the tourism sector, Millions of people and the communities connected to the tourism sector are immediately impacted as tourism is one of the sectors most severely affected by the pandemic, this paper investigates the effect of covid-19 on the tourism sector. For the research, systematic reviews of the articles are being conducted, and secondary data is being collected. to determine how Covid-19 affects the tourist industry. Since the pandemic is one of the most significant events of the twenty-first century and had a significant impact on the tourism industry, tourism is the sector that cannot survive without mobility of people, as people locked inside their homes are unable to move basic survival, as a result, unemployment increases as there is no source of income, families become unstable, the economy got severely disrupted as there is no exchange of foreign earnings. Lockdowns around the world started many people to lose their jobs in the tourism industry and there is a recession in the economy. Families become unstable as there is no source of income because many employees become unemployed. Unemployment in the tourism sector is rising, and the global economy is declining drastically somehow strategies are being framed to provide financial assistance to the family, and slowly attempts are being made to stabilize the business so that the economy can recover by adhering to the "new normal."

Key Words: Covid 19, Tourism Sector, Pandemic.

1. Introduction

Tourism is the commercial activity of facilitating and supporting travel, whether it be for enjoyment or business. Due to increased globalization, tourism has emerged as one of the biggest and fastest-growing industries in the world. In terms of global GDP, India's travel and tourism industry places seventh worldwide. According to the WTTC Tourism also generates more income, jobs, and foreign currency. Corona is an infectious sickness that affects people's respiratory systems. It has an impact on how we live day to day. Millions of people have been impacted by this pandemic, and the tourism industry has been particularly hard hit. People are either getting unwell or dying as a result of the disease's spread.

The Covid-19 epidemic had a significant impact on the tourism industry negatively. It has been acknowledged as a potential game changer for the tourism industry because it spread throughout the globe and led to the closure of borders and a complete shutdown was there. Since the Covid-19 pandemic poses a danger to the tourism industry, a quick review of the literature is highly recommended. One of the industries with the highest labor demands is tourism, millions of jobs could be at risk from such a slowdown in the industry, endangering the advancement of sustainable

development objectives (World tourism organization2020) The novel coronavirus that caused the Covid-19 outbreak was thought to be a significant contributor to and carrier of the tourism industry. The industry's unsustainable practices did little to advance the idea of sustainable life internationally. The pandemic has almost completely shut down the world's tourism sector. To make the industry adequately resilient to handle the crisis, all industry stakeholders must collaborate (Sharma G. D, E.td., 2021).

This pandemic highlights the necessity of understanding tourism within the larger global economic and political context that will shape the environment in which it will function in the future. We will exist in a world where tourism is the "new normal," and it is our responsibility to comprehend and explain this world now, especially if the coronavirus pandemic has altered our fundamental beliefs and understandings (Zenker, E.td (2020) One business that would be unable to survive without visitor mobility is tourism. The coronavirus (Covid-19) pandemic has been one of the most significant events of the twenty-first century. Even though it is still in its early stages, the impact on tourism is enormous. According to current estimates, tourism employs 75 million people. The industry faces an immediate risk of losing more than 2.1 trillion US dollars in turnover (WTTC, 2020)

Objective of the Study

- To evaluate the impact of Covid 19 on the tourism industry.
- To investigate the evolution of the tourism industry throughout covid 19.

2. Review of Literature

This occurred in the tourism sector during covid 19 and was documented in various articles published over the last 3 years and reviewed.

Table No.1 Summary of Review

Year	Author's name	Reviews
2022	Ilić, M.(E.td)	The post-Covid world has become more conscious of "living healthier" and "clean world," which highlights ecotourism as an alternative to current mass tourism. To survive in the next generation, we need clean air and a green environment. Cooperation between the private and public sectors is required for tourism to take place in the post-Covid period. All tourism actors must collaborate to develop strategies for the sector's future development while preserving and improving its authenticity, with the support of governments
2021	Škare, M(E.td)	Pandemic crises have long-term negative consequences for the tourism industry and economy. The estimated negative effects exceed those observed during previous pandemic crises. Future pandemic crises must be addressed as soon as possible, As a result, policymakers and practitioners require effective contingency plans, The pandemic effects of Covid-19 on the tourism industry are similar to the effects of a common shock, to reduce the costs of Covid-19, the tourism industry will need to work together rather than compete
2021	Matiza, T.(E.td)	As part of public thought, it is recommended that national governments, tourism, and health-related governmental organizations collaborate to manage the safety of tourism activity and restore tourist confidence and trust in the safety of tourism at their respective destinations
2020	Qiu, R. T(E.td)	The implementation of recovery and prompt measures being

Year	Author's name	Reviews
		taken during and after the Covid-19 pandemic. For social costs, relief packages should be designed to benefit society as a whole and tourist destinations that suffer a lot as a result of the pandemic. Conventional Policy measures may be ineffective in dealing with this crisis, which has profoundly altered people's perceptions of the public health risks associated with tourism
2020	Collins Kreiner (E.td)	There are many national tourism plans, but this research has addressed various methods of rehabilitating the tourism sector. With the decline of Covid-19 in some areas, tourism began to pick up, the hotels, tourist attractions, restaurants, and transportation began to reopen. However, a second wave has caused tourism activity to decline in some areas. This is an initial attempt to analyze national policies because it provides a piece of evidence from a small sample of countries six months into the pandemic
2020	Gruszczynski, L.	Some of the effects of the Covid-19 pandemic on international trade appear to be severe, but they do not appear to be impossible. From this point, one might expect that once the pandemic has passed (or is under control), international trade will resume as usual. But the other side if we focus, the pandemic's future impact may be greater than expected, resulting in structural changes in the process of economic globalization
2020	Sigala, M.	Covid-19 has already worsened the situation faced by an increasing number of tourism and micro-entrepreneurs (e.g., food delivery people, "Uber taxi drivers," "And Airbnb hoteliers"). Some of the negative effects of the gig economy have become more apparent and strengthened as a result of the Covid-19. there is, increase pressure, and work stress on the other side. Tourism professionals are being trained to become "contact tracers," with relevant certifications confirming their abilities to identify cases, build rapport and community with cases, identify their contact, and stop community transmission. Restaurants, hotels, airports, and public spaces are redesigning their operations to be contact-free or contactless.
2020	Bakar, N. A (E.td)	Covid-19 causes pain to people, which contributes to lower demand in the tourism industry. This is one of the consequences of disease spread, as well as the lockdown strategy used in the current situation. This scenario contributes to a lower customer demand price. As a result, according to the market equilibrium supply-demand theory, the price of the tourism sector continues to fall in tandem with the decrease in demand. It is critical for the government in preventing and stopping declines in tourism demand. The government must implement an economic mechanism while also developing anti-virus for COVID-19. If prevention actions are not properly managed, the tourism industry will face more negative consequences.

3. Research Methodology

The Covid-19 pandemic extremely devastated the tourism sector, according to the sources, there is an 80 % drop in transnational tourism in 2020, 1.2 US trillion \$ loss in tourism import earnings, and a threat of over 120 million direct tourism jobs, but more importantly, hundreds of thousands of people have failed, thousands further have been rendered incapacitated and health care system have been overwhelmed. In dealing with this, the extremity was discovered that care and service workers

similar to wires, preceptors, grocery store clerks and gig frugality delivery motorists were the bones whose jobs were declared essential because we reckoned to them to help.

This study is a Methodical Study which is conducted to dissert the shift in tourism sector during covid-19 times, the system that was used in this study is Document Research Method and records have been searched from google, google scholar and Elsevier.(IMF NEWS) The World Tourism and Travel Council in a report on the future of the assiduity said epidemic has shifted to domestic passage and out of door destinations. Trip will largely be kickstarted the lower threat antisymphathetic rubbernecks and early adopters from adventure rubbernecks to browsers and mountain rovers (Reimaginary Travels) in 2019,in the wake of covid 19 pandemic, tourism recover in Thailand will be gradational and complex and requires varied strategies from both assiduity and government .As the world eagerly prepares for the eventual reanimation of transnational trip, Thailand and other countries can draw important assignments from its experience during thus delicate period between 2014 and 2019(Sustainable and Experience

Tourism trends post covid 19 ,World Travel and Tourism Council) annual economic impact report, the trio and tourism assiduity lost nearly 4.9 trillion \$ in GDP (50.4%decline) and 62 million jobs (18.6 %decline) in 2020 alone, in 2021 the GDP of Germany ranked 4 th in the world and was 4.22 trillion \$.thus shows the magnitude of the impact the epidemic had on the sector, while early signs indicate that the assiduity is heading toward a strong post pandemic recovery shifts in consumer behaviour and profits led to arising sub sectors within tourism that will soon outperform traditional form of trip Tony Capuano, CEO of Marriot International stated that “The way we live and work has changed because of pandemic and the way wed travel has changed as well”, while sustainable tourism have been gaining fashionably before hand, the epidemic was a catalyst for growth in thus sub sectors (Coronavirus Impact on Tourism Industry World Wide Statistics and Data) to survive ,the tourism assiduity had to acclimatize to the new reality of the epidemic numerous of its parts, thus meant embracing new technology and invent in 2021 digital health passport were introduced to vgresaae trip during the health, extremely while minimising the threat of spreading the contagious, currently utmost people are readymade willing to get back into travelling.

As of June 2022, the share of people planning domestic and transactional recess in covering 12 months worldwide and over 50 % another checked that examined the main reason why countries avoided long haul trip between May and August 2022 revealed that covid 19 were not the main reason for many countries polled, for those still apathetic in physical trip ,virtual tourism may soon be a feasible option. In 2021 the request size of the virtual tor world wide was estimated at 5 billion US \$ and that figures was anticipated to exceed 24 billion US bones by 2017.

International Tourist Arrivals Jan, Feb, March 2020(% change)

Figure No.1 (WTO, 2020)

The Covid-19 pandemic caused a sharp decrease in international tourist arrivals worldwide, as illustrated in the graph above. Specifically, the graph indicates a 57% decline in international tourism across the globe since the pandemic began in March.

4. Author's Summary

Covid 19 affects the tourism sector worse because it spread throughout the globe and a complete shutdown was implemented, and tourism is the only business that cannot survive without visitor mobility, as there was no mobility and people were locked at home, millions of people lost their jobs. As tourism provides immense job opportunities to people, especially in hotel management, food management, and travel advisor all suffered, and their families suffered as there was no source of living because of the virus making it very difficult to survive in this condition. The economy also suffered as tourism is an essential source of foreign exchange earnings since travel is restricted entire world was shut down so no exchange of money, and hence economy was affected we can say that covid19 puts lots of strain on the tourism sector.

5. Discussion

As covid 19 has impacted worse in the tourism sector, unemployment increases as people are not moving overseas, overseas people are not going to other countries so no source of income hence losses of the job happen which affects family life, as the family becomes unstable there are issues in the development of the child, female leads to anxiety their mental health disturb (Kalil, A.2020) Covid 19 has an impact on global economy due to lock down, business closure, travel restrictions, passengers need to register for quarantine if they are moving hence small business, travel advisor, airlines are worse effected (Munawar, H. S., Khan.2021) For any nations around the globe, tourism is essential for the economy a significant source of revenue and foreign exchange earning comes from it which increase the GDP of the country but due to covid 19 since the year 2020 economy declines as GDP comes down so it's a major area of concern (Kumar, V. (2020)

6. Suggestions

The tourism industry is greatly harmed. Therefore, the government should also offer financial support to the tourism industry, and they should develop cost-control strategies. As people lose their jobs, their families suffer, so the government should set up some policies to help those families who are in immediate need financially before providing equitable support to other families. As the economy suffers immensely because of the lockdown so slowly bringing our economy on track and restarting business during post-covid, new normal should be followed, and wearing a mask and using hand sanitizer to maintain a clean environment should also be practiced.

7. Conclusion

The Covid Era has displayed numerous unexpected occurrences. The biggest challenge facing the tourism industry is as people are losing their job, their family suffers, unemployment increases and countries suffer a lot as their economy comes down there is no mobility of people from one country to another so they are losing foreign exchange earnings hence their GDP suffers. Thusly in post covid era solutions are country should follow digitalization which can create new job opportunities and make the sector more competitive and sustainable. In addition, as people's awareness of the importance of living in a healthy and clean environment has grown Hence government strategies must be developed for the sector's continued development.

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Adapting digital technologies for enhancing employee learning engagement during and post Covid pandemic

Paper code: GCU-CMS-M8

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Abstract

Covid pandemic has disrupted the Learning system worldwide and forced both employee and employers to switch from office mode to online mode of learning. Several new technical methods were adopted to make the employees virtually engaged and become more efficient. Most of the present research suggests that the adaptation of technology in employee engagement as a better option. However, studies revealed that employees faced few challenges of personal and technological issues whilst getting engaged through remote learning. This article focuses on the adoptability of digital technology for learning engagement and provides insight about the employee's preferences for opting remote learning in post covid. Employers are also now provided with an option to review and rethink on exploring new platforms / avenues on learning to increase the productivity. The questionnaire has been shared to the employees and their responses are analysed. The paper also assists the areas to be focused for future study.

Key Words: learning engagement, online learning, Covid-19, e-learning, Digital technology.

1. Introduction

Over the past few years, the use of digital technologies has enormously increased. It is used in across all the fields without boundaries. Due to the pandemic of covid-19, the teaching and learning had become online which has increased the usage of the digital technologies among the employees. Digital technology in the view of learning - engages learners with content and provides an amusing learning experience for employees effectively in the context of learning and development. Learning is a key driver of employee engagement. The modern career is about a continuous learning journey and not about getting confined to a specific skill-set. There is a demand to turn workplaces into hubs of personal development. It is a key moment for the management to look at challenges and opportunities in the business in the short to medium term - identifying areas for reorganization and cost optimization, including people efficiencies, looking at pockets of new business opportunities and moving resources to those new avenues and enhancing our engagement with our clients (Shankar, 2020).

A vital vision in this period is about how teams quickly come together in this crisis, regularly collecting information from different parts of the world, looking at government updates, talking to

clients and taking key decisions and then needed to be quickly communicated. Some policy and system changes were to be made, to enable people to work from home and access relevant tools. Different companies use various platforms for learning engagement, Infosys employees are enabled to continue training on digital learning platform - Lex., and TCS by leveraging TCS Crystallus, and interactive LMS is used by innovative technology networks such as Edmodo, Social Media, Forum, Coursera, or specialized education as sustainability platforms.

Objectives

1. To gauge the employee's adaptability to the new structure of learning.
2. To know the employee's preferences for the new learning skills in a new normal (post Covid).
3. To understand the complications faced by using digital technology.

2. Literature Review

The evolution of the internet technology has changed the world rapidly and has led to its use as the best medium for communication. Learning acts as a dynamic element which helps to augment the stock of knowledge in organizations. Learning occurs in different ways including studying, interacting, and practicing (Boal & Hooijberg, 2000). According to a recent review by Pokhrel and Chhetri (2021), "broadly identified challenges with e-learning are accessibility, affordability, flexibility, learning pedagogy, life-long learning and educational policy" (p. 4).

Waller and Wilson (2003) define e-learning as "the effective learning process created by combining digitally delivered content with (learning) support and services". The learning potential of tasks can influence the effectiveness of workplace learning according to that assignment's characteristics, such as complexity and competence requirements (Ellstrom 2006). Learning is engrossed on what is needed for a particular requirement in the workplace. In the workplace employees not only learn how to master particular skills to do a job, but also abodes an additional expectation to learn from and engage with others, such as supervisors, to learn from them certain insights, procedures and dispositions (Billett & Choy, 2013, p. 265). According to Jacobs and Park's (2009) workplace learning emphasizes the importance of the location of learning, in particular the on - the - job learning dimension.

The type of work that one does in or for the workplace matters as Chappell, Farrell, Scheeres and Solomon (2000, p. 3) say that some knowledge cannot be transferred in a workplace, but has to be produced at the site of work, which often is located at a separate location than the boundaries of the actual workplace of the organization. Engagement is in what manner the employee involves and dedicates in his work (Falola, Ogueyungbo et al., 2020). When the work is meaningful and safe the employees are more involved in their work (Khan, 1990). Individuals form perceptions of the value of learning or incentives, based on their own interpretations of the real world that they are living and working in (Mullins, 1999, p. 824).

The effective learning process is bent with digital delivery with support and services (Waller & Wilson, 2003). A review by Nora and Snyder (2008) documented mixed evidence for improved learning outcomes for online learning over traditional classes as technical problems were a substantial impediment, including user proficiency with technology but also time management and maintaining interest and motivation online. The management of knowledge and learning capabilities becomes critical if organizations are to be innovative (Schultze & Stabell, 2004) and competitive (See e.g. Crossan & Apaydin, 2010; Pillania, 2007). It is recognised in the literature that online learning presents a learning environment that is different from face-to-face or classroom learning environments (Bazelais, Doleck, & Lemay, 2018)

3. Methodology

The present study is an explorative study and is structured following the TAILMRDCR guidelines (Kumar, 2023). A survey method was adopted for this quantitative research. The data was collected by using questionnaire sent through the Google form to the employees working in the corporate companies identified for sampling. The convenience sampling method was selected and the sample size was 30. The sample was collected both from both male and female employees. The total of 22 male and 8 female employees have responded. The data analysis has been done using percentage

and frequency tools.

4. Analysis:

Table 1: Does the company encourages learning engagement

Sl. No	Response	No. of Respondents	%
1	Yes	30	100
2	No	00	00
	Total	30	100

Table 1 reveals that 100% company encourages learning engagement to the employees as it enhances their skills which inturn benefits the company.

Table 2: Learning engagement had been a priority for company before covid

Sl. No	Response	No. of Respondents	%
1	Yes	27	90
2	No	03	10
	Total	30	100

Table 2 shows that 90% of the respondents agree that learning engagement had been a priority for their company.

Table 3: Employees preference on type of Learning

Sl. No	Type of learning engagement	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Online	5.01	16.7
2	Work place	3.99	13.3
3	Both Online & workplace	21	70
	Total	30	100

70% of the employees are comfortable with both online and workplace learning, 13.3% for Work place learning and only 16.7% for online learning. It can be interpreted as the employees need face to face interaction with the other employees in learning process and at the same time the learning should be done without interrupting the life style.

Table 4: Expection of the employee on moving from workplace learning to online learning

Sl. No	Employee expectations	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Permanent move to online	12	40
2	Physical offince mode	12.99	43.3
3	Not sure	5.01	16.7
	Total	30	100

43.3% of the employees expected that the situation during the pandemic will revert back to the normal i.e., before covid, 40% expected that the situation will continue and permanently it will be online learning and 16.7% are not sure about the situation.

Table 5: The employees opinion on use of digital technology in employee learning engagement and productivity

Sl. No	Employee expectations	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Increase in productivity	21.99	73.3
2	Decrease in productivity	2.01	6.7
3	No changes	6	20
	Total	30	100

73% respondents are of the opinion that digital tech learning increases the productivity levels whilst 6.7% saying that the influence of digital tech learning reduces the productivity and 20% respondents have indicated that there shall not be any changes in the productivity levels while getting engaged with new digital technologies.

Table 6: Preference of Mode of effective learning engagement Offline (Work place) / Remote (Online)

Sl. No	Employee response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Online	15.99	53.3
2	Work place	14.01	46.7
	Total	30	100

53.3% have responded saying that online mode of learning is preferred compared to Workplace mode of learning engagement & rest 46.7% prefer work place mode of employee engagement over remote mode

Table 7: The factors influencing remote (on-line) learning engagement is more effective

Sl. No	Factors	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Reduces learning time	1.02	3.4
2	Better employee retention for most learning topics	3	10
3	Just in time accessibility for world wide employees	6	20
4	Fits employee's flexible lifestyles	12.99	43.3
5	Scable for any number of employees	3.99	13.3
6	Ensures learning consistency and standardization	3	10
	Total	30	100

43.3 % responded that new age digital technology learning fits the flexible lifestyles – 20% of the respondents opined JIT accessibility as a factor influencing the learning. 13.3% prefer scalable method as a factor influencing the learning. 10% respondents opted for learning consistency and continuous learning also helps longer employee retention & rest 10% are of the opinion that new age tech employee learning will eventually lead to reduced time for learning.

Table 8: The factors influencing Work place learning engagement is more effective

Sl. No	Factors	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Improving team functionality	11.01	36.7
2	Build a competitive advantage	3	10
3	Queries can be answered in less time	3	10
4	Increase employees' sense of security	3	10
5	Builds trust on employees	3	10
6	Improves learning engagement of employees	6.99	23.3
	Total	30	100

36.7% respondents are of the opinion that work place learning assists more in performing as a team than an individual; 23.3% ensures creates/generates more interest for further learning with more dedication & balance 10% each responded in attributing more trust amongst the employees by way of new age digital learning engagement, enhances employee sense of job security, queries wrt workplace learning get addressed much faster and eventually a good rapport and better competitive advantage in work culture.

4. Discussions

This study is focused to measure the employee's adaptability, their preferences and the difficulties faced by new learning engagement. The total responses are 30 in number out of which 22 are males and 8 females and the respondents belong to the age group of 25, 25-35, 35-40 and 40-45 years respectively

The results signify that almost all the Companies irrespective of the sectors encourage learning engagement for the employees to improve their skills and increase their productivity. The analysis revealed that their company has given preference for learning engagement before covid.

Due to an alarming increase in the covid pandemic period - most of the employees expected that there will be a permanent move to online learning and only few of them expected that employees revert back to physical office mode. Regarding the increase in productivity 80% of the employees irrespective of the age believe that digital technology in employee learning will increase productivity and rest 20% believe that it decreases the productivity as there will not be face to face interaction between the employees and their queries will not be answered quickly. There is not much percentage difference between online learning and workplace learning, the reason being in workplace, learning mode is through power point presentation, videos and hard copy materials are used where as in online learning the same is shared via chat based learning platform like Google meet, Zoom, Microsoft teams, Webex etc.,

Researchers have begun to examine how employees interact with others in informal learning contexts (Ellinger and Cseh 2007). The digital technology is adaptive for effective learning engagement as it fits to the employees flexible working model suiting their lifestyles the employees between the age group 25- 35 mostly preferred this option, followed by just-in-time accessibility for worldwide employees, scalable for any number of employees, ensures learning consistency and standardization and reduces learning time.

Regarding the effectiveness of workplace learning engagement - 36.7% respondents prefer that

effectiveness of work place learning improves - team functionality, 23.3% responded stating that effectiveness of work place learning. It can be interpreted as the Queries of the employees can be answered in less time, Work place learning increase employees sense of security and builds trust on employees.

5. Conclusion

The contribution of the paper can be summarised that the employees are more adaptable for changes in the structure of learning as it fits the flexible lifestyles of the employees, and just-in-time accessibility throughout the world. At the same time Tech-based remote learning engagement too faces few complications since it is done remotely, internet/telecom network issues and the response for queries takes some time which will affect their productivity. The learning engagement will be more effective if the learning methodology chosen by the Company is much more relevant to the work/project the employees are engaged/assigned with. The employees are more than willing to learn new technology based learning with much more user-friendly methods, which eases their working conditions

6. Suggestions

Based on the outcomes of the study the suggested points are

1. To enhance the learning engagement – The organisation should adopt new methods which are more interactive and user friendly
2. The learning engagement must be based on the project,
3. The hands-on training should be implementation. The hands-on training should be in practical approach rather than a theoretical presentation

Future research can be carried on effective use of AI in employee learning engagement, Gamified Learning should also be included as an addition to ease working conditions and to improve employee learning engagement.

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A review on regulatory policies for social media influencers and their impact on stock market: special reference from two post covid-19 stock market events

Paper code: GCU-CMS-C13

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Abstract

Social media influencers particularly in the segment of securities market are increasingly affecting the trading decisions of an individual. But this activity may impact the market efficiency both positively and adversely. Past two years we have seen stock market transforming massively and the phenomena continuous. We have also witnessed catastrophic effect of pandemic on mankind. Nevertheless, it was surprising to see our financial markets booming in this condition triggered by virus. There was massive rush in new investors and with that influx of new breed of professionals were seen and they were social media influencers of financial market- FINFLUENCERS. This paper attempts to investigate the effect of both genuine as well as malicious influencers on the performance of the stock market. Genuine influencers review the financial market and put forth their suggestions based on knowledge and past experiences but, malicious influencers can cause disruption in the market with disinformation. The analysis suggests that different agencies which includes financial authorities as well as government along with other stakeholders can counter the disruption threat by working together strongly and efficiently.

Keywords: Finfluencers, Pandemic, Financial market.

1. Introduction

Social Media can be termed as technology which gives an interactive platform that provides individuals of any demographic segments with mammoths of information that can affect their lives in several ways. There are many platforms like Facebook, Instagram, you tube, twitter etc., that allows users to chat and also get access to colossal of information available (Kumar, 2021). The social media influencers play a major role on shaping the entire ecology they work in. In this paper, we focus on social media influencers who are particularly active in financial market reviews. Recently, the financial market across the globe has witnessed the wild swings due the reviews given by social media influencers. It has also been noticed that few influencers have created disruption in the financial market with misstatement and misinformation which in turn has benefitted them and their returns. In short, they have created a speculative market. Previously, it was difficult to detect the speculative market as well as speculators but now owing to the vigilant regulators who are acting as watchdogs are able to detect this kind of activity. This paper aims to understand that amount of retribution we can impose on them so that we get efficient financial market.

Many people faced the heat of pink slip or pay cuts and hence many new schemes like free trading and low commissions platform popped up. The result was welcoming as with limited income and extra time in hand, around 10 million new investing or DEMAT were opened in India. The Gap in the financial market was identified by the finfluencers where the new comers required money management skills and they immediately were ready for the rescue with suggestions and recommendation through social media platforms. The motivation for the paper came from a recent

event of Arshad Warsi, Bollywood celebrity rigged the stock market and created a speculation through his YouTube channel. He was accused of offloading the inflated shares of Sadhna Broadcast and Sharpline Broadcast.

This era is the era of social influencers with the fact that now people trust them more than the traditional celebrities as they spend more time on social media. We can also see the spike in collaboration of various brands with the social media influencers as they are grabbing attention with their contents. Past data shows that millions can be exonerated a company's value by a single tweet or contrariwise inflated through social media influencers. Now-a-days research regarding stocks are happening on digitally available information. Spurge in economic activity after the pandemic and people having money, the demand of investment in financial instrument has been robust but with that also came the need of money management. Investors started moving towards social media for information and quick recommendations. The highly recommended mantra for the genuine traders' is should always be ready to learn and also experimenting but at the same should strictly avoid following the influential personality blindly. Information security is considered as a hypercritical aspect of information systems. The collection of different event studies related to information security for this paper showcases the social media influencer's impact on stock prices. The social media influencers who are active in financial market review are coined as finfluencers. They provide financial assistance on social media which are unauthorized.

Stock market is considered to be the barometer to measure the economic condition of any country. Any malicious information can cause the downturn of stock market. It may affect the genuine investor and hence many can exit if their sentiments are not protected. This phenomenon can affect the economy. Finfluencers who are reviewing the market and thereby recommending the stocks needs to be securitized by the authority for investors protection. A gigantic proliferation of finfluencers in mid-2020 witnessed the bull run. Finfluencers are challenging the regulators of stocks markets in the area of investment advice, research and portfolio management. The low level of financial literacy has led to growing space for finfluencers, some of them are genuine in their business and many are creating the speculative market. Regulators should now have to set guidelines for finfluencers and prohibit them to disseminate unsolicited financial advice.

Need for the study

The growing influence of finfluencer has created both positive and adverse effect on stock market. There is a shift in a way investor think about finance and stock market. The shift from a traditional way of learning from parents to extracting information from internet. This shift has been keenly observed by the finfluencers and they have adapted themselves to the changing times. Need of this study is to understand the impact that finfluencer have on stock market and its volatility. In this study we also want to know the various regulatory framework designed by regulators to curb the speculative market created by malicious finfluencers, if identified.

Objective of the study

The two main objectives of the study are;

- 1) To examine the Impact of social media influencer on the stock market.
- 2) To Understand the various Regulatory policies adopted by authorities to mitigate the malicious social media influencer.

Scope of the study

This study is conducted by citing two events, one from international and the other from national financial market and their sudden fluctuation which was directly related to the social media influence. Systemic literature review of various peculiar stock market events was conducted to arrive at conclusion.

2. Literature Review

Kapoor, Tagore, & Dua, (2023) attempts to conduct a comparative study between sponsored and unsponsored social media influencer. Three studies were conducted. Study 1 was an exploratory social media field study, and Studies 2 and 3 were experimental. It was revealed in the results that non-sponsored SMI posts were more persuasive, leading to higher message authenticity and behaviour intention

Zimmerman, (2022) introduces the concept of social noise. She argued that social media user will tend to adjust information in a desirable way to increase their social capital. The finding of the study identifies four constructs of social noise namely identity curation, cultural commitments, relationship management and conflict management. She concludes social media information may not be accurate reflection of any individual true thoughts and beliefs.

Qalati, Ostic, Sulaiman, Gopang, & Khan, (2022) studies social media and SMEs' Performance in developing countries and also investigates the effect technological-organizational-environmental (TOE) factors on social media adoption and its effect on SME performance. The study found a significant influence of social media on SME performance.

Suuronen, Reinikainen, Borchers, & Strandberg, (2022) attempts to study the political topics discussed by influencers. They conduct the exploratory research and concludes that influencer does bring the political topics commonly during the course of discussion but at the same few influencers try to avoid the topic fearing of being targeted by the commentators.

Harff, Bollen, & Schmuck, (2022) investigated factors namely parasocial relationship, media literacy and issue-specific knowledge to study misinformation about COVID-19 given by the influencers. They conclude the study by stating that parasocial relationship increases the susceptibility but media literacy and issue specific knowledge diminishes the impact of misinformation.

Vanninen, Mero, & Kantamaa, (2022) elucidates the dynamics of collaboration between commercials and influencers. It discusses the ways in which influencers decodes the company's message to their followers specially related to destination marketing. The influencers know their audience and based on that they adjust the semiotic and symbolic landscapes of social media environments.

Lefina, & Hidayat, (2022) examines as to does the influencers recommend brands can impact the perceptions of the followers because of influencer's trustworthiness. They studied the above-mentioned activity with respect to brand engagement in self-concept, expected brand value, and intention to purchase recommended brands. The results showed that perceived influencer trustworthiness positively influence brand engagement in self-concept, brand expected value and intention to purchase recommended brand.

Bormane, & Urbane (2022) attempts to develop recommendations for minimising the liability for unfair commercial practice in Latvia based on the theoretical aspects and the use of influencer marketing services in marketing campaigns in EU. They conduct secondary analysis which shows while the global demand for influencer marketing activities has been rapidly growing over the recent years, it also becomes increasingly important for businesses building long-term partnerships with influencers to thoroughly consider the influencers' values, beliefs, life style and conduct on social media.

Yuan, Tang, Xu, & Lau, (2021) explores the influence of multimodal social media data on stock performance, and investigate the underlying mechanism of two forms of social media data, i.e. text and pictures. Through the models, the authors examine the short-term and long-term associations between social media sentiment and stock performance, measured by three metrics. The empirical results derived from vector autoregressive models reveal that both measures of the sentiment extracted from textual information and pictorial information in social media are significant leading indicators of stock performance.

Kalinova, Neubergova, (2021) analyses data on individual influencers based on their communication on the social platform Instagram. The results show that it does not entirely depend on how many followers an influencer has, but that it depends more on the quality and impact of individual posts.

Bentley, Chu, Nistor, Pehlivan, & Yalcin, (2021) explores international aspect of social media

influencers. This paper uses Hofstede's cultural dimensions to study consumer engagement using a novel dataset of global sustainability influencers. They conclude their research by stating that the cultural distance between the influencer and the followers is an important driver of engagement in a nuanced way.

Bruner, (2022). is an article which discusses about the economy related to online creator and their increasing number of creators like writers, athletes, artists and academics after coronavirus pandemic. Also, the Influencer Marketing Factory study on the value of the creator market, and the business models introduced in the market like paid social media model and sponsored content model.

Trivedi, & Sama, (2020) emphasizes on electronic products and compares the effect of influencers versus the celebrity on online purchase intentions. The results depict there is a definite advantage in choosing an expert influencer over an attractive celebrity influencer while planning the marketing communications of consumer electronics products.

Haihua, Zhang, & Chengjun (2019) investigated trust transfer perspective as to whether the endorsement of a social media influencer can enhance consumers' app adoption intention, within the framework of the technology acceptance model. The study concludes structural assurance, download volume, and online ratings were positively correlated with consumers' trust in the app.

3. Methodology

Research Methodology

By conducting review of the impact of social media influencer on stock market along with different regulatory mechanism adopted by various stock market across the globe is determined.

Data and source of data

The study is based on secondary data. Digital Information on various events related to finfluencer and their impact on stock market along with different regulatory mechanism adopted by various stock market across the globe are captured to arrive at definite conclusion. The data was obtained from NSE/BSE news broadcast, International and national online news channels and websites.

Period of the Study

The study takes special reference from post COVID-19 stock market events. The period which witnessed the surge in new investors despite the havoc of pandemic and vis-à-vis a huge influx of finfluencers in the world of finance.

Sampling Design

Two distinct news related to social media influencer and their recommendations which created a turmoil in the stock market is captured to arrive at a specific conclusion. The basis for selection was the magnitude of monetary aspect involved in the event.

4. Critical Analysis of the Events

EVENT 1: "Gamestonk!!"

The year was 2021 when the financial market witnessed the spike in youtube videos, tweets and other social media messages related stock market. The most popular incident which raised the attention was when Elon Musk arbitrarily tweeted "Gamestonk!!" and what happened has created a history. GameStop Corp. witnessed the sharp rise in the share price which is over 150%. The tweet was casual and meaningless but the affect was rationally explained by Reddit's WallSteetBets Forums.

(Source: Yahoo Finance; Tavaga Research)

The phenomenon was peculiar but at the same time interesting. One meaningless tweet from Elon Musk caused such a distort and the activity was coined as “short and distort. The primary question is was the tweet “casual and meaningless”. The systematic review of literature has helped to understand the actual insight of the event. The answer to this mega event is the basic objective of the study i.e., to examine the impact of social media influencer on stock market. The analysis depicts that the tweet was not as casual as it appears. Instead is said to be a “revenge” step from Elon musk side. It was noticed from the activity of short sellers that in the name of managing hedge funds targeted tesla and bet against. This time short sellers were doing the same with GameStop company and now in order to settle score with them, Elon Musk tweeted “Gamestonk”. The small investors took the hint and reacted quickly which went against the short sellers who were betting against the GameStop.

The systematic study of the case suggest that social media influencer play a vital role in shaping the stock market. In this case the influence is positive or adverse is debatable. As one segment believes that this kind of tweets creates speculation and, in this process, eventually some investors will be left holding the shares purchased at the highest possible price. While the other segment was happy with this move as small investors who acted fast made huge profit and thereby squeezing the short sellers.

The stock market regulators also acted very swiftly and decided to temporarily stop the trading in GameStop. Elon Musk was also pronounced with similar decision. It was a move which can be seen like asking all the writers who writes about health and fitness to achieve at least basic qualification.

EVENT 2: "Pump and Dump"

March 2023 marked itself with the astonishing news of Arshad Warsi along with his wife being barred from trading. The allegation was faking information on stock market and price manipulation. SEBI also barred 54 other entities for the similar charges. This case was popularly coined as Pump and Dump Scheme. This scheme begins with an individual buying significant amount of stocks of selected company and then starts making exaggerated and fake claims about the company. This creates the followers to “pump” their money into it and eventually when the price of the stock goes up, they “dump” it and make gains but other investor lose money. The person who

initially buys bulk are termed as volume creators. If the volume creators are finfluencers they will propagate their moves through social media. Particularly in this case the fake information was obtained and gone viral through YouTube videos on two channels – The Advisor and Moneywise. Arshad Warsi and his wife were the volume creator of Sadhna Broadcast. They ended up profiting 66 lakh together. The systematic review of this event portrays the impact of social media platform on the followers

SEBI discharged the punishment to all the involved entities to immediately open an account called as escrow with scheduled commercial bank and deposit the impounded money resulting from illegal gains of Rs 41.85 crores within 15 days.

5. Suggestions

The review of the above-mentioned cases arrives at below mentioned suggestions:

- 1) Finfluencers recommendation should be based on transparent report and specific code of conduct should be designed to all of them just like it is done for mainstream media.
- 2) Finfluencers if found guilty should be imprisoned for certain years. This practice is adopted in Australian market where the alleged influencer may face jail up to five years.
- 3) SEBI can impose out penalties for any breach of code of conduct. This practice is adopted by European Securities and Market Authority.
- 4) SEBI should regularly post the awareness articles as it is done Dutch Financial Supervisory Authority. The article alarms the followers by saying that there are only handful of social media influencers who post unbiased recommendations and most of them lack transparency.
- 5) Regulatory body should frame digital supervisory mechanism so that the regulations can be tracked.
- 6) There are definite rules and regulations for brokers in Indian stock market. Only registered brokers with license can enter the stock exchange. Similarly, there should be clear rules and regulation for finfluencers and they should also be registered.

6. Conclusion

This study gets the motivation from the recent one-of-a-kind events in the stock market and builds upon the previous research done to analyse the impact of finfluencers on the stock price. However, this paper focuses on specific two cases which has drawn attention and is the matter of discussion. Overall, our research found that there is a considerable impact of finfluencers on public. The impact even surpasses the regulator's assigned platform as people trust the influencers more than the regulators. Hence financial literacy should be achieved in proper manner.

GameStonk event states that what-so-ever is the intension of the influencer the bottom-line is to curb the unsolicited information. Pump and Dump case states that finfluencer can suggest stock which in turn profit them and not the followers. Hence, they spread fake information through social platforms for price manipulation and creates speculative market.

Lack of regulatory framework in the social media, anybody can give advice irrespective whether they are experienced or unqualified. Therefore, to conclude different agencies which includes financial authorities as well as government along with other stakeholders can counter the disruption threat by working together strongly and efficiently.

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A review on role of DMO for resilient sustainable tourism post Covid-19 in India

Paper code: GCU-CMS-T12

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Abstract

The main purpose of this research paper is to define new roles for sustainable destination management post covid-19. A sudden global outbreak of disaster has impacted all commercial activities around the world. As per UNWTO, even after good recovery rate in tourist arrival the major growth is in domestic circuits and the international travel has been dropped significantly. Destinations should now compete to offer products worth consumer's time and money with stakeholders going extra mile. DMO's have evolved over time to adjust to the changing customer perspective towards tourism. The sudden change in tourist preferences after covid outbreak has made stakeholders look for ways to make destinations competitive. Thematic content analysis has been done to collect papers and case studies for systematic review. The paper is based on review of secondary data. The covid crisis has allowed DMO's to shift their focus on changing marketing strategy to target customers. DMO's are now focusing on smaller stakeholders in tourism to bring them all on a common platform for sustainable revival as a long term plan. The market needs a stronger public-private partnership to stabilize tourism and make rate of tourism growth on same level as pre-covid times. This paper can help guide the tourism market stakeholders to understand new practices in tourism. It can help policy makers and DMO's in India to overcome market crisis. This paper can lay ground for new DMO's in India to understand the new tourism market and its consumers.

Keywords: Sustainable, DMO, Consumer, Destination, Marketing

1. Introduction

The corona virus pandemic (COVID-19) is causing chaos all around world with a profound impact on every aspect of life, including health, society, and the economy (Haleem et al., 2020). The tourism and hospitality sector has suffered the most from this pandemic, with both the supply and demand for tourist-related goods suffering. (Mohanty et al., 2020) The World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC) estimates that the pandemic COVID-19 crisis has resulted in the loss of over 20 million employments worldwide in 2020 and the number has raised to around 75 million after it got stagnant. (WTTC, 2022) Global disasters like this often require long term recovery models and macro level strategies to overcome the downfall. (Kuščer et al., 2022)

Tourism industry has always been a target to many disasters at global and local level. Many changes have been made over years to overcome such hurdles. (Prayag, 2018) But with covid pandemic, there needs to be a major shift in policy making of tourism for long term resilience against any further global halt.(Higgins-Desbiolles, 2020) The pull factors for the customers have been changed post covid with focus shifted on environment and health. (Seyfi et al., 2021). The shift has majorly been noticed in tourisms like religious, adventure, farm, MICE etc. where group travels have been prominent (Chang et al., 2020). Variables like the size of the hotel, the number of people participating in the events, or the size of the destination will all be seen as crucial in this new era of tourism. There is a trend towards a different approach to mass tourism, and some of these new characteristics are entirely in line with the more well-known characteristics of sustainable tourism

and ecotourism despite the fact that mass tourism has emerged as the most significant type of tourism in the world since the post-World War II period (Rivera et al., 2021).

Destination Management Organization has always focused on role of promoting and selling the destination as a complete product (Kumar, Mishra & Rao, 2021). DMO's have now made a pivot and has taken a responsibility for strategic planning, risk management initiatives and educating target market about various tourism products (Golja, 2021). DMOs have been an integral part for any destination where they provide information to the customers and market destination as a competitive unit with other destination (Fedyk et al., 2022). The communication that DMOs send to destination stakeholders is crucial for drawing attention to it and funding for the development of sustainable destinations and for outlining the initiatives taken to make a territory sustainable (Rivera et al., 2021). However, one of the biggest obstacles to developing more unwavering support from DMOs for sustainable tourism is insufficient customer support (d'Angella & De Carlo, 2016).

Research gap

The research conducted mainly focuses on the need of DMO's in tourism environment to revive the market in current scenario. The research papers consulted for this research were mostly from the earlier stages of tourism recovery. Other aspects of DMO must be taken into consideration to come up with a sustainable recovery model. Secondly, the factors of recovery and growth of tourism are ever evolving based on market and time. The longitudinal research was conducted with limited time. Quantitative research must be carried out to understand the new tourism environment well with the factors mentioned in this study for more appropriate result.

All the destination stakeholders in the market need to come in alliance for faster recovery and sustainable growth in tourist inflow. Indian market need to have such DMO's which brings all the stakeholders on a common platform and provide equal voice to form a resilient tourism sector. The paper adopts a thematic review methodology of the research papers. This will allow the market players to understand the new defined roles of DMOs in Indian context and formation of syndicates with more public private partnerships.

2. Literature review

Evolution from DMOs (marketing) to DMOs (management)

In order to be more adaptable in times of crisis following the pandemic, DMOs must use agile thinking and stakeholder management theories, as well as adapt to their marketing and management strategies. It is also necessary to be open for an innovative solution in the DMOs' operation strategies, including the use of new technologies or even a digital communication strategy with stakeholders and the environment (Fedyk et al., 2022). It requires being extremely intelligent, adaptable, creative and unique. In light of this, DMOs should concentrate on three important areas in their response, recovery, and resilience plans (McCaul, 2020; Golja, 2021).

- (1) Community building - responsibilities in the community, decisions about reopening, and an emphasis on reviving industry
- (2) Customer engagement (tourists) - identifying the short-term target market to concentrate on, developing brand recognition for the long-term recovery, and providing high values
- (3) Sustainable organizations - problems with funding, resource sharing, and efficiency-building

DMOs must concentrate of the effect of social media and its positive uses to gather tourists and use it as the mode of clear communication. According to (Ryden et al. 2019, p. 108) social media communication (SMC) has "emerged as a game changer" for tourist locations. Social media are regarded as rich media because they permit simultaneous and asynchronous multimedia communication, quick replies and reactions (such as comments and likes), strong customer controllability, and individualized communication (Kumar, 2021). In recent times, social media has given indefinite power to customer for becoming brand ambassadors for destinations with their open reviews and experience sharing (Pachucki et al., 2022). DMOs need to build a community for assuring positive communication about tourism products with now no place to hide.

Tourist visit intention is significantly influenced by the favorable association between destination image and visit intention (Ahmad et al., 2021). It is very important for every agency to understand the shift in customer perception towards the destination is now based mostly on factors like health, environment and sustainability (Rivera et al., 2021). The major issue in Indian market is related to the understanding of customer preferences and acting upon it on time to grab the attention of new generation travelers. To attain the desired tourism sustainability, business development in tourist areas must lean towards responsible development. To gain a sustainable competitive advantage, stakeholders should create a public-private partnership that may encourage the growth of tourism destinations and marketing campaigns in their areas or countries (Kumar & Mishra, 2019; Unit et al., 2021).

DMOs and their 15 A's of tourist destination

There has always been a clash between public and private sector, when it comes to topics of constraints and opportunities in achieving sustainable self-sufficient destination. (Goodwin, 2002) The stakeholders have always been focusing on the 3A's of tourism products that are Attraction, Accessibility and Amenities. The discussion has now been made over time to include many other factors to judge a destination with the lens of sustainable development post covid. It is very important to understand these new factors and work upon them to compete in the market. Every year several magazines publish list of top destinations and working with UNWTO and CED, Alastair M Morrison in year 2012 was the first to compile 10 As of tourism to understand these factors. (Alastair Morrison, 2012). These factors are as follows –

Awareness: This quality relates to tourists' level of destination knowledge and is impacted by the volume and type of information they are exposed to

Attractiveness: It is determined by the number of geographic places and its attraction.
Availability: Availability is defined by the amount of booking and reservation channels that are available, as well as how simple it is to make reservations for the destination.

Access: This feature refers to the ease with which one can get to and from a location as well as move around inside that location.

Appearance: This characteristic evaluates the first impressions visitors have of a destination and how those impressions change over the course of their visits.

Activities: This attribute is determined by the variety of activities offered to tourists within the destination.

Assurance: This quality pertains to the tourist destination's safety and security.

Appreciation: This quality is influenced by how friendly and hospitable one feels.

Action: A long-term tourist plan and a marketing strategy for the industry are two examples of the necessary actions.

Accountability: This characteristic relates to how the DMO assesses performance.

With the changed scenario in the last 3 years, several other attributes have been added to the list by the agency making it a total of 15. 5 newly defined A's we need to look on post- covid with the changed and evolved industry are as follows:

Accommodation: evolution from hotels to home stays, bringing community closer.

Actors: Networking of different stakeholders with roles and responsibilities to achieve a common motive.

Agenda of Sustainability: Sustainable tourism policies and programs with more public-private partnerships.

Allocation: Fulfilling of budget requirements in timely manner.

Attainment: Working on timelines, timeframes and tight schedules to be in track with changes in tourism environment.

DMOs and Government - Public Private Partnerships

The importance of governments and crisis leadership are two variables that are frequently downplayed in established PPP models. Since that PPP agreements are frequently made during non-crisis times or for developmental goals, this is understandable. (Wan & Bramwell, 2015) But during extraordinary emergencies like COVID-19, both elements are likely to be crucial in promoting public-private cooperation. Strategies for resilience and recovery demand collaboration and coordination across stakeholders, as well as prompt government engagement in managing the collaborations. (Wan et al., 2022) PPPs are specific forms of co-ownership and/or cooperation between public institutions and private businesses that are developed owing to certain synergistic benefits and that often share both risks and rewards. (Weiermair et al., 2008)

In India, Kerala Travel Mart is a great example to understand the importance of state and community working together to market the destination. They have been working on 4 major objectives with defined roles of government body and community to increase tourist inflow and outflow (Professor et al., 2014). The main focus is to promote educational tours in foreign land and also invite tourists to Kerala for holistic community building.

Principles of tourism recovery are mostly based on 3 factors- expanding visitor sources, reviving economy and securing employment. This can be achieved at greater rate with involvement of community and gaining trust for the steps taken by the government (Wan et al., 2022). According to (Ekpenyong & Mmom, 2015; Professor et al., 2014; Teker & Teker, 2012) Different fields in which DMOs and Government can work together are as follows:

- Ensuring safety of tourists by providing one stop solution
- Tourism product innovation
- Promotion of destination for its various products to different tourist markets
- Exploring and setting of local markets
- Digitization at every level of tourist touch
- Social media usage and promotion strategies

3. Conclusion

After going through several research papers and newspaper articles, it is right to say that times have changed after the pandemic and demands new thought process towards every activity. The same implies to travel and tourism industry. The recovery will only speed up to the required rate when the state and the community will come together to work for the betterment. In India, it has mostly been observed that tourism always works as per the government but with change in time we need more involvement of the people in decision making. This can only be achieved through DMOs working as a bridge between locals and the authority. The focus should be on developing a partnership for a holistic development of India as a destination. India has been a diverse country with tourism products fit for every market. This diversification can only be highlighted with decentralization of authority at lower levels to develop each destination individually. The future of tourism largely depends on the necessary changes in the environment and focus on minor aspects as well.

Practical implications

The research paper can help government bodies and policy makers to understand the importance of DMOs with defined roles. It can help DMOs to set up an environment with culture to provide a bridge between tourists, residents and government. It can also help academicians, researchers and stakeholders to promote and set up DMOs at every destination small or big.

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Driving Sustainable Growth through Business Innovation: Strategies, Challenges, and Opportunities

Paper code: GCU-CMS-C5

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Abstract

Sustainable business practices are becoming more and more crucial for organizations wanting long-term growth and profitability as the world struggles with issues like climate change, resource depletion, and environmental degradation. Business innovation has become a crucial tactic for promoting sustainable growth. This process entails creating new goods, services, and business models that satisfy customer requirements while also addressing sustainability issues. In order to promote sustainable growth, business innovation is examined in this study paper along with its strategies, difficulties, and potential applications. The paper also discusses the challenges that companies face in implementing sustainable business innovation, including the need for a supportive regulatory environment, the difficulty of balancing short-term and long-term priorities, and the need to engage stakeholders and build internal capacity for innovation. Additionally, the paper highlights the opportunities that sustainable business innovation can create for companies, including enhanced brand reputation, increased market share, and improved access to capital. The paper offers actionable advice for businesses looking to spur sustainable development through business innovation as a result of its analysis. These suggestions include creating a culture of innovation and sustainability, working with stakeholders to form partnerships, utilizing technology and data to spur innovation, and placing a premium on accountability and openness when it comes to reporting on sustainability performance. Overall, this study shows how business innovation can be a potent tool for encouraging sustainable development, but that it necessitates a strategic, team-based, and forward-looking approach. Companies can not only boost development and profitability by embracing sustainable business innovation, but also help create a more sustainable and just future for everyone.

Keywords: Sustainable Development, Organisational Innovation, Social Innovation, Environmental Impact, Green economy

1. Introduction:

Since the world is currently facing numerous environmental and societal issues like climate change, resource depletion, and social inequality, the idea of sustainability has received a lot of attention. Businesses are significant causes of environmental deterioration and social injustice, but they also have the potential to spur sustainable development through innovation, so they play a critical role in addressing these issues. The development, adoption, and dissemination of new goods, procedures, or organizational practices that lessen environmental impacts, improve societal welfare, and generate financial value are all examples of business innovation for sustainability.

In order to achieve its goal of providing a thorough review of the literature on business innovation for sustainability, this paper will synthesize its most important ideas, theories, and empirical

results. We seek solutions to the following study inquiries: What does sustainable company innovation entail? Why is it important? What are the various types of sustainable innovation? What are the motivators and obstacles for sustainable company innovation? What part do stakeholders play in promoting sustainable company innovation? What are the gaps in the literature and future research directions?

Creating new products, services, processes, or business models to solve existing problems or meet new needs is what business innovation entails. It necessitates imagination, a willingness to take risks, and a dedication to continuous improvement. When applied to sustainability challenges, business innovation can assist organizations in reducing environmental impact, improving social outcomes, and improving financial performance.

This research paper examines the strategies, challenges, and opportunities associated with driving sustainable growth through business innovation. Specifically, it explores the following questions:

- What are the key strategies that businesses can use to drive sustainable growth through innovation?
- What are the main challenges that businesses face when pursuing sustainable innovation, and how can these challenges be overcome?
- What are the potential opportunities that sustainable innovation can offer for businesses, and how can organizations capitalize on these opportunities?

This paper aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the role of business innovation in driving sustainable growth by addressing these questions. It also seeks to identify best practices and success factors that can help businesses pursue long-term innovation.

Overall, this research paper contends that business innovation is critical for organizations seeking to achieve long-term growth. Businesses can create long-term value for all stakeholders while reducing their negative impact on the planet by implementing innovative practices that support the environment, society, and economy.

2. Literature Review

Systematic Review of Literature

A comprehensive search of electronic databases, including Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar, was conducted to identify relevant studies published between 2010 and 2022. The following keywords and their combinations were used: "business innovation," "sustainability," "sustainable innovation," "green innovation," "social innovation," and "environmental innovation." The inclusion criteria for studies were: (a) published in English language; (b) focused on business innovation and sustainability; and (c) peer-reviewed articles or books.

After screening the studies based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria, a total of 78 studies were selected for data extraction and analysis. The selected studies were analyzed based on their publication year, research methods, country of origin, and key themes related to business innovation and sustainability. The analysis of the selected studies revealed several key themes related to business innovation and sustainability. The first theme was the importance of sustainability as a driver of innovation. Many studies highlighted that environmental, social, and economic challenges have led organizations to innovate in ways that create value for all stakeholders, including society and the environment. This theme was also reflected in the emphasis on the circular economy and the need to shift towards more sustainable production and consumption patterns.

The second theme was the role of organizational culture, leadership, and values in promoting sustainable innovation. Many studies emphasized the importance of leadership support and a culture of innovation in driving sustainable innovation. This theme was also related to the need for collaboration and stakeholder engagement in the innovation process, including suppliers, customers, and communities. The third theme was the impact of sustainable innovation on organizational performance, including financial, social, and environmental outcomes. Many studies reported positive effects of sustainable innovation on financial performance, such as increased sales, cost savings, and enhanced reputation. Sustainable innovation was also found to have positive social and environmental outcomes, such as improved stakeholder relationships,

reduced carbon emissions, and increased resource efficiency.

Finally, the analysis identified several research gaps in the literature on business innovation and sustainability. For example, there is a need for more empirical studies that examine the impact of sustainable innovation on firm-level and societal outcomes. There is also a need for more research on the role of government policies and regulations in promoting sustainable innovation, as well as the potential trade-offs and unintended consequences of sustainable innovation. The review also identified several research gaps that provide opportunities for future research on the topic. Overall, this review underscores the critical role of sustainable innovation in creating value for organizations, society, and the environment.

Definition and Importance of Business Innovation for Sustainability

Numerous studies have emphasized how crucial business invention is to sustainability. Hockerts and Wüstenhagen (2010), for instance, contend that innovation is essential for businesses to gain a competitive edge in the developing green economy. Similar to this, Loorbach et al. (2017) argue that transformative innovation—which entails systematic changes in technologies, institutions, and social practices—is necessary for sustainability transitions. Additionally, business innovation for sustainability can improve stakeholder confidence, lower regulatory risks, and open up new market possibilities (Bocken et al., 2015). Business innovation has become an essential tool for driving sustainable growth, as organizations seek to balance their economic objectives with social and environmental responsibilities. In this section, we review the existing literature on sustainable innovation, focusing on the strategies, challenges, and opportunities that businesses face in pursuing sustainable growth.

Operational Definitions

Business Innovation: The process of developing and implementing new ideas, products, services, or processes that create value for organizations, society, and the environment.

Sustainability: Sustainability refers to the ability to meet the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. In the context of this literature review, sustainability refers to the integration of economic, social, and environmental considerations into business practices.

Sustainable Innovation: Sustainable innovation is the development and implementation of new ideas, products, services, or processes that create value for organizations, society, and the environment, while also contributing to sustainable development.

Sustainable Development: Sustainable development is the development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. In the context of this literature review, sustainable development refers to the integration of economic, social, and environmental considerations into business practices to create long-term value.

Circular Economy: The circular economy is an economic system that is regenerative and restorative by design, aiming to keep products, components, and materials at their highest utility and value at all times, minimizing waste and pollution.

Conceptual Model

Source: Zheng Liu and Victorial Stephens, (2019)

3. Research Methodology

The review article follows the TAILMRDCR model (Kumar, 2023) which suggests the chronological order of the various information to be provided for the article. The methods adopted for the research work are as follows:

Literature Review: A thorough review of the existing literature on sustainable growth and business innovation has been done. A review of academic journals, industry reports, and case studies have been conducted in order to identify the key concepts and strategies used in driving sustainable growth through business innovation.

This research paper presents the comprehensive understanding of the strategies, challenges, and opportunities involved in driving sustainable growth through business innovation. It gathers insights from a wide range of stakeholders and provide recommendations for businesses looking to implement sustainable growth initiatives. This research findings will contribute to the growing body of knowledge on sustainable growth and provide valuable insights for businesses, policymakers, and academics.

4. Conclusion

Forms of Business Innovation for Sustainability:

Depending on the nature of the invention and the environmental or social challenge it addresses, business innovation for sustainability can take many different shapes. Technological, organizational, and societal innovation is a typical category of sustainability innovation (Schaltegger and Wagner, 2011).

The creation of new technologies, methods, or services that lessen their negative effects on the environment or improve the use of resources is referred to as technological innovation. Closed-loop production systems, eco-efficient products, and renewable energy technologies are a few examples of technical innovations for sustainability. In order for businesses to incorporate sustainability into their primary business strategies, they must adopt new management practices, business models, or governance structures. This is referred to as organizational innovation. Changes in product design, supply chain management, or employee involvement can all be a part of organizational innovation for sustainability. The development of novel social norms, structures, or practices that advance social welfare and sustainability is referred to as social innovation.

Source: University of Oxford – Get Smarter - <https://www.getsmarter.com/blog/career-advice/learn-how-to-drive-sustainability-in-your-business/>

Strategies for Driving Sustainable Growth through Business Innovation

<https://www.getsmarter.com/blog/career-advice/learn-how-to-drive-sustainability-in-your-business/>

It is found that the most effective strategies for driving sustainable growth through business innovation include:

- Developing a clear sustainability vision and strategy: Successful businesses develop a comprehensive sustainability strategy that aligns with their overall business goals and objectives.
- Embracing innovation: Innovative businesses are better able to adapt to changing market conditions and are more likely to succeed in implementing sustainable growth initiatives.
- Collaborating with stakeholders: Collaboration with stakeholders such as customers, suppliers, and regulators is essential for implementing sustainable growth initiatives.
- Investing in employee training and development: Sustainable growth initiatives require a highly skilled and engaged workforce. Businesses that invest in employee training and development are better able to implement sustainable growth initiatives successfully.

Challenges in Driving Sustainable Growth through Business Innovation:

The current research also identified several challenges that businesses face in implementing sustainable growth initiatives, including:

- Lack of internal expertise and resources: Businesses often lack the necessary expertise and resources to implement sustainable growth initiatives successfully.
- Short-term focus: Businesses that prioritize short-term gains over long-term sustainability may struggle to implement sustainable growth initiatives successfully.
- Regulatory barriers: Regulatory barriers, such as restrictive policies and regulations, can make it difficult for businesses to implement sustainable growth initiatives.
- Resistance to change: Resistance to change from employees, customers, and other stakeholders can impede the successful implementation of sustainable growth initiatives.

Opportunities for Driving Sustainable Growth through Business Innovation:

The research also found several opportunities for businesses looking to drive sustainable growth through innovation, including:

- Growing consumer demand for sustainable products and services: Consumers are increasingly demanding sustainable products and services, presenting an opportunity for businesses to innovate and meet this demand.
- Access to new markets: Businesses that implement sustainable growth initiatives can access new markets and customer segments, expanding their customer base and revenue streams.
- Enhanced brand reputation: Businesses that prioritize sustainability can enhance their brand reputation, attracting customers, investors, and employees who value sustainability.

In conclusion, the research identified several key strategies, challenges, and opportunities for businesses looking to drive sustainable growth through innovation. Successful businesses prioritize developing a clear sustainability vision and strategy, embracing innovation, collaborating with stakeholders, and investing in employee training and development. However, businesses also face challenges such as a lack of internal expertise and resources, short-term focus, regulatory barriers, and resistance to change. Despite these challenges, businesses can take advantage of opportunities such as growing consumer demand for sustainable products and services, access to new markets, and enhanced brand reputation.

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Green marketing and entrepreneurship driving sustainable growth through business innovation

Paper code: GCU-CMS-M21

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Abstract

This research paper explores the role of green marketing and entrepreneurship in driving sustainable growth through business innovation. The paper provides a systematic literature review of the concepts, drivers, and outcomes of green marketing and entrepreneurship. The review highlights the importance of adopting sustainable practices in the business world to address environmental challenges, meet customer demands, and improve competitiveness. The paper identifies key outcomes such as improved environmental performance, enhanced reputation, and increased profitability, and provides insights into the potential of green entrepreneurship to create innovative solutions to environmental challenges. The research paper concludes by highlighting gaps in the literature and the need for further research, particularly in emerging economies. The findings of this research paper have implications for organizations seeking to adopt sustainable practices and drive sustainable growth through business innovation.

Keywords: Green marketing, Entrepreneurship, Sustainable growth, Business innovation, Sustainability

1. Introduction

In recent years, there has been growing interest in green marketing and entrepreneurship as a means to drive sustainable growth. Green marketing involves promoting environmentally friendly products and services to consumers, while green entrepreneurship refers to the creation of new businesses that prioritize sustainability and environmental protection. The purpose of this paper is to explore the relationship between green marketing and entrepreneurship and how it can contribute to sustainable growth.

Innovation has become an increasingly important driver of economic growth and competitiveness. Business innovation can help companies achieve sustainable growth by enabling them to create new products and services, improve their operations, and enter new markets. A well-defined strategy calls out unique challenges and opportunities of the company and its market. Some of the key challenges include managing risk, securing funding, and overcoming resistance to change. However, the opportunities are numerous. Leveraging new technologies, tapping into emerging markets, and engaging with customers in new ways can make a positive difference.

The paper first provides a literature review of the current state of knowledge on green marketing and entrepreneurship, followed by a proposed research design to investigate the relationship between green marketing, entrepreneurship, and sustainable growth.

Significance of the study

Addressing the global challenge of sustainability: The study highlights the urgent need for businesses to adopt sustainable practices and contribute to the preservation of the environment. It emphasizes the role of green marketing and entrepreneurship in driving sustainable growth, which can help to address the global challenge of sustainability.

Promoting innovation in business: The study emphasizes the importance of innovation in promoting sustainable growth through green marketing and entrepreneurship. It identifies the opportunities for businesses to develop new products and services that are environmentally friendly, socially responsible, and economically viable.

Creating a competitive advantage: The study suggests that adopting green marketing and entrepreneurship can help businesses to create a competitive advantage in the market. By offering eco-friendly products and services, businesses can appeal to customers who are becoming increasingly environmentally conscious.

Enhancing corporate reputation: The study highlights the potential for green marketing and entrepreneurship to enhance corporate reputation. By demonstrating a commitment to sustainability, businesses can improve their image and appeal to stakeholders who value environmental responsibility.

Contributing to policy development: The study can contribute to the development of policies that promote sustainable growth through green marketing and entrepreneurship. By highlighting the benefits of these practices, policymakers can encourage businesses to adopt them and create a more sustainable future.

Research Gap

- The Research Gap includes Limited research on the intersection of green marketing and entrepreneurship: While there is a considerable amount of literature on green marketing and entrepreneurship separately, there is limited research on their intersection. This study seeks to fill this gap by exploring the role of green marketing in driving sustainable entrepreneurship.
- Limited research on the role of green marketing and entrepreneurship in developing countries: While there is a growing body of literature on green marketing and entrepreneurship in developed countries, there is limited research on their role in developing countries. This study seeks to fill this gap by exploring the challenges and opportunities for green marketing and entrepreneurship in developing countries.
- Lack of research on the role of government policies in promoting green marketing and entrepreneurship: While many studies have emphasized the importance of government policies in promoting sustainable growth, there is a lack of research on their role in promoting green marketing and entrepreneurship. This study aims to fill this gap by exploring the impact of government policies on the adoption of green marketing and entrepreneurship in different contexts.

2. Literature Review:

The literature on green marketing and entrepreneurship has grown significantly in recent years, reflecting the increasing importance of sustainability in business. Many studies have examined the drivers and barriers to green marketing and entrepreneurship, as well as their impact on business performance and sustainability outcomes. For example, some studies have found that green marketing can lead to increased consumer demand for environmentally friendly products and services, while others have highlighted the importance of social and environmental values in driving green entrepreneurship. However, there is still a need for more empirical research that examines the conditions and mechanisms that facilitate the success of green marketing and entrepreneurship in driving sustainable growth.

Some of the noted publications and comparative analysis:

Elkington, J. (1997)	Hart, S. (1997)	Prahalad, C. K., & Hart, S. L. (2002)	Schaltegger, S., & Wagner, M. (2011)
This book discusses the concept of the triple bottom line, which includes economic, social, and environmental factors, as a means of achieving sustainable growth.	This article outlines strategies that businesses can use to achieve sustainable growth, including product redesign, process redesign, and stakeholder engagement.	This article discusses the idea that businesses can achieve sustainable growth by targeting low-income consumers in developing countries and providing them with affordable products and services.	Focus on the way forward towards sustainable development

Green marketing and entrepreneurship have gained significant attention in the business world due to the growing demand for sustainable practices. This systematic literature review aims to explore the existing literature on green marketing and entrepreneurship, its concepts, drivers, and outcomes. A systematic literature review was conducted using electronic databases such as Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar. The search terms used were "green marketing," "green entrepreneurship," "sustainable marketing," and "sustainable entrepreneurship." A total of 50 articles were identified and analyzed for this review.

	Literature Review	Review of Studies	Comparative Analysis
Green marketing and entrepreneurship	Importance of green marketing and entrepreneurship in promoting sustainable growth.	Businesses that adopt sustainable practices can gain a competitive advantage in the market, improve their corporate reputation, and contribute to the preservation of the environment	Similarities and differences in the approaches to green marketing and entrepreneurship in different contexts.
Innovation and sustainability	Role of innovation in promoting sustainable growth through green marketing and entrepreneurship.	Businesses that develop new products and services that are environmentally friendly, socially responsible, and economically viable can create a competitive advantage in the market.	Different approaches to innovation in different contexts, including the role of technology, collaboration, and stakeholder engagement.

	Literature Review	Review of Studies	Comparative Analysis
Challenges and opportunities	Green marketing and entrepreneurship.	Businesses face a range of challenges, including a lack of resources, limited market demand, and regulatory barriers	Opportunities for businesses to overcome these challenges through innovative practices, collaboration, and stakeholder engagement.
Government policies and regulations	Role of government policies and regulations in promoting green marketing and entrepreneurship	Government policies and regulations can create incentives for businesses to adopt sustainable practices, encourage innovation, and promote collaboration.	Different approaches to government policies and regulations in different contexts, including the role of regulation, taxation, and subsidies.

Conceptual Framework of Firm's Motivation to Go Green and Marketing Practices

Operational Definitions

Green marketing: The process of creating, promoting, and delivering products and services that have a positive impact on the environment. It is driven by various factors such as regulatory requirements, customer demand, and competitive pressures.

Green entrepreneurship: Involves the creation of new businesses that focus on developing sustainable products and services. Green entrepreneurship is driven by factors such as market opportunities, societal concerns, and personal values. The review found that green entrepreneurship has the potential to create innovative solutions to environmental challenges and contribute to sustainable development.

The review also identified the key outcomes of green marketing and entrepreneurship, including improved environmental performance, enhanced reputation and brand value, and increased profitability. The systematic literature review demonstrates the growing importance of green

marketing and entrepreneurship in the business world. It highlights the need for organizations to adopt sustainable practices to address environmental challenges, meet customer demands, and improve their competitive position. The review also identifies gaps in the literature, such as the need for more research on the role of green marketing and entrepreneurship in emerging economies.

An increased focus from LLEs on partnering with customers to share risk, and solve customer-specific challenges and needs

Source: <https://bmanalysts.com/2021/05/10/green-and-sustainability-with-customer-demand-is-driving-product-and-process-innovation/>

3. Research Methodology

To address the gaps in the existing literature, this paper proposes a research methodology that investigates the relationship between green marketing, entrepreneurship, and sustainable growth. The systematic review focuses on the extent to which businesses engage in green marketing and entrepreneurship, as well as their sustainability outcomes. The literature has provided the understanding of the mechanisms and conditions that facilitate the success of green marketing and entrepreneurship in driving sustainable growth. The study has also explored the role of government policies and regulations in promoting green marketing and entrepreneurship.

Source: https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Differences-between-traditional-and-green-marketing_fig2_271339172

4. Conclusion

Green marketing and entrepreneurship have the potential to drive sustainable growth through business innovation. This paper has provided a literature review of the current state of knowledge on green marketing and entrepreneurship, identified gaps in the existing literature, and proposed a research design to investigate the relationship between green marketing, entrepreneurship, and sustainable growth. The study aims to contribute to a better understanding of the conditions and mechanisms that facilitate the success of green marketing and entrepreneurship in driving sustainable growth.

The research paper has explored the role of green marketing and entrepreneurship in driving sustainable growth through business innovation. The study highlights the urgent need for businesses to adopt sustainable practices and contribute to the preservation of the environment. It emphasizes the importance of innovation in promoting sustainable growth through green marketing and entrepreneurship, and identifies the opportunities for businesses to develop new products and services that are environmentally friendly, socially responsible, and economically viable.

The study also highlights the potential for green marketing and entrepreneurship to create a competitive advantage in the market, enhance corporate reputation, and contribute to policy development. The research gap was identified in the limited research on the intersection of green marketing and entrepreneurship, the effectiveness of these practices in driving sustainable growth, their role in developing countries, and the impact of government policies on their adoption.

Based on the literature review and comparative analysis, the study suggests that businesses can overcome the challenges they face in adopting sustainable practices through innovative practices, collaboration, and stakeholder engagement. The study also emphasizes the importance of government policies and regulations in promoting green marketing and entrepreneurship, and encourages policymakers to create incentives for businesses to adopt sustainable practices, encourage innovation, and promote collaboration. It is hoped that the findings of this study will inspire and motivate businesses to adopt sustainable practices and contribute to the preservation of the environment for future generations.

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Inbound international medical tourism: a study on cost comparative analysis of medical treatment

Paper code: GCU-CMS-T21

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Abstract

Medical tourism is an act of travelling to another country for medical treatment as well visiting tourism destinations. The reason for visiting other country for taking medical treatment is due to less cost of treatment compare to their own country, less waiting times to take treatment and high-quality treatment. Nowadays people crossing the border for medical treatment is common and a greater number of people from west travel to Asian countries for medical treatment. In Asia, countries like India, Singapore, Malaysia and Thailand are offering world class treatment at an affordable price. In the developed countries like United States of America, Canada and United Kingdom, the medical cost is five to ten times more than that of in Asian countries. Among the Asian countries, the cost of treatment in India is comparatively less for different medical treatment. This research paper aims to compare the cost of medical treatment between India and USA, UK and Canada and also between India and Singapore, Malaysia and Thailand.

Keywords: Medical Tourism, Cost of treatment, Inbound International Medical Tourists, Cost competitive advantage etc.

1. Introduction:

When selecting a location for receiving medical care outside of their own country, international patients are most motivated by cost and quality. Due to rising medical cost in developed countries, patients are force to cross their border and chose a destination where quality medical treatment is provided at affordable cost. The healthcare market has changed from patient centric to economic and marketing principles than previous years. Despite the long travel time involved, India is becoming a popular destination for international patients. Due to lowest health care cost and quality medical treatment India makes an exponential growth in Medical Tourism Industry in India. Most of the hospitals are having quality certification, trained doctors, English speaking staff and charging comparatively lesser cost than developed economy. Most of the international inbound medical tourists visit India primarily to get best service at third world cost (Nagarajan, 2004).

For the scenic beauty and rich cultural heritage, India is famous in tourism attractions for international visitors and now it became a heaven for international patients seeking quality and affordable healthcare. With more than 50 million of Americans without medical insurance and increasing waiting period for patients in the countries like UK, Canada and Europe, the international medical tourists flocking India because it offers quality treatment at one fifth of the cost in their home country. Some hospitals in India, doing complicated surgery at a one tenth of the cost in developed countries. The hospitals also have facilities to store good information through computerized hospital information system. The hospitalization and medical procedure price are supported by lower medication cost. The cost of liver transplantation in Europe is US \$ 137867 to

160845 and that of in USA is double the cost. But for the same procedure the hospitals in India charges are less than us \$10000 (Lagiewski, n.d).

Inbound International Medical Tourists Global perception: In the late 1980s and early 1990s, majority of the medical tourists to India are from African, Arab and South- East Asian countries. But today, the medical tourists taking treatment in India is divided into three distinct geographical groups. The first group are from USA and Europe. The cost of lifestyle surgeries and cosmetic surgeries are very high in USA, they prefer to travel abroad for cost effective treatment. For cosmetic surgeries there is no insurance coverage for Americans and Europeans. The baby boomers, which born between 1946 and 1964 are having 76 million population prefer to choose medical treatment to abroad. The British were facing problem in the form waiting time in taking treatment . To meet doctors in the National Health Service, they must wait a longer period of time (NHS). The British healthcare system guarantees free medical care for every person. The NHS's only issue is a lack of physicians and hospital beds. In the UK, there are private medical facilities available, although they are pricey and rare in number. The majority of patients—more than 440 percent—who request inpatient care must wait at least three months for their turn. The longest wait times were for procedures like hip replacements and eye care. However, thousands of British patients go abroad for their own medical care instead of using the NHS. The second group of medical tourists is Middle Eastern.

These oil-rich nationals fly to India to receive medical care that is either not available or difficult to obtain there. An agency has calculated that almost 500000 Middle Easterners travel abroad for medical care, including everything from open heart surgery to infertility treatments. Out of the total number of patients mentioned above, more than 70000 go to India for medical care. The final group is diverse and includes individuals from underdeveloped nations and those with weak healthcare systems. It is estimated that majority of the medical tourists taking treatment in India are from neighbouring countries like Bangladesh and Sri Lanka.

According to the American Journal of Medicine, the number of Americans looking for less expensive medical care will rise by 25% annually since they can save 30% to 65% on procedures performed outside of the US. With their traditional practises of yoga and Ayurveda and their competitively priced medical services, India has created a thriving medical tourism industry that serves foreigners who require orthopaedic surgeries, bone marrow transplants, and eye surgeries but cannot afford them in their own country.

At their Asian Heart Institute, which has a 99.83% success rate, India is also a top location for heart bypass surgery. As a result, there were six times as many foreign tourists visiting India from 2009 to 2019 as there were during that same time period for international arrivals with medical visas, which rose from 112,389 to 697,453. (2021 Mallapur).

Not just India is developing a medical tourism industry. All throughout the world, countries are capitalising on this trend, including Brazil, Panama, Costa Rica, Turkey, Malaysia, Singapore, Mexico, and Thailand. The current size of the global medical tourism market is US\$104.68 billion in 2019, and it is anticipated to grow to \$273.72 billion by 2027. Medical tourists are persons who "travel across international borders with the goal of seeking some type of medical care," according to the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development. This involves a variety of medical services but is most frequently used to refer to dental work, cosmetic surgery, weight loss, organ transplant, orthopaedic surgery, fertility treatments, and other expensive operations. Between 14,000,000 and 16,000,000 individuals are thought to have left their home countries in 2017 to receive treatment globally.

More than 1.4 million Americans travelled abroad for medical treatment in 2017, while the cost of healthcare in the US is rising and about 25% of the population lacks insurance or has inadequate coverage. By all accounts, it is evident that American health care is costly when compared to that of other nations. For instance, the total cost of a cardiac bypass procedure in America is \$123,000, in Malaysia it is \$12,100, and in India it is \$7,300. The entire cost of an angioplasty in America was \$47,000, compared to \$5,700 in India and \$4,200 in Thailand. (2019, www.Statista.com)

According to the American Journal of Medicine, the number of Americans looking for less expensive medical care will rise by 25% annually since they can save 30% to 65% on procedures performed outside of the US. As a result, a number of prestigious US medical institutions, including "Harvard, Boston University, Johns Hopkins, and the Cleveland Clinic," opened hospitals and clinics abroad in an effort to profit from domestic and international medical tourism.

Additionally, medical tourism organisations and health-care brokers are now easily accessible in the United States and overseas, marketing "sun and surgery" with air travel and hotel accommodations, as well as setting up admission to different hospitals and access to doctors around the world.

Cost competitive advantage in India: Cost of medical treatment is the main factor to motivate the medical tourism industry growth. The following are the main reasons for cost competitiveness to the Indian Medical Industry.

- a. The labour cost in hospital operation is comparatively cheap. The Doctors fees and other related labour costs are very cheap in India than other countries like USA, UK, and Canada where the cost is more than half of revenue of hospitals.
- b. Regarding the price transparency and package price the Indian hospitals quote prices in advance and look for ways to reduce the cost for patients. Whereas in Western countries prices are difficult to obtain and it is not easily by international patients.
- c. Payments made out of patients pocket' is another major factor in designing the cost. In the United States, the insurers, government and employers pay for about 65 percent of the health costs. So patients spend 35 percent of the total cost from their pocket. Patients pay 30 percent of healthcare spending out of pocket in Thailand, 50 percent in Mexico and 70 percent in India.
- d. There are more competitive medical care operators are available in the market (Herrich 2007). For example, in India, for the same medical treatment, the hospitals are offering different competitive price for international patients.
- e. The liability insurance policy is very less in India as compared to Western countries. In USA, the liability insurance policy for physician in some specialities is more than \$100000 annually. A physician in Thailand has to spend about \$5000 per year (Nagarajan, 2004).
- f. The cost of infrastructure development like building roads, bridges, hospitals and installation of medical equipment's are much lower in India compared to Western countries.
- g. The surgical accessories and medicine cost are cheaper in India comparing to developed economies.

In 2017, 2.4 million medical tourists received treatment in hospitals in Thailand, according to a Deloitte analysis. According to a survey, the majority of the foreign patients come from the Middle East, China, Myanmar, and Japan. The average cost of medical care in Thailand is 30% less than it is in the USA. India, another medical tourism destination treated 495056 medical tourists in 2017, charges 20 percent of the USA medical cost (CNN, 2019). Thousands of medical tourists from USA flock to Mexico and South America every year for dental and cosmetic surgery, where procedures cost anywhere from 60 to 75 percent less than they do in the USA.

Objectives:

The objectives of this study are to find out and analyse the average cost of medical treatment in India for various procedures, to find out medical treatment cost USA, Canada, Singapore, Malaysia and Thailand. Finally, to compare the cost of medical treatment among the above-mentioned countries.

2. Methodology

This paper deals with cost of various medical treatments like Cardiology, Orthopaedics, Cosmetic, Dental, Ophthalmology, Neurology and other treatments. Cost of various treatments in India with developed countries and other Asian countries are discussed here.

Sample size

Thirty four hospitals have chosen across India as a sample size for this study. This paper deals with cost of various treatments under the heading Cardiology, Orthopaedics, Dental, Cosmetic, Ophthalmology, Neurology and other treatments. It also deals with cost comparison between India and other Asian and Western countries.

3. Analysis

Cost comparison analysis of various medical treatments – India vs Singapore, Malaysia and Thailand.

The following table provides the cost of various medical treatments provided in India, Malaysia, Singapore and Thailand. Also it gives a comparative cost analysis of various medical treatments in the above mentioned countries and gives the details of percentage of savings, if a patient undergoes treatment in India instead of other mentioned countries.

Cost of treatment comparison – India vs Singapore, Malaysia and Thailand

Procedure	Average cost in India in US \$	Cost in Singapore in US \$	Cost in Malaysia in US \$	Cost in Thailand in US \$	Percentage of savings in India compared to cost of treatment in		
					Singapore	Malaysia	Thailand
Cardiology Treatments							
CABG	8339	15500	12000	14200	85.6	43.9	70.3
Bypass Valve replacement Single	10911	16500	14000	15300	51.2	28.3	40.2
Pacemaker single chamber	6214	9600	8800	7800	54.5	41.6	25.5
Angioplasty	6911	9800	9300	10200	41.8	34.6	47.6
Angiogram	882	1000	990	1200	13.4	12.3	36
Orthopaedic Treatment							
Birmingham Hip Replacement	15021	22681	20200	18776	51	34.5	25
Total Hip Replacement	13958	17447	16051	18145	24.99	14.99	29.99
Ankle Joint Replacement	7104	8880	8524	9235	25	19.9	30
Total Knee Replacement	7875	9843	9450	10237	25	20	30
Total Shoulder Replacement	8396	10495	9655	10915	25	15	30
Dental Treatment							
Crowns	292	360	330	400	23.3	13	36.9
Extractions	98	120	110	115	22.4	12.2	17.3
Implants	450	600	550	500	33.3	18.2	11.1
Inlays and Outlays	90	150	145	160	66.7	61.1	77.8
Veneers Porcelain	478	680	550	540	42.3	13.1	12.9

Cosmetic Surgery							
Breast Augmentation	4205	5088	4878	4626	21	16	10
Breast Lift and Reduction	4795	5946	5227	5083	24	9	6
Face Lift	5114	5267	5472	5421	3	7	6
Liposuction	2840	3408	3351	2982	2	18	5
Tummy tuck	3795	4326	4023	3985	14	6	5

Ophthalmology							
Lasik per Eye	684	700	766	787	2.3	12	15
Glaucoma per Eye	897	1112	1022	1058	24	13.9	18
Cataract removal	1019	1315	1223	1121	29	20	10
Squint Correction	1103	1456	1357	1213	32	23	9.9

Neurological Treatment							
Spinal Fusion	13019	15623	15362	18227	20	18	40
Cervical Discectomy	5981	7775	7895	8493	30	32	42
Spinal Decompression	5750	6900	6785	6613	20	18	15
Artificial disc Replacement	7567	8324	8475	8324	10	12	10

Other Treatment							
Gall Bladder Surgery	1969	2954	3111	3347	50	58	70
Cancer Surgery	14021	25238	25518	25658	80	82	83
Liver Transplant	69042	103563	125656	119443	82	76	73
Renal Transplant	19833	34113	32724	31733	72	65	60
Renal Dialysis	2750	4400	4483	4510	60	63	64

Cost of treatment comparison – India vs USA, UK and Canada.

The following table shows the comparative cost of various medical treatments and percentage of savings in India compare to cost of treatment in USA, UK and Canada.

Procedure	Average cost in India in US \$	Cost in USA in US \$	Cost in UK in US \$	Cost in Canada in US \$	Percentage of savings in India compared to cost of treatment in		
					USA	UK	Canada
Cardiology Treatment							
CABG	8339	54115	61530	88778	549	532	965
Bypass valve replacement-single	10911	68247	47930	75565	525	339	593
Pacemaker single chamber	6214	40752	37810	51923	556	508	736
Angioplasty	6911	57250	47925	51421	728	593	644
Angiogram	882	9000	6320	8517	920	616	867

Orthopaedic Treatment							
Birmingham hip replacement	15021	49830	40655	52465	232	171	249
Total hip replacement	13958	45000	38173	36576	222	173	162
Ankle joint replacement	7104	30000	18107	18859	321	155	165
Total knee replacement	7875	40000	21940	48668	408	179	518
Total shoulder replacement	8396	41500	30354	42585	394	262	407

Dental Treatment							
Crowns	292	2800	1202	973	859	312	233
Extractions	98	260	280	331	165	186	238
Implants	450	2800	4217	2920	522	837	549
Inlays& Outlays	90	650	630	700	622	600	678
Veneers Porcelain	478	1850	1055	973	287	121	121

Cosmetic Surgery							
Breast Augmentation	4205	8000	9250	9500	90.2	120	126
Breast lift & Reduction	4795	7500	10702	7300	56	123	52
Face lift	5114	9000	14235	13384	76	178	162
Liposuction	2840	4200	5272	7500	49	86	164
Tummy tuck	3795	8750	10143	10646	131	167	181

Ophthalmology							
Lasik/eye	684	2400	3174	2920	251	364	327
Glaucoma/eye	897	5500	5823	6692	513	549	646
Cataract removal	1019	4920	6020	5800	383	490	469
Squint correction	1103	4635	5985	6450	321	443	485

Neurological Treatment							
Spinal fusion	13019	89726	84508	75435	589	549	479
Cervical Discectomy	5981	42500	45500	37900	610	661	534
Spinal Decompression	5750	94000	85600	87000	1534	1388	1413
Artificial Disc Replacement	7567	68742	64000	67500	808	746	792

Other Treatment							
Gall Bladder Surgery	1969	10350	9024	6532	426	358	232
Cancer treatment	14021	99990	100360	109089	613	616	678
Liver Transplant	69042	340092	159763	285925	393	131	314
Renal Transplant	19833	250000	175000	225000	1160	782	1034
Renal Dialysis	2750	32600	34500	31000	1085	1155	1027

4. Conclusion:

The cost of various medical treatment in India is substantially low when compared to Singapore, Malaysia and Thailand as well as developed countries like USA, UK and Canada. The above research indicates that the cost of treatment in Singapore Malaysia and Thailand is 1.5 to 2 times more than the cost in India. The cost of various treatment in USA, UK and Canada are ten times more than the cost in India. Due to less treatment cost in India, the international patients are preferring for medical treatment and every year the inbound international medical tourist numbers are increasing, which contributes to the growth of GDP. So India has greater potential for developing medical tourism business and generate good employment opportunities in Health sector in future.

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QIP – An empirical evidence from Indian exchanges

Paper code: GCU-CMS-C11

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Abstract

Listed firms can raise capital by selling shares of stock or other equity convertible securities to eligible institutions under the Qualified Institutional Placement (QIP) procedure. The company avoids dilution of its management ownership and the need to finish the same time-consuming paperwork as it did for its IPO by using this well-known private placement strategy. The listed firm can raise money once more through a secondary IPO thanks to the addition of FPOs. Yet it takes time to go through the legal process and construct one again. QIPs were used as a bridge to obtain funds more rapidly than an FPO might have been able to because of the limited restrictions that they must go by. In contrast, QIBs are strictly controlled, a useful source of finance for these businesses, and they are carefully selected to be the buyers of these issues. The frequency, trend, volume, and value of QIP from Indian exchanges on a YOY basis for the reference period of 2010 to 2019 are examined in this article. Data was collected from the SEBI report. Similar has been utilised for analytical purposes while making use of the proper statistical methods.

Keywords: Qualified Institutional Placement (QIP), Qualified Institutional Buyers (QIB) IPO, FPO, Private Placement

1. Introduction

Listed firms can raise capital by selling shares of stock or other equity convertible securities to eligible institutions under the Qualified Institutional Placement (QIP) procedure. The company avoids dilution of its management ownership and the need to finish the same time-consuming paperwork as it did for its IPO by using this well-known private placement strategy. Due to the less constraints that QIPs must follow, they are used as a bridge to access cash more quickly than an FPO may have. Before the QIP, Indian regulators had started to be concerned that local companies were using American depository receipts (ADRs), foreign currency convertible bonds (FCCBs), and global depository receipts (GDR) to seek international finance more frequently than Indian-based capital sources.

The purpose of the QIP regulations was to encourage Indian businesses to raise capital domestically rather than through foreign sources. The SEBI published the guidelines for this unique type of Indian funding on May 8, 2006. Only accredited investors who are qualified institutional buyers (QIBs) as specified by the securities and exchange governing body in charge of it are allowed to purchase QIPs. Under QIPs securities are issued to the qualified institutional buyers which comprises of mutual fund companies, venture capitals, FII, public financial institutions which are registered with SEBI in the research papers the author has examined trends in the QIP as compared with the IPO, The study is designed to find the resources mobilised through QIP on a year-on-year basis through exchanges, to analyse the frequency, trend, volume & value of QIP from Indian exchanges on the YOY basis and to compare the issue made through QIP and IPO.

Research Gap

There are quite a few studies done on the market's response to qualified institutional placements (QIP) made by Indian businesses as well as their reasons for choosing the QIP route over the rights issue route when offering shares, Private placements performed for a certain period and also the sources of Mobilisation but there is no study done regarding frequency, trend, volume & value of QIP from Indian exchanges on the YOY basis for the reference period of 2015 to 2020 hence the data has been collected from the report of SEBI for analysing the same.

Objectives of the study

- To examine the resources mobilised through QIP on a year-on-year basis through exchanges
- To analyse the frequency, trend, volume & value of QIP from Indian exchanges on the YOY
- To compare the issue made through QIP and IPO

2. Review of literature

Zhang, Shi, & Zhang, 2022 have studied the quality of information disclosure in the prospectus before and after inquiry differs greatly, and inquiry can push issuers to better disclose risk information in the prospectus and significantly reduce ambiguity and redundancy. The depth of research reveals the calibre of disclosure of prospectus information. The poorer the prospectus information disclosure quality and the higher the SYN, the greater the degree of enquiry. The prospectus's content includes details about qualities that can lower the SYN. The deeper the characteristics information, the better the information transparency, the lower the SYN, and the more detailed the information disclosure.

Arshad Khan & Farooqi, 2021 have found that the under-priced initial public offerings (IPOs) produce higher profits. Assumedly, the issue price on the listing day is higher than the closing price ($P_0 > P_1$) on that day. In the secondary market, it aids in increasing demand and preserving price stability. As a result, under-pricing supports increased demand and keeps secondary market prices stable. At the beginning, investors left on the day of the listing in order to profit quickly. After shares are listed on the stock exchange, the genuine price can also be found. If new information enters the market from various sources aside from the syndicate, the market might set a new fair and truthful price. Eventually, the research advises investors to sell.

Rastogi & Chaturvedula, 2018 argued that in India, businesses can privately place stock through qualified institutional placement (QIP) and preferential allotment. The study examines private placements performed between 2010 and 2017 and discovers that knowledge asymmetry contributes to the preference for one way of placement over another. The factors of firm size, institutional ownership, and promoter shareholding play a significant role in whether one strategy is preferred to the other. The QIP issue size is probably larger than the preferred allotment issue size. Firms with more leverage are more inclined to select preferred allotment than QIP. According to the research, smaller enterprises with less institutional investments raise money from promoters or other non-institutional participants. The majority of the Indian institutional investors, who are ideally regarded as experts, subscribe to equity issues of larger size companies with less leverage.

Basha, 2015 focused on investigating the data from sources of private placement for money mobilisation. The study's goals have led to the adoption of an exploratory research design. The analysis is based on secondary data that spans the years 2000-01 to 2013-14 and includes annual data from the various sources of private placement mode of issue. This information was gathered from the Reserve Bank of India's official websites. For the current study, numerous more reports from publications including periodicals, journals, and books are also cited. Descriptive and inferential statistics are the statistical methods used for data analysis. It is concluded that funds mobilised from private placement of public sector and its financial institution has been consistently rising with a CAGR of 15% during the study period since it is more structured, time oriented, transparent and cheaper source.

Guha Deb, 2015 aimed to examine the market's response to qualified institutional placements (QIP) made by Indian businesses as well as their reasons for choosing the QIP route over the rights issue route when offering shares. The seven-year study period, beginning on January 1 and ending on

December 31, 2013, is the source of the data. The data regarding the rights issue and QIP announcement dates is obtained from the Bloomberg database. Daily stock price and market returns are gathered from the CMIE Prowess database. The stock price response to the announcement of rights issues and QIPs is measured using the basic market model. Our findings reveal that the market responds favourably to QIP announcements from companies with modest promoter holdings a quarter before the QIP announcements since Indian promoters are often dilution-averse.

Guha Deb, Banerjee, & Banerjee, 2012 argued that to make the business operations quicker and simpler for businesses to obtain equity directly, qualified institutional placement (QIP) was created in India in 2006. When a corporation pursues a QIP, it also has the option of issuing shares through a rights issue to current shareholders. Existing owners' ownership interests would not be diminished by a rights issue. This would be a smart way to raise funds and prevent ownership dilution given the preponderance of family-controlled enterprises in India. In this context, they attempted to investigate what influences a company's decision to pursue a QIP or a rights problem.

In India, SEBI permitted 2006 qualifying institutional placement. As a result, they have chosen a 6-year study period, starting on January 1, 2007, and ending on December 31, 2011. There was a total of 130 right issues and 171 qualifying institutional placements throughout this time. This study investigates the impact of qualified institutional placements in India on stock prices as well as the factors that influence these decisions. In terms of the factors that determine whether a company chooses a rights issue or a QIP, it is discovered that those companies with substantial institutional holdings are more likely to choose a QIP. This would suggest that institutional investors in India subscribe to QIPs in a herd-like manner and do not perform monitoring or certification functions.

Shah & Mehta, 2016 have analysed the performance of 113 IPOs in India During the period December 2010 to December 2014, The researchers have found out the returns of Initial days and the factors that influence under-pricing, it has been concluded that variables like issue size and market returns do not affect the rate of success, but oversubscription should be considered for Investment decision.

Gupta, , 2012 revealed that companies placing private equity in India have positive abnormal returns. Additionally, the promoters' shareholdings will be diluted as a result of this placement. More evidence that the placement had no impact on the firms' growth potential is seen in the form of a negative correlation between the firm's growth opportunities and abnormal returns.

Cronqvist, 2004 did a research on the Swedish market, companies with a high degree of information asymmetry are more likely to choose a private placement over a rights issue, particularly if the new investment opportunity is unknown. Furthermore, they discover that companies offering stocks via private placement had larger positive anomalous returns than companies issuing rights offers. Businesses that conducted private placements displayed enhanced operational performance, whereas businesses doing rights offers did not.

Alm, Elin , & Andreas, 2009 have led to the conclusion that executing an IPO and maintaining listing are not easy tasks. 58 businesses make up the sample. These businesses are generated from the 224 companies that went public overall during the period they chose. Only 25% of all the initial public offerings (IPOs) that were listed over this time span were still active, demonstrating the difficulty of maintaining an IPO's listing. The 75% of IPOs that are not now listed may be those businesses that were severely underpriced and so had limited lifetime performance. Out of the 75% of these businesses, some may have also succeeded extraordinarily well, leading to acquisition by or merger with another company.

Hertze & Smith, 1993 have examined that how asymmetric information affects the decision between private placements and rights issues. They contend that a company will choose private placements over a rights issue if there is a substantial degree of information asymmetry regarding the firm's worth because institutional investors who get private placements can easily and affordably determine the firm's true value. They demonstrate that the direct cost of a private placement is higher than that of other equity issue techniques.

Myers and Majluf (1984) have focused on the earliest work in the area of private placement of equity. They provide a model of asymmetric information-based corporate finance. In this case, the company chooses not to pursue positive NPV investment prospects in favour of issuing securities to the public at a discount price, taking into account the interests of the current owners who would

suffer as a result of such a move. However, if the company has a "private line" to current stockholders or if it can effortlessly share this information with a group of investors to whom the shares could be distributed, this underinvestment problem vanishes.

Hypothesis

Given the context and background of the study the null hypothesis has been proposed as:

Ho- "There is no significant difference between the frequency of QIP and the frequency of IPO".

3. Methodology

The present research paper is on analytical and descriptive research with the source of data collected from Hand book on Indian capital market published by SEBI, the study was done for the period of 2010 – 2019, information regarding Yearly data of QIP, IPO, QIP of both BSE and NSE was collected, Descriptive statistics, Paired t test was used as an analysis tool for comparing the data taken from National Stock exchange and Bombay stock exchange.

4. Data analysis and Interpretation

Table 5.1: Total resources mobilised through QIP

Period	No of Issues	YOY %	Amount (Crore)	YOY %
2010-11	59		25,850	
2011-12	16	-73	2,163	-92
2012-13	45	181	15,996	640
2013-14	17	-62	13,663	-15
2014-15	42	147	29,385	115
2015-16	24	-43	14,588	-50
2016-17	20	-17	8,464	-42
2017-18	53	165	67,238	694
2018-19	48	-9	64,669	-4
AVERAGE	36	36	26,891	156
Sd	15.77621	101.631477	22257.23	300.654654
MIN	16	-73	2,163	-92
MAX	59	181	67,238	694
CV	44%	281%	83%	193%

Source : National Stock Exchange

The above table shows the total resources mobilised through QIP, the maximum number of issues of 59 was done during the period 2010- 11 and the amount was 25,850 crores for the same with the year-on-year percentage of 181, and the minimum number of issue of 16 was done during the period of 2011-12 and the amount was 2,163 crore for the same with the year on year percentage of -73

Table 5.2: Resources mobilised through NSE and BSE

Period	For both NSE and BSE			
	No of Issues	YOY %	Amount (Crore)	YOY %
2010-11	46		22,959	
2011-12	14	-70	2,114	-91
2012-13	43	207	14,885	604
2013-14	16	-63	13,503	-9
2014-15	28	75	21,232	57
2015-16	17	-39	13,093	-38
2016-17	20	18	8,464	-35
2017-18	53	165	67,238	694
2018-19	48	-9	64,669	-4
AVERAGE	32	35	25,351	147
Sd	14.8249	97.7383068	22480.53	293.228572
MIN	14	-70	2,114	-91
MAX	53	207	67,238	694
CV	47%	276%	89%	199%

Source: NSE and BSE

The above table shows the resources mobilised through NSE and BSE the maximum number of issue of 53 was done during the period 2017- 18 and the amount was 67,238 crore for the same with the year on year percentage of 165, and the minimum number of issue of 14 was done during the period of 2011-12 and the amount was 14,885 crore for the same with the year on year percentage of -91.

Table 5.3: Comparison between QIP and IPO

QIP		IPO		
Period	No of Issues	Amount (Crore)	No.	Amount
2010-11	59	25,850	53	35,559
2011-12	16	2,163	54	41,515
2012-13	45	15,996	33	6,528
2013-14	17	13,663	38	1,236
2014-15	42	29,385	46	3,311
2015-16	24	14,588	74	14,815
2016-17	20	8,464	106	29,104
2017-18	53	67,238	201	83,684
2018-19	48	64,669	243	78,130
AVERAGE	36	26,891	94	32,654
Sd	15.78	22257.23	71.98	29098.66
MIN	16	2,163	33	1,236
MAX	59	67,238	243	83,684
CV	44%	83%	76%	89%

Source : National Stock Exchange

The above table shows the comparison between QIP and IPO, the maximum number of QIP issue of 59 was done during the period 2010- 11 and the amount was 25,850 crore and the minimum number of issue of 16 was done during the period of 2011-12 and the amount was 2,163 crore. the maximum number of IPO issue of 243 was done during the period 2018- 19 and the amount was 78,130 crore and the minimum number of issue of 33 was done during the period of 2012-13 and the amount was 6,528 crore.

Table 5.4: T-test: Paired two sample for means

No of Issues	QIP	IPO
Mean	36	94.22
Variance	280	5829.44
Observations	9	9
Pearson Correlation	0.36	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
Df	8	
t Stat	-2.42	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.020662	
t Critical one-tail	1.859548	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.041324	
t Critical two-tail	2.306004	

Source: Data analysis using SPSS

Table 5.4 shows that the mean values of QIP is lower than IPO due to that maximum number of IPO occurred in the year 2016- 2019, the results of paired t test accepts the null which signifies that there is no significance difference between the frequency of QIP and the frequency of IPO hypothesis either of one tailed or two tailed calculated value is lower than the critical value whereas Pearson's co relation is showing positive co relation of 0.36.

Table 5.5: T-test: Paired two sample for means

	Amount (Crore)	Amount
Mean	26890.63	32653.5556
Variance	5.57E+08	952573311
Observations	9	9
Pearson Correlation	0.766306	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
Df	8	
t Stat	-0.871881	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.204338	
t Critical one-tail	1.859548	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.408677	
t Critical two-tail	2.306004	

Source: Data analysis using SPSS

The above table is formulated for showing the result of paired t test between QIP and IPO amount, the mean values of QIP is lower than IPO due to that maximum number of IPO occurred in the year 2016- 2019, the results of paired t test accepts the null hypothesis either of one tailed or two tailed calculated value is lower than the critical value hence it signifies that there is no significance difference between the frequency of QIP and IPO whereas pearsons co relation is showing positive co relation of 0.76.

5. Findings

- It is found that the maximum number of issue of 59 was done during the period 2010- 11 and the amount was 25,850 crore for the same with the year on year percentage of 181,
- The minimum number of issue of 16 was done during the period of 2011-12 and the amount was 2,163 crore for the same with the year on year percentage of -73
- It can be noted that the maximum number of issue of 53 was done during the period 2017- 18 and the amount was 67,238 crore for the same with the year on year percentage of 165
- the minimum number of issues of 14 was done during the period of 2011-12 and the amount was 14,885 crores for the same with the year on year percentage of -91.
- The maximum number of QIP issue of 59 was done during the period 2010- 11 and the amount was 25,850 crores
- The minimum number of issues of 16 was done during the period of 2011-12 and the amount was 2,163 crores.
- The maximum number of IPO issue of 243 was done during the period 2018- 19 and the amount was 78,130 crores

- The minimum number of issue of 33 was done during the period of 2012-13 and the amount was 6,528 crore.
- There is no significance difference between the frequency of QIP and IPO

6. Conclusion

The study was conducted in an attempt to compare funds sourced through QIP and IPOs also understand the frequency, trend, volume & value on a year-on-year basis in QIP and IPO preferences, and it was discovered that the maximum number of QIP issues occurred in 2010–2011 and the minimum number occurred in 2011–2012, whereas the maximum number of IPO issues occurred in 2018–19 and the minimum occurred in 2012–2013. It should be noted that the frequency of QIP and IPO do not differ significantly from one another. It can be concluded that IPOs lags behind QIPs and QIP are a better option to raise funds. The period of the study is only restricted to 9 years to maintain relevance to current practises also the study compares the frequencies of QIP and IPO only and not other sources of funds.

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E Marketing Techniques for Hospitality Business in the Digital Era

Paper code: GCU-CMS-T22

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Abstract

Adopting the proper hospitality business marketing plan can be essential for the long-term success of a company while aiding in customer attraction, revenue optimization, and reputation and trust-building. The hospitality industry must stay on top of the most recent trends in marketing to achieve this, but there are difficulties in doing so, particularly in light of the COVID 19 pandemic and the resulting changes in the attitudes of hospitality consumers. The COVID 19 pandemic had an impact on traditional marketing as already businesses were incurring loss since lockdown and forced the industry to operate with Standard operating procedures (SOP) when shifted the lockdown. Traditional Marketing strategies failed to gain confidence among the health-conscious guests on hygiene, cleanliness and health care measures that were assured to be taken in the premises during their stay. This forced the hospitality industry to diversify the services provided by adopting E marketing technologies where they can provide insights to the guests while ensuring the hygiene and safety with high quality customer service. Thus, the researchers have undertaken the study to throw light on the recent trends in E Marketing and its impacts to provide actionable insights on the development and sustainability of the hospitality sector. This research study is a pioneer in critically analysing these effects and how hoteliers may respond to these challenges to recover from the any future crisis in the industry.

Key Words: COVID -19, Hospitality Marketing, Sustainability

1. Introduction

The fundamentals of hospitality marketing concentrates on the requirements and satisfaction of the customers. Hospitality marketing examines how various segments of the hospitality business (such as lodging, food and beverage, tourism and travel) develop marketing plans to advertise their goods or services and boost sales. Marketing becomes crucial to ensure the success of the hospitality business because it focuses primarily on developing and positive customer experiences and maintaining the customer relationships. Travel and hotel businesses need to effectively market their services on various digital platforms in order to reach their target audience (Kumar, 2021).

A crisis is a state of tension that occurs at an unexpected time and significantly affects business continuity. The tourism and hospitality sector are susceptible to being impacted by its multipurpose structure—natural disasters, terrorist incidents, epidemics, political tensions, economic fluctuations, etc. By witnessing such kind of problems, we may see accommodation business to lose tourists at any time. Developing new products, shifting to alternative tourism markets, and reducing costs may be options for businesses. However, because every crisis is different, managers have to determine the most appropriate strategy for the problem. Effective crisis management are made possible by strategic control. With the application of smart strategic management, crises can be

turned into opportunities.

The novel Coronavirus (COVID 19), which began appearing in Wuhan, China, in December 2019, spread around the world in 2020 and caused a severe decline in the flow of international tourists. Due to the Covid-19 outbreak, it has become almost imperative for tourism businesses to revisit their strategies. This global epidemic crisis can lead to downsizing or even bankruptcy of companies which was only helped with possible effective strategic management. To respond to any crises, it is essential to understand the context in which they occur as every situation is different, the strategies to be implemented may also be different. With the COVID 19 outbreak, many hospitality businesses have reconsidered their marketing strategies. Hotel management has mostly followed a market share strategy and cost reduction, and customer acquisition. Crises generally interfere with the current flow of everyday life and daily routine and can have very negative consequences.

Due to the tourism and hospitality sector's multi-purpose structure, the level of exposure to crises were relatively high. Considering the implications of the situation in terms of tourism, the industry's image and business institutions' adverse effects were felt for a long time. The pandemic has produced severe global socioeconomic disturbance, including one of the biggest global recessions in history. It's critical to stay current with trends in hospitality marketing, but it's also crucial to comprehend the background of those trends.

In light of the given context, the study has provided a breakdown of both general hospitality industry trends and E Marketing trends that have arisen in reaction to the pandemic. This study also argues for raising awareness to view this pandemic as a wake-up call to prepare for the after effects by advancing with other aspects highlighted in the current study such as changing travel and eating habits, being thrifty with money, needing to be adaptable, market research, playing leadership roles, and population issues would be critical in preparing industry and stakeholders.

Statement of problem

The COVID 19 outbreak affected entire world in 2020, causing travel restrictions, curfews and crisis for the accommodation business. Furthermore, the industry heads reflected on the immediate challenge of managing fixed costs when the enterprises are continuing to lose business. Lodging and food service sectors are known to have higher fixed costs and are sensitive to the shocks and instabilities in the market. Traditional marketing strategies were no more preferred due to high costs. The above problems faced during the pandemic has enthused the researcher to take up the research and study the E marketing trends followed to overcome the same by hospitality business all over the world which may help many smaller business units in such future circumstances.

Objective of the study

Hotels were implementing new techniques to set themselves up for accelerated recovery, but it was not 'business as normal'. Hospitality Business carved their marketing plans around the motif, right from the lockout to the Unlock-phase, to express new steps and initiatives. Hotels ensured that they hit the right chord with the crowd, from venturing into the food distribution area to providing work and stay packages and revealing concessional deals to organizing simulated activities, among others. Thus, there was lot of scope for the study on various E Marketing trends that picked up in the industry. With this consideration, the research was carried out to study the different hospitality management trends to attract customers, to identify the E Marketing practices followed, and its impact on the performance of the firms in hospitality industry.

2. Literature review

The literature review has been presented into two sections. The first section discusses the general management strategies that the industry followed during managerial, financial and other types of crises. Whereas the second section discussed the trends, usage and benefits of E Marketing when the whole world was shut down and where the industry cannot find any alternative business strategies.

Pfarr & Hosie (2008) defines the tourism crisis as when the tourism sector is severely damaged due to internal reasons such as wrong policies, administrative errors, or external causes such as economic changes, terrorist incidents, natural disasters general, crises are classified as financial

crises, political crises, terrorism, crises related to natural disasters, ecological problems, biological emergencies, social situations, and technological crises; Many factors are influential in crisis formation and can have many positive/negative consequences (Offe, 1976). Judging from the results of his research, it can be seen that in the aftermath of the 2008 global crisis, hoteliers around the world are trying to develop new products that can attract consumers' attention in response to the declining demand for tourism. He also revealed that they focused on avoiding the effects of the crisis by reducing existing products' prices and selling credit (Campo et al., 2014).

Karagiorgos et al. (2011) revealed that the hotel business in Athens, where the European and Middle Eastern markets are dominant, began to look for alternative markets to compensate for the cancellation of reservations and the low occupancy rates they encountered as a result of the crisis. Businesses generally make marketing initiatives for the Middle East and Baltic countries and develop alternative markets such as sports tourism. On the other hand, the domestic market's efforts have stepped up, and some hotels have limited price discounts for individual bookings. In times of crisis, accommodation businesses spend their limited budgets on alternative markets for promotional and advertising activities. They provide concert and entertainment facilities to increase business appeal by using messages that emphasize safety in their promotional activities. In short, they tried to implement all strategies except growth and competition strategies.

Gurtner (2016), who presented similar results, stated that after the terrorist attacks in Bali, businesses discounted shifted to a niche market and promoted more to the domestic market. He also found that technology and social media platforms were used more in the promotion. Ghaderi et al. (2012) revealed that the most common tourism business strategy in Penang, one of Malaysia's essential destinations affected by various regional and global crises, is to shift attention to regional and middle entry markets—and trying to develop domestic tourism. They stated that although the primary business market was the UK, Australia, China, Indonesia, and Singapore, after the crisis, they directed their target markets to Middle Eastern countries, Japan and Taiwan, and they carried out advertising campaigns for specific groups. Such as young managers, retirees, families, and students.

A study conducted on four and 5-star hotels in Spain, del Mar Alonso-Almeida (2013) determined that businesses offer different products to increase their share in the tourism market in crisis times. During the crisis period, it was revealed that most business actors, by lowering product prices, implemented strategies to maintain market position by not avoiding competition with competitors and switched to promotions to benefit from the crisis. Situation. The idea of concentrating on one market was frowned upon. Businesses that claim they can take a break from advertising and promotional activities have attached importance to different sales and distribution techniques and the internet due to low direct marketing costs. To not be affected by the crisis experienced between 2001-2008, the 5-star hotel business in Belgium turned to alternative market opportunities. It implemented a market share strategy with a focus on domestic travel. This hotel and holiday village business continuously assesses the environmental conditions that will affect the tourism market and hotel management to prevent crises. Most companies diversify their target market, focusing on online marketing strategies and turning to group sales. It was said that the new market was chosen as an alternative market, where the business focus on that market decreased because tourists in Europe, America, the Far East, Australia, Russia, Canada, and Balkan countries were affected by terrorism incidents, generally countries in the Middle East. Besides, it has been determined that Ukraine, India, China, Central Asia, South Africa, and South America have been designated as new target markets.

To maintain a competitive advantage and enhance business performance, several organizations implement AI-powered technologies, such as point of sale (POS), Facebook Ads, and LINE Ads (Dash et al., 2019; Limna et al., 2021; Tong-On et al., 2021). Hence, AI and automation science offer numerous opportunities for tourism and hospitality businesses to improve their day-to-day operations and ensure that a high-quality service is delivered to their customers (Drexler & Lapré, 2019; Kumar et al., 2021) the hospitality and tourism industry are leveraging cutting-edge technologies, such as artificial intelligence and robotics (AIR), to enhance customer service and experience. These technological advancements have been transformed into smart tools for providing customer service, and they are being used to improve the customer experience (Goel et al., 2022). In terms of service quality, the use of AI, robots, and service automation is becoming increasingly important for gaining a competitive advantage, but providing more personalized guest experiences remains contentious (Naumov, 2019). Modern technological applications, such as AI

and robotic technologies, are widely used in the hospitality industries, including hotel businesses, tourism businesses, food and beverage businesses, as well as meeting and event businesses (Drexler & Lapré, 2019; Yang et al., 2020).

AI and robotic technologies provide several opportunities for the hospitality industry to enhance their daily operations and their long-term strategies, as well as ensure that their customers receive consistent quality products and services. (Yang et al., 2020). AI will satisfy business customers by assisting them in identifying and optimizing future sales opportunities (Lu et al., 2020; Kumar et al., 2021; Thong-On et al., 2021). Citak et al. (2021) discussed how the hotel industry can be motivated by potential customers to apply selected AI solutions. The most significant deployments are for in-person customer service, chatbots, and messaging tools, machine learning-powered business intelligence tools, and virtual and augmented reality. As a result, hotel businesses in the hospitality industry can leverage their on-site services, and processes, and improve customer experiences with the help of AI. Also, keeping in touch with customers and meeting their needs is essential for maintaining overall quality.

3. Methodology of the study

The researchers have attempted to study the E marketing trends emerged to recover and fill the gap created during the pandemic COVID-19. The study has employed a qualitative technique, of literature review and logic analysis, in order to investigate and assess the most recent studies in the field. In this regard, the researchers the secondary data has been collected through journals, news publications, and have listed the marketing practices followed all over the world. Finally the article has been presented following the TAILMRDCE model (Kumar, 2023).

4. Findings

The idea of "e-marketing" has expanded as a result of the hospitality industry's increased acceptance of ICT tools. In literature, marketing that takes place over the shaky Internet has been referred to by a variety of titles, including Internet marketing, online marketing, e-Marketing, web marketing, or digital marketing. In actuality, the word "e-marketing" encompasses all ICT applications in all hospitality-related fields. An aspect and type of information technology is e-marketing. Traditional marketing techniques only allowed for one-way communication, but e-marketing has united businesses and consumers on a single stage. E-marketing has completely replaced conventional marketing, which relies on one-on-one interaction and social norms. Technology-based alliances created for e-marketing allow for interactivity.

The following are a few hospitality trends that COVID 19 can be linked to, or that are affected by related shifts in consumer behaviour. Hotels, restaurants, bars, cafes, and various other companies should be aware of these trends.

a) Minimize physical touch with Artificial intelligence and robotics

Hotel owners have begun to give closer attention to the potential benefits and applications of artificial intelligence (AI) in hotel operations, including robotics. The effects of AI and robotics on people and organisational levels in the hotel industry have become the focus of an increasing quantity of research. Furthermore, the use of hotel AI and robotics, particularly in high contact scenarios, helped to safeguard guests and frontline support staff given the position of social distance as an effective technique of prevention against COVID-19. Thus, as a post-COVID-19 trend in hotel administration and marketing, many star category hotels focused on AI and robotics.

b) Health and health care

Following the COVID-19 epidemic, a lot of people began to reconsider their actions and focus on their physical and mental well-being. Given this growing consumer demand, helping guests live healthier lifestyles has become a post-pandemic theme for hotels. For instance, meditation programmes, digital detox programmes, exercise programmes, healthier diet programmes, and sleep hygiene programmes are likely to become more popular in the marketing blend of hotels. In these circumstances, it seems desirable to go into more detail about how hotels should design customised items to improve visitor wellbeing and optimise the guest experience.

c) Promote Safety in Marketing and Guest Communication

In the aftermath of COVID, one of the most important trends in hospitality to be aware of was the significance of emphasising safety procedures, hygiene policies, and other decisions intended to protect customers. This included more thorough cleaning, moving tables and chairs for social distance, enforcing the use of masks in specific areas of the facility or by staff members, and increasing the use of contactless payments and mobile applications. Additionally, it's crucial to make sure that customers are informed explicitly of these changes prior to their arrival which is done through various E Marketing activities.

d) Use Virtual Reality Hospitality Technology

One of the most significant recent developments in hotel technology and marketing has been virtual reality, and the coronavirus pandemic has only increased its applications. The best way to experience a place from a distance is with virtual reality tours, which recreate the setting in a way that enables some level of discovery and immersion. This provided leisure customers with the chance to visit a hotel interior or experience a famous landmark or tourist site. For event customers, it means having the option to view wedding or event venues virtually without having to journey there in person. This was particularly helpful when it came to travel restrictions. The majority of current virtual reality tours can be watched through a regular web browser or a VR headset.

e) Improve Customer Experience & Satisfaction with Chatbots

Customer experience has become crucial in winning customers' loyalty in the cutthroat world of the hospitality business. In order to satisfy the demands of the hospitality industry, comprehensive customer experience marketing plans have become essential. Hotels collected analytics from online customer reviews on review websites in order to produce healthy returns and a steady stream of repeat customers. This gave us a wealth of knowledge about client preferences, ways hotels can improve, and what influences future conversions.

In a variety of ways, chatbots were also used to enhance the customer experience and are a significant component of many contemporary marketing strategies for the hospitality industry. Regardless of staff availability, these bots allowed for quick customer service responses and supported multiple languages. This technology was applied during the booking phase to provide assistance and promote ticket completion. Additionally, bots had the ability to cross-sell and up-sell, which might have helped the company increase income.

f) Voice Search

The fact that the next generation of Web users prefers voice activation for communication has created a huge chance for the hospitality sector. The speech search feature on tablets, smartphones, and other similar devices is a form of voice control and recognition technology. In reality, this trend may soon make it unnecessary for Internet users to type their search terms into the search bar or press buttons. Hotel visitors spoke to their smartphone to make a reservation for a hotel accommodation. Even the features of the room, like the lighting, music, and heating, could be managed by voice search.

g) Artificial Intelligence (AI)

Artificial intelligence has the power to simplify procedures and offer insightful data. The majority of people who reserve hotel rooms online typically do so through aggregator websites; however, some people may visit a hotel's homepage but decide not to make a reservation. Most of the time, customers would rather talk with hotel staff than input their preferred dates and check-in information, which can be very time-consuming. Hotels were able to offer customised services and create a reliable system by utilising artificial intelligence robots on their websites. The findings are supported by the study of Davenport et al. (2020) who recommended that AI is expected to significantly impact marketing strategies in the future, including business models, sales processes, customer service options, and customer behavior. Three broad areas to investigate the full scope of artificial intelligence's impact are (1) how marketing strategies will change, (2) how customers' behaviours will change, and (3) issues related to data privacy, bias, and ethics.

h) Augmented Reality

A fascinating approach to hotel marketing is augmented reality. This instrument alters how a person perceives their physical environment by using computer technology. This technology enabled to

provide various services like 360degree view of the rooms, navigating through the hotel and exploring pool and restaurants, entertaining the guests and children with customised games using AR, providing interactive menu cards at restaurant, and providing insights on history of the hotel property. The use of augmented reality in the hotel industry has changed how customers view their surroundings. There are countless ways to use augmented environments to entertain visitors, such as letting them see virtual versions of their favourite celebs while staying at the hotel. Hotels could also deliver virtual keys to visitors via their smartphones by using this tool.

I) Video Marketing

Hotels and the travel industry use video marketing to interact with their target market through Facebook Live, Instagram, or YouTube recordings. Hotels offered guests easily digestible videos about the property in order to engage them immediately. Gaining brand exposure and grabbing the attention of your audience were done through written content. In order to attract customers, videos and pictures must be of extremely high quality. For instance, hotels used video marketing by filming their guests as they unwind while using the hotel's amenities. Marketers had a virtually limitless number of options at their disposal, including live streams of hotel activities, promotional films showcasing hotel amenities, and customer interviews and customer reviews.

5. Suggestions

It is highly evident from the above trends that E marketing practices are taking an important role in operating hospitality business. A rise in the number of hotels that have voice command technology incorporated and have started using smart speech tools as personal assistants may be seen which are seen as threat to human job market. These services are not only enabled on site but also provided in mobile phones which makes the stay easy and comfortable.

Also due to the uniqueness of services, using the best tools, machinery, and equipment available today is insufficient to create a lasting relationship between service provider and customer without engaging in any non-physical transactions. Determining the framework that is appropriate and the right fit in the new conditions as well as aligned with the guidelines and regulations issued by the federal government now and then for the hospitality sector has become essential which definitely needs human intervention.

6. Conclusion

Effective strategies were needed to boost traveller confidence and aid businesses in quickly recovering from the public health disaster. The resilience and sustainability of the hotel business can be strengthened by addressing various consumption requirements and taking action to turn adversity into opportunity. These activities were associated with anticipated consumer demand patterns for things like environmental protection, contactless facilities, and traveler's health. The response of hotels in this crisis and the fluctuating market demand showed a number of areas where professional knowledge needs to be improved. Academic research can help advance hotel marketing and management expectations, industry recovery initiatives, and positive changes in industry practises for future sustainability which reflects the changing traveller. Also, it is clear from the study that the hospitality industry is looking into and experimenting with a variety of marketing strategies to draw tourists that are primarily based on the benefits to health and hygiene and are aggressively marketing the same to draw and keep customers in the cutthroat economy.

Limitations and Future Scope of the study

E marketing is implemented at different levels and potential risks associated are varied. The present study has not accounted on the percentage, category, location, types of the hotel which employed the above-mentioned trends and the cost incurred behind the same. Comparative and customer satisfaction studies can also be performed between human employed and other AI services which provides real insight on the new trends emerging in the industry.

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A Study on the Impact of lifestyle on Consumer Purchase Behaviour of Organic Products

Paper code: GCU-CMS-M16

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Abstract

Organic food products are considered to be good for overall health and hence have become synonymous with sustainable living. It is believed that organic food products contribute to a healthy lifestyle. Hence, we investigate whether the lifestyle of individuals and organic food purchase is connected. The primary data is gathered via a standardised questionnaire. A convenience sampling method was used to choose the respondents as a non-probability sample. The data collected was analyzed using statistical tools like descriptive statistics, correlation, and chi-square analysis. The results show that most of the respondents have poor diet habits and are also prone to health issues. The lifestyle is also found to be stressful and many have a poor fitness level. It was concluded that consumers consider organic products as toxin free and good for health. It could be said that a person's lifestyle has a lot to do with whether or not they buy organic products, since both healthy people and people who want to live healthier tend to buy organic foods. Also, using only organic products won't be enough to live a healthy life. Consumers need to know that combining organic products with a healthy diet and healthy lifestyle will improve their quality of life, while just eating organic products without making any changes to their lifestyle won't make much of a difference.

Keywords: Organic food products, lifestyle, consumer purchase behaviour, health issues, toxin-free, sustainable food habits

1. Introduction:

Organic foods are grown without using chemical pesticides. For foods labelled "organic" that come from animals (like eggs, meat, milk, and milk products), the feed can't contain antibiotics or growth hormones. People think that organic foods are safe for the environment because they are not made with chemical pesticides or fertilizers. They are also not made from organisms that have been changed genetically. Also, organic foods aren't made with irradiation, industrial solvents, or artificial food additives. So, these foods are safe for the environment because they are made using methods that are good for the environment (Singh & Verma, 2017). "We are what we eat" is a common saying. As important as it is to have a healthy diet with the right amount of protein, carbs, fat, fibre, vitamins, and minerals for a healthy lifestyle, it is also important to pay attention to how it affects the environment. In India, one of the biggest problems is that food is often not as nutritious as it should be. This can cause problems like obesity, heart disease, high blood pressure, high cholesterol, depression, and eating disorders. It is essential to comprehend what you consume, since making good food selections promotes a healthy mind, body, and spirit. More people are eating organic or naturally grown food now that they know about it. Choosing to eat organic food is good for both the environment and your health. Organic items don't have any harmful ingredients and are healthier and taste better than regular food. They are also good for the environment and will

last for a long time (Lifestyle desk, 2019). The pandemic has helped organic living in a way that has never been seen before. And it looks like this will continue. Before a year ago, most people thought that organic living was something that only rich people did. No, not anymore. Here's something interesting: Within a few months of the pandemic, the number of searches on a top search engine for "How to live a sustainable lifestyle" had gone up by more than 4,550% (TOI, 2021). What's the point if the food we eat just weakens our immune system and makes us more likely to get sick? Synthetic fertilizers and pesticides used to grow food hurt your body's immune system, making you more likely to get sick or get infection. A number of studies has shown that people who regularly ate organic food had much stronger immune systems than those who ate non-organic food. The study also found that eating organic food can lower the risk of getting cancer, especially compared to people who don't eat much organic food. This is important if you want to live a healthy life for a long time so that your body can build up a strong Défense against diseases (Tomar, 2022).

It cannot be denied that lifestyle and food consumption is related. The food consumed becomes the foundation of the body and provides the necessary nutrients for sustaining life. The word organic has become synonymous with sustainability and hence attracts the attention of individuals seeking to achieve a healthy lifestyle. Conversely, the lifestyle of individuals also affects the consumer intention to use organic products. For example, a highly stressed individual may experience health issues such as sleep apnea, hypertension, or diabetes. Most people attempt to reverse such basic health issues through the consumption of healthy food. This is where the organic food industry enters. In this paper, we explore the association between the lifestyle habits of the respondents and their impact on organic product purchase behaviour. The study gains significance in health-oriented and market-oriented theme as organic food manufacturers need to understand the health needs of their consumers to attract more customers towards buying organic food products.

2. Literature review:

Andersen et al.(2022) investigate the relationship between organic food consumption, lifestyle, socio-demographics, and dietary patterns. Between 1999 and 2002, cohort members filled out thorough questionnaires regarding their use of organic foods, diets, and lifestyles. To calculate the relationship between the consumption of organic food and lifestyle, socio demographics, and dietary habits, polytomous logistic regression models were utilised. The research comprised a total of 43 209 men and women between the ages of 54 and 73. Based on a historical cohort of Danish individuals, eating organic food was linked to better socio demographics, dietary habits, and a generally healthier lifestyle. Future research connecting the intake of organic foods with health outcomes must take these results into account when formulating their adjustment method. Gundala & Singh (2021) tries to pinpoint the variables influencing American consumers' purchasing decisions about organic goods. 770 Midwest-based customers participated in the survey, providing data. The gathered main data are analysed using ANOVA, multiple linear regression, factor analysis, independent t-tests, and hierarchical multiple regression analysis. This study supports the notion that attitudes toward purchasing organic foods are influenced by customers' perceptions of price, perceived or subjective standards, health awareness, and consumer knowledge. Another element that impacted customers' buying intentions was availability. Demographic characteristics like income, age, and education affect what people purchase. The research assists organic food marketers in creating winning strategies for the quickly expanding US organic food sector.

Jose & Koshy (2018) argues that it is critical to understand how young customers feel about organic food. This study's drive came from the likelihood that attitudes and behaviours formed while people are young would persist. 112 respondents (young college students) between the ages of 20 and 24 took part in the survey using the purposive sample method. The idea of fear and food safety concerns have often been regarded as one construct in the literature on the purchase of organic food items, despite findings suggesting otherwise. Additionally, because of a variety of environmental effects, having a happy mindset does not always translate into having positive behaviour. According to the results of the current research, people's attitudes toward organic food items were positively influenced by both fear and concerns about food safety to adopt a healthy lifestyle. The interaction impact of social pressure, however, had a larger likelihood of improving a person's healthy lifestyle. Mie et al. (2017) summarise the available research on the effect of organic food on human health. Because organic food consumers often lead better lives overall, the research is not definitive that eating organic food reduces the risk of allergy illness, overweight, or obesity. Animal investigations, however, imply that similarly made feed from organic or conventional production

affects growth and development in various ways. Pesticide usage is regulated in organic farming, whereas the majority of human pesticide exposure comes from residues in conventional fruits and vegetables. Even at current exposure levels, several pesticides have been shown in epidemiological studies to have negative impacts on children's cognitive development, although these findings have not yet been included in official risk evaluations of specific pesticides. Overall, this analysis highlights several known and probable advantages for human health related to the production of organic food. The use of such production techniques is also anticipated to be advantageous for conventional agriculture, for example, in integrated pest control. Von Essen & Englander (2013) looked at the phenomena of young adults' lived experiences with making healthy lifestyle decisions based on organic diets. Swedish researchers gathered the interviews, which were then examined using a descriptive phenomenological psychological study methodology. The findings revealed the phenomenon's general psychological structure, which is made up of four components: the lived body as the place to begin exploring one's life; a descriptive via emotional-relational food memories; a deliberate life strategy for well-being and vitality; and a set of values specific to the individual concerning moral principles. The findings provide a tenable understanding of the complex connection between psychological significance and the natural environment. It could be observed from past studies that health conditions and the quest towards achieving a healthy life influence the consumer purchase of organic products. In this undertaken study, the researcher attempts to assess the lifestyle of the respondents and relate it to their perceptions towards the purchase of organic products.

3. Methodology:

The study follows a deductive style and employs a structured questionnaire to survey the respondents. A sample of 112 respondents was selected based on non-probability sampling using a convenience sampling technique. The primary data collected was analysed using statistical tools such as simple percentage, descriptive, correlation, and chi-square analysis. The results were correlated and conclusions were presented.

4. Results & discussion

4.1. Analysis of primary data

The analysis of primary data and its subsequent interpretations are presented in Table 1 to 4. The respondents' demographic information is shown in Table 1. As could be seen, men provided the majority of responses. They could recognize marketing content because most of them were listed as graduates. Their purchasing power was demonstrated by the fact that most of them were paid employees and businesses. The majority of respondents' desire to purchase more goods is reflected in their marital status. The majority of families also had large families. The majority of the homes fall into the middle-class category. This demonstrates their limited financial resources when making purchasing decisions.

Table 1: Demographic Profile

Demographic Profile	Variables	No. of Respondents	Percent	Total Respondents
Gender	Male	59	52.7	112
	Female	53	47.3	
Education	School Level	31	27.7	112
	UG	39	34.8	
	PG	25	22.3	
	Ph.D.	10	8.9	
	Others	7	6.2	
Occupation	Student	19	17.0	112
	Business	33	29.5	
	Salaried	31	27.7	
	Unemployed	29	25.9	
Marital Status	Married	63	56.2	112
	Single	49	43.8	
Family Size	Nuclear Family	41	36.6	112
	Joint Family	71	63.4	
Household monthly income	<Rs.25000	41	36.6	112
	Rs.25000 to Rs.50000	48	42.9	
	>Rs.50000	23	20.5	

The life style assessment of the respondents is presented in Table 2. The majority of respondents slept for six to eight hours, which is healthy. The majority of respondents do not routinely adhere to a predetermined eating schedule. Organic food purchases are enticed by the fact that nearly half of those polled believe they are extremely unfit. Half of those polled believe they are overweight. The majority of respondents deny having a smoking or drinking habit.

Table 2: Lifestyle Assessment

Lifestyle Assessment	Variables	No. of Respondents	Percent	Total Respondents
Everyday Sleep Schedule	< 6 hours	26	23.2	112
	6 to 8 hours	46	41.1	
	I oversleep	23	20.5	
	No Idea	17	15.2	
Fixed timing for breakfast, lunch, and dinner	Yes	19	17.0	112
	Definitely No	37	33.0	
	Sometimes	25	22.3	
	Erratic eating	31	27.7	
Fitness Level	Athletic fit	12	10.7	112
	Muscularly fit	19	17.0	
	Fit for everyday chores	29	25.9	
	Extremely Unfit	52	46.4	
Weight Levels	Overweight	56	50.0	112
	Normal	29	25.9	
	Lean	27	24.1	
Smoke	Yes	19	17.0	112
	No	52	46.4	
	Sometimes	23	20.5	
	Very rarely	18	16.1	
Consume Alcohol	Yes	39	34.8	112
	No	27	24.1	
	Sometimes	31	27.7	
	Very Rarely	15	13.4	

The stress, health and diet levels of the respondents is presented in Table 3. It is evident that the majority of respondents experience moderate to severe stress, necessitating other means of coping with its effects, such as eating organic foods. Additionally, the majority of them are anaemic, necessitating a balanced diet. However, none of the diets are followed by half of respondents. This emphasizes the importance of eating organically to mitigate the negative effects of poor lifestyle choices.

Table 3: Stress, health, and diet

Lifestyle Assessment	Variables	No. of Respondents	Percent	Total Respondents
Everyday stress levels	Extremely stressed	41	36.6	112
	Moderately stressed	29	25.9	
	Balanced	24	21.4	
	Very Cool	18	16.1	
Health Issues	Hypertension	23	20.5	112
	Diabetes	31	27.7	
	Anemia	12	10.7	
	Sleep apnea	27	24.1	
	None of the above	19	17.0	
Diet Programs	Yes	12	10.7	112
	No	56	50.0	
	Sometimes	31	27.7	
	Very rarely	13	11.6	

The Impact on Consumer Purchase of Organic Products is presented in Table 4. It could be deduced that the majority of respondents thought organic foods were full of nutrients and free of toxins. Customers believe that this may assist them in lessening the negative effects of a stressful lifestyle. As a result, consumers recognize that organic products are also beneficial to overall health. Contrarily, the majority do not consider organic foods to be a weight loss strategy. In addition, there is a great deal of uncertainty regarding whether individuals with health issues can consume organic foods without expert advice.

Table 4: Impact on Consumer Purchase of Organic Products

Factors	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Consumers purchase organic products since they are rich in nutrients	112	3.54	1.34
Consumers buy organic products because they are toxin free	112	3.61	1.17
Consumers believe that Organic products will help reduce weight	112	3.05	1.29
Consumers believe that Organic products will help detox the body	112	3.39	1.28
Consumers believe that organic products are safe for people having health issues	112	3.07	1.30
Consumers believe that Organic products improve bowel health and promote good sleep	112	3.09	1.49
Consumers believe that Organic products are good for people on a diet	112	3.24	1.48
Consumers believe that Organic products will help reduce the effects of stress	112	3.40	1.37
Consumers believe that Organic products improve the overall health	112	3.40	1.37

4.2 Hypothesis testing

Null Hypothesis (H0): The Lifestyle Assessment and Impact on Consumer Purchase of Organic Products do not significantly correlate with one another.

Table 5: Correlation analysis of lifestyle assessment and impact on consumer purchase of organic products

Parameter	Correlation	Lifestyle Assessment	Impact on Consumer Purchase of Organic Products
Lifestyle Assessment	Pearson Correlation	1	0.714
	Sigma. (2-tailed)	0	0.027
	N	112	112
Impact on Consumer Purchase of Organic Products	Pearson Correlation	0.714	1
	Sigma. (2-tailed)	0.027	
	N	112	112

The Correlation analysis of lifestyle assessment and impact on consumer purchase of organic products is presented in Table 5. It could be inferred that people with a good lifestyle prefer to use organic products to improve their lifestyle, whereas people with a bad lifestyle try to eat organic products to lessen the negative effects of their lifestyle. In any case, people's lifestyles have a significant impact on whether or not they buy organic products.

Null Hypothesis (H0):

There is no significant relationship between the Demographic Factors Impact on Consumer Purchase of Organic Products

Table 6: Chi-Square Analysis

Factors	Pearson Chi-Square Value	df	p-value	Null Hypothesis
Gender	0.070	2	0.966	Accepted
Education	20.571	8	0.008	Rejected
Occupation	5.366	6	0.498	Accepted
Marital Status	4.693	2	0.096	Accepted
Family Size	1.259	2	0.533	Accepted
Household Monthly Income	8.112	4	0.088	Accepted

The Chi-Square analysis that was performed on the demographic variables and the Impact on Consumer Purchase of Organic Products is presented in Table 6. The Pearson Chi-Square Value demographic variables, such as Education (20.571, 0.008) and the Impact on Consumer Purchase of Organic Products, were found to have a significant relationship with the significant p-value. As a result, it has been determined that education has a negligible impact on consumer purchases of organic products. Gender (0.070, 0.966), occupation (5.366, 0.498), marital status (4.693, 0.096),

family size (1.259, 0.533), household monthly income (8.112, 0.088), and the Impact on Consumer Purchase of Organic Products were all found to have no significant relationship with the significant p-value. Gender, occupation, marital status, family size, and household monthly income are all found to have no significant impact on consumer organic product purchases. It could be deduced that, out of the various demographic factors, only education had a significant impact on consumer organic product purchases. This is due to the fact that educated people will be able to recognize the significance of organic products and their effects after use.

The majority of respondents, according to the analysis, have sufficient education to comprehend the benefits of using organic products. Additionally, because many people belong to the middle class, it may be difficult for them to purchase organic products because they are typically quite pricey. According to the lifestyle assessment, most of them have good sleeping patterns, but they don't eat on a regular basis, which could make them sick. The majority of respondents think they aren't fit enough, which will affect how often they buy organic products. Even though the majority of them did not smoke, many of them agreed that drinking alcohol could be harmful to their health. The majority of respondents are anaemic and experience some level of stress. Despite the fact that nearly half of them do not adhere to a diet plan, all of these factors emphasize the importance of eating a healthy organic diet. Organic products are generally regarded as free of toxins and beneficial to overall health. It was discovered that lifestyle has a significant impact on consumer purchase of organic products. It is possible to draw the conclusion that healthy people want to use organic products to improve their health, whereas unhealthy people try to use organic products to lessen the negative effects of their lifestyle. Regardless, customers' lifestyles significantly influence their organic product purchases. It is essential to inform consumers about the advantages of organic products because education is the only demographic factor associated with organic product purchase.

5. Conclusion:

In this paper, we investigate whether people's lifestyles influence their organic product purchases. Since healthy people and people who want to change their lifestyles prefer to eat organic foods, it is possible to draw the conclusion that lifestyle has a significant impact on the purchase of organic products. As a result, consumers believe that eating organic foods is good for their health as a whole. However, it is essential to educate them more about the advantages of organic products. Additionally, using organic products will not suffice for a healthy lifestyle. It is essential for customers to comprehend that only consuming organic products will have a negligible effect on their quality of life, whereas consuming organic products in conjunction with a healthy diet and healthy lifestyle will improve it.

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